

Global Archive of Paleo Sea Level Indicators and Proxies (GAPSLIP), version 2.0

Evan James Gowan

Contents

1	Introduction	7
2	Update history	8
2.1	Version 1.1: October 22, 2021	8
2.2	Version 1.2: March 14, 2022	8
2.3	Version 1.3: July 4, 2022	9
2.4	Version 2.0: May 11, 2023	9
3	Summary of ice and Earth models	9
3.1	Ice models	10
3.2	Earth models	10
4	Paleo-sea level compilations	11
4.1	North America	11
4.2	Europe	11
4.3	Eurasian Arctic	12
4.4	Southeastern Asia	12
4.5	Tropical Corals	12
4.6	Antarctica	12
4.7	Australia	13
4.8	Data locations	14
5	Summary of results	15
5.1	MIS 1 and 2 (LGM to present)	16
5.1.1	Antarctica	16
5.1.2	Australia	16
5.1.3	Caribbean	17
5.1.4	East Asia	18

5.1.5	Eurasian Arctic	18
5.1.6	Europe	19
5.1.7	Greenland	20
5.1.8	North America Arctic	22
5.1.9	North America Atlantic	22
5.1.10	Pacific Islands	23
5.1.11	Proxy Based Sea Level	24
5.1.12	South Asia	24
5.1.13	Southeast Asia	24
5.2	MIS 3 and 4	25
5.2.1	Antarctica	25
5.2.2	Australia	25
5.2.3	Caribbean	25
5.2.4	East Asia	26
5.2.5	Greenland	26
5.2.6	North America Atlantic	26
5.2.7	Pacific Islands	27
5.2.8	Proxy Based Sea Level	27
5.2.9	South Asia	27
5.2.10	Southeast Asia	27
6	MIS 1 and 2 (LGM to present) – Sea level Indicators and Proxies	29
6.1	Antarctica	30
6.1.1	East Antarctica	30
6.1.2	West Antarctica	34
6.2	Australia	36
6.2.1	New South Wales	36
6.2.2	Northern Australia	39

6.2.3	Queensland	44
6.2.4	South Australia	48
6.2.5	Tasmania	51
6.2.6	Western Australia	54
6.3	Caribbean	60
6.3.1	Lesser Antilles	60
6.4	East Asia	61
6.4.1	Ryukyu Islands	61
6.4.2	Sea of Japan - East Sea	61
6.5	Eurasian Arctic	62
6.5.1	Franz Josef Land	62
6.5.2	Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya	63
6.5.3	Southern Barents Sea	69
6.5.4	Western Siberia	70
6.5.5	White Sea	74
6.6	Europe	80
6.6.1	Gulfs Of Riga - Finland	80
6.6.2	North Baltic	88
6.6.3	North Sea	94
6.6.4	Skagerrak - Kattegat	101
6.6.5	South Baltic	108
6.7	Greenland	118
6.7.1	Northeast Greenland	118
6.7.2	Northwest Greenland	128
6.7.3	Southeast Greenland	133
6.7.4	Southwest Greenland	133
6.8	North America Arctic	143
6.8.1	Hudson Bay	143

6.8.2	Hudson Strait	147
6.9	North America Atlantic	149
6.9.1	Eastern United States	149
6.9.2	Labrador	153
6.9.3	Maritimes	154
6.9.4	Newfoundland	162
6.9.5	Northeastern United States	165
6.10	Pacific Islands	169
6.10.1	French Polynesia	169
6.10.2	Melansia	170
6.11	Proxy Based Sea Level	171
6.11.1	Red Sea	171
6.12	South Asia	172
6.12.1	Bay of Bengal	172
6.13	Southeast Asia	173
6.13.1	Java Sea	173
6.13.2	Papua New Guinea	174
6.13.3	South China Sea	175
6.13.4	Sundaland	175
7	MIS 3 and 4 – Sea level Indicators and Proxies	181
7.1	Antarctica	182
7.1.1	East Antarctica	182
7.2	Australia	184
7.2.1	Northern Australia	184
7.2.2	Queensland	185
7.3	Caribbean	187
7.3.1	Lesser Antilles	187

7.4	East Asia	188
7.4.1	Ryukyu Islands	188
7.4.2	Sea of Japan - East Sea	189
7.4.3	Yellow Sea	189
7.5	Greenland	191
7.5.1	Northeast Greenland	191
7.6	North America Atlantic	193
7.6.1	Eastern United States	193
7.7	Pacific Islands	195
7.7.1	French Polynesia	195
7.7.2	Melansia	196
7.8	Proxy Based Sea Level	197
7.8.1	Java Sea	197
7.8.2	Red Sea	197
7.9	South Asia	199
7.9.1	Bay of Bengal	199
7.10	Southeast Asia	200
7.10.1	Papua New Guinea	200
7.10.2	South China Sea	201
7.10.3	Sundaland	201

Bibliography	205
---------------------	------------

1 Introduction

One of the primary ways to assess the quality of paleo ice sheet reconstructions is to calculate the sea level change using a glacial isostatic adjustment (GIA) program, and compare the modelled sea level with records of past relative sea level. By comparing the spatial and temporal pattern of sea level changes, it becomes possible to deduce the history of the evolution of ice sheets. To accomplish this, I have created a framework called the Global Archive of Paleo Sea Level Indicators and Proxies (GAPSLIP). This framework can be found on Github (https://github.com/evangowan/paleo_sea_level), and is constantly being updated with new data. It contains a database of sea level indicators, that give an estimate of the position of past sea level, as well as marine and terrestrial limiting data and other sea level proxies. It also provides scripts to plot the data and put it into a unified report, like the one you are reading now.

There have been recent efforts to compile sea level records into a unified format. Most notably the HOLSEA project has been set up for compiling records of the past 15,000 years (Khan et al., 2019), and the WALIS (World Atlas of Last Interglacial Shorelines) database for the last interglacial period from 115,000 to 130,000 years ago (Rovere et al., 2023). For the HOLSEA project, regional scrutinized datasets have been assembled and placed into spreadsheets. The WALIS is a unified SQL database. At present, the HOLSEA project has many areas without compilations. There is also a lack of data compilations for the period between about 70,000 years ago to 15,000 years ago.

For the purpose of GIA assessment, it is necessary to put these compilations into a format that makes data-model comparison possible. The information provided in the HOLSEA formatted spreadsheets makes it easy to do this, but other datasets found outside of this framework often require additional information that may need to be manually collected. For example, sometimes the location of the data is presented only in a map in the study, so this must be determined using an external program like Google Earth. I have noted all the alterations and additions that were needed before inclusion in the database in the “scratch_datasets” folder in the Github repository.

The framework of this database makes it possible to re-calibrate radiocarbon dates, as many of the compilations were produced prior to the 2020 update of the calibration curves. The Marine20 marine calibration curve (Heaton et al., 2020) invalidated previous reservoir corrections due to a shift in the average ocean age, so it also was necessary to create new corrections via the Calib web tool (<http://calib.org/marine/>). Marine material in this database have been calibrated using Marine20 (Heaton et al., 2020), Northern Hemisphere terrestrial material with IntCal20 (Reimer et al., 2020), and Southern Hemisphere terrestrial material with SHCal20 (Hogg et al., 2020). All radiocarbon dates have been calibrated using OxCal version 4.4.4 (Bronk Ramsey, 2009). The database spreadsheets list the age uncertainty as 1-sigma. In the plots the calibrated ages, and the non-radiocarbon ages, are displayed and analyzed using 2-sigma limits.

Whenever possible, I have tried to track down the original references to the data. This gives credit to the original authors, and also makes it easy for people to find more information if they need it. As of version 2.0, there are 1040 references in the database, most of which are data references. The references are collected in a bibtex file. For non-English studies, I have created fields that include the names, titles and journal names in the original language if available. Titles have been translated using DeepL (<https://www.deepl.com/translator>) when an English title is not given.

2 Update history

This database has its beginnings as a way for me to evaluate ice sheet reconstructions. The first efforts were reported in Gowan et al. (2016), where I first created the scripts and scoring method that I continue to use. This was done in a fairly disorganized way, as it was made in haste without any illusions that it would be expanded into global database. The data used in Gowan et al. (2016) focused on northwestern Canada, but since I have changed the way I organize and assess the data, this is not included in the current database.

Later on, in order to refine the global ice sheet reconstruction reported in Gowan et al. (2021), I was forced by necessity to create a more organized database structure. I included data from Eastern Canada and North America, northern Europe and Asia, southeastern Asia, and a few additional sites that have data between 80,000 and 15,000 years ago. I still largely relied on the scripts and programs created in Gowan et al. (2016), but the plotting was automated to a certain degree. This was considered to be version 1.0 of the database. Further updates are described below.

2.1 Version 1.1: October 22, 2021

This document has been updated to include several additional sites at the LGM and MIS 3. It also has fixed an error in the Cairns and Mackay sites caused by incorrectly subtracting half of the depth range rather than adding it. I apologize for this error. For the coral data for Tahiti and Huon Peninsula, it was originally set to be marine limiting, since the living range was tens of meters. We now use the 2-sigma range determined by Hibbert et al. (2016). We include the interpretations of sea level range by Ishiwa et al. (2019) and Yokoyama et al. (2000) for the Bonaparte Gulf shallow marine/estuary/intertidal data in addition to my conservative marine limiting assignment. I also included the interpreted sea level of Huon Peninsula by de Gelder et al. (2022) for MIS 3 to compare with the coral depth range interpretation by Hibbert et al. (2016). Finally, I also recalibrated all the radiocarbon dates using updated calibration curves published in 2020 (Heaton et al., 2020; Hogg et al., 2020; Reimer et al., 2020).

This update was used in the paper Gowan et al. (2022).

2.2 Version 1.2: March 14, 2022

I have included data from the Baltic Sea (Rosentau et al., 2021) and North Sea (Vink et al., 2007).

2.3 Version 1.3: July 4, 2022

In this update, data from Antarctica are included (Briggs and Tarasov, 2013; Ishiwa et al., 2021). I have also updated the figures so that index points are now drawn as rectangles, rather than the green dots as before. I have used different shades of green depending on whether or not the indicator uncertainty is below or above 10 m.

2.4 Version 2.0: May 11, 2023

This version represents a substantial revision of the database structure. A lot of the analysis and plotting code that was originally written in Bash and Fortran has been rewritten in Python. The map plots are now generated automatically (previously, I manually created the map boundaries). There is now a “scratch_datasets” folder, where I store the spreadsheets with the original data. The scripts in the scratch datasets folder will automatically create the subregions in the “sea_level_data” and extract the reservoir ages from the shapefiles in the GIS folder. The revised Marine20 calibration curve necessitated this move, as it invalidated the old reservoir ages. These changes means that the amount of time for upkeep and future data incorporation is substantially reduced.

This update includes data from Greenland and Australia. The Greenland data was largely compiled by myself, using the list by Lecavalier et al. (2014) as a starting point, but also including data not from that list. Notably, it includes the compilation of isolation basin based sea level indicators by Long et al. (2011). The data for Australia was largely derived from compilations by Lewis et al. (2013), Sloss et al. (2007), Belperio et al. (2002).

3 Summary of ice and Earth models

The main models included here are from PaleoMIST. This is a global ice sheet reconstruction at a very crude 2500 year time step. I have started to use a 500 year linearly interpolated version, which should produce more accurate results in ice covered areas. This interpolation has less impact in far field regions.

For this document, I use PaleoMIST 1.0. The minimal MIS 3 configuration reconstruction is PM_1, while the maximal configuration is PM_1_A.

For the Earth models, I created a shorthand scheme during my PHD, which I have continued to use. A full explanation can be found on the github page:

https://github.com/evangowan/icesheet/blob/master/global/earth_model_format_codes.txt

The full description of each model compared in this document is in this section.

3.1 Ice models

PM_1_A_h - PaleoMIST 1.0 - full MIS 3 Laurentide Ice Sheet scenario, with Hudson Bay fully covered, and ice extent much larger. In this version, the sea level was calculated by linearly interpolating the ice load to 500 year time steps, which should mitigate some of the issues with overpredicting the loading in ice covered regions.

3.2 Earth models

ehgr - 120 km thick lithosphere, 4×10^{20} Pa s upper mantle, 4×10^{22} Pa s lower mantle

4 Paleo-sea level compilations

This is a list of paleo-sea level compilations, which served as the basis for this report. We acknowledge the hard work of the people compiling the data, as well as acknowledging those who collected the original data.

4.1 North America

- Eastern Canada - Vacchi et al. (2018)
- Hudson Bay - Simon et al. (2016)
- Greenland isolation basins - Long et al. (2008)
- Eastern United States north of Georgia - Engelhart and Horton (2012)

For eastern Canada, the database by Vacchi et al. (2018) referred just to compilations (such as Simon et al. (2016)) rather than the original sources. I have tried to track down the original sources as much as possible, but in some cases it was not possible. I made use of the compilations by Simon et al. (2016), Gowan et al. (2016) and an unpublished dataset by A.S. Dyke and T.S. James (some which was summarized in Dyke and Peltier (2000)) to track down references. Some were not listed in any of these compilations, so I had to track it down myself.

The MIS 3-5 data from the east coast of the United States was compiled by Pico et al. (2017).

Most of the data for Greenland was compiled by me, aside from the isolation basin dataset by Long et al. (2008). Though it did not contain a compilation of data, Lecavalier et al. (2014) listed references to a large number of studies that had sea level data. This was used to find the data used in this database. I also did a literature search for studies published after 2013.

4.2 Europe

- Baltic Sea - Rosentau et al. (2021)
- North Sea - Vink et al. (2007)

The Baltic Sea sea level indicators are from (Rosentau et al., 2021). Note that some of the regions that they designated were really large with the gradient of the GIA, so I made smaller regions. This is why the regions in this report do not correspond to theirs in many places. Also note that Rosentau *et al* chose to enter the radiocarbon dates for Ångermanland as pre-calibrated dates. I have not changed them.

The main compilation for the North Sea is by Vink et al. (2007). Though this predates the HOLSEA project, they use the indicative meaning concept and have a rigorous assessment of error, and is compatible with it. For Rotterdam, Netherlands, there is a HOLSEA compilation by Hijma and Cohen (2019). In Langeoog, there is a HOLSEA dataset by Bungenstock et al. (2021). I have also included HOLSEA formatted data from Norderney (Scheder et al., 2022). Western Denmark does not a HOLSEA formatted compilation, so I added data compiled by Gehrels et al. (2006) and Jessen et al. (2019).

4.3 Eurasian Arctic

- Northern Russia - Baranskaya et al. (2018a)

The compilation of sea level indicators for northern Russia comes from Baranskaya et al. (2018a). Thank you to Alisa V. Baranskaya for sending the references (including translations from Russian) that were missing from the published compilation.

4.4 Southeastern Asia

- Southeastern Asia (SEAMIS) - Mann et al. (2019)

The sea level indicators from southeastern Asia were compiled by Mann et al. (2019). I corrected a number of errors, which are listed in the scratch datasets notes.

4.5 Tropical Corals

- Tropical corals - Hibbert et al. (2016)

Corals from tropical regions were compiled by Hibbert et al. (2016). In this report, I have taken indicators for Huon Peninsula, Vanuatu and French Polynesia from this database. An additional interpretation of the Huon Peninsula data comes from de Gelder et al. (2022).

4.6 Antarctica

- East Antarctica - Ishiwa et al. (2021)
- Antarctica - Briggs and Tarasov (2013)

Currently, I have included two compilations from Antarctica. The compilation by Ishiwa et al. (2021) is focused on East Antarctica and includes MIS 3 data. The other is by Briggs and Tarasov (2013), and includes data from both West and East Antarctica for the Holocene. I also added a couple of sites not included in these compilations, including Hjort et al. (1997) and Braddock et al. (2022).

4.7 Australia

- Australia - (Lewis et al., 2013)
- New South Wales - Sloss et al. (2007)
- Queensland - Larcombe et al. (1995)
- South Australia - Belperio et al. (2002)
- Tasmania - Morrison (2019)

The main compilation of Australia is from Lewis et al. (2013). Thanks goes to Stephen E. Lewis, who kindly sent me the spreadsheets from this compilation and allowed me to include them in this database. This database was actually kind of a “database of databases”, which put together state databases, including New South Wales (Sloss et al., 2007), Queensland (Larcombe et al., 1995) and South Australia (Belperio et al., 2002). Tasmania was not included in the Lewis paper because of a lack of studies. There is a compilation of Tasmania in Morrison (2019), which I have included. In addition, I have included the Great Barrier Reef data from Yokoyama et al. (2018) and Bonaparte Gulf from Yokoyama et al. (2000) and Ishiwa et al. (2019).

4.8 Data locations

Figure 1: Map showing the location of data entered into the database.

5 Summary of results

This is a summary of the results of the modelling. There are a total of six models with which are compared. In addition, these tables give how many sea level indicators, number of marine limiting, number of terrestrial limiting, and number of sea level index points.

The sea level is calculated at the location of each data point. To evaluate how well the calculated curve fits the data point, a score is assigned. This metric was originally used by Gowan et al. (2016). The score is the discrepancy, in number of meters, the calculated sea level falls outside of the constraint plus the error bars. A score is zero if the calculated sea level is consistent with the data point. As an example, if the calculated sea level curve is below a terrestrial limiting point, it is given a score of zero. The sum of the scores for each location for each model are shown in the tables. A warning about the scores is that a lower score does not necessarily mean a better fit, as it will depend on the age distribution of the indicators, and the number of indicators of a specific kind. For example, if there are a lot of marine limiting data points, a calculated curve that is over a hundred meters above those indicators may provide a good score, but it is not necessarily a good fit. As a result, it is a good idea to also look at the plotted curves for visual inspection.

5.1 MIS 1 and 2 (LGM to present)

5.1.1 Antarctica

Table 1: Number of data points and model scores for East Antarctica

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	170	94	55	21	559
Langhovde	51	51	0	0	210
Larsemann Hills	12	2	10	0	53
Ongul Islands	36	7	29	0	48
Rauer Group	32	24	8	0	68
Southern Scott Coast	8	1	0	7	145
Terra Nova Bay	13	4	4	5	7
Vestfold Hills	13	5	0	8	1
Windmill Islands	5	0	4	1	27

Table 2: Number of data points and model scores for West Antarctica

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	93	13	54	26	179
James Ross Island	9	9	0	0	0
King George Island	8	0	7	1	10
Marguerite Bay	13	1	12	0	87
Pine Island Bay	63	3	35	25	82

5.1.2 Australia

Table 3: Number of data points and model scores for New South Wales

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	249	139	6	104	228
Lord Howe Island	5	0	0	5	20
Nambucca Heads	5	0	0	5	16
Newcastle	12	0	0	12	51
Sydney	32	3	2	27	43
Ulladulla	74	50	0	24	39
Wollongong	121	86	4	31	59

Table 4: Number of data points and model scores for Northern Australia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	268	39	0	229	564
Bonaparte Gulf	90	19	0	71	211
Bonaparte Gulf SLI	84	20	0	64	135
Ishiwa2019					
Bonaparte Gulf SLI	16	0	0	16	191
Yokoyama2000					
Cambridge Gulf	4	0	0	4	0
Darwin	5	0	0	5	3
Eastern Timor Sea	1	0	0	1	0
Sahul Shelf SLI	2	0	0	2	0
Ishiwa2019					
Sahul Shelf SLI	2	0	0	2	0
Yokoyama2000					
South Alligator River	64	0	0	64	24

Table 5: Number of data points and model scores for Queensland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	1078	62	0	1016	4748
Bowen	57	0	0	57	428
Brisbane	7	0	0	7	20
Cairns	322	6	0	316	1722
Cape Melville	69	18	0	51	237
Gladstone	3	0	0	3	5
Hydrographers Passage	281	38	0	243	590
Sunshine Coast	3	0	0	3	14
Townsville	336	0	0	336	1732

Table 6: Number of data points and model scores for South Australia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	208	80	0	128	511
Franklin Harbour	15	7	0	8	42
Gulf St Vincent	84	32	0	52	197
Port Lincoln	12	2	0	10	37
Redcliff	73	24	0	49	171
Smoky Bay	24	15	0	9	64

Table 7: Number of data points and model scores for Tasmania

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	28	5	7	16	38
Circular Head	1	0	1	0	0
Flinders Island	4	1	0	3	5
Glamorgan-Spring Bay	12	0	0	12	27
Hobart	9	4	4	1	6
King Island	2	0	2	0	0

Table 8: Number of data points and model scores for Western Australia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	176	0	0	176	634
Albany	4	0	0	4	7
Broome	2	0	0	2	2
Bunbury	22	0	0	22	38
Cape Leeuwin	4	0	0	4	6
Esperance	3	0	0	3	7
Exmouth Gulf	17	0	0	17	6
Geraldton	30	0	0	30	69
King Sound	9	0	0	9	0
Perth	63	0	0	63	104
Rowley Shoals	10	0	0	10	370
Shark Bay	12	0	0	12	25

5.1.3 Caribbean

Table 9: Number of data points and model scores for Lesser Antilles

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	196	0	0	196	1029
Barbados	196	0	0	196	1029

5.1.4 East Asia

Table 10: Number of data points and model scores for Ryukyu Islands

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	7	6	1	0	1
Miyakojima	7	6	1	0	1

Table 11: Number of data points and model scores for Sea of Japan - East Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	13	6	0	7	264
Tsushima-Korea Strait	13	6	0	7	264

5.1.5 Eurasian Arctic

Table 12: Number of data points and model scores for Franz Josef Land

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	170	21	0	149	582
Proliv Markama	123	15	0	108	398
Zemlya Georga	44	4	0	40	138
Zemlya Zichy	3	2	0	1	46

Table 13: Number of data points and model scores for Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	90	8	19	63	286
Baydaratskaya Bay	2	0	1	1	4
Gulf of Ob	11	0	8	3	1
Kara Sea shelf	2	2	0	0	0
Khalmyer Bay	5	0	3	2	226
Ostrov Sibiryakova	3	0	3	0	0
Pechora Sea	5	4	1	0	41
Severny Island North	36	0	0	36	12
Severny Island West	19	1	0	18	2
Vaygach Island	3	0	0	3	0
Yuzhny Island	4	1	3	0	0

Table 14: Number of data points and model scores for Southern Barents Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	43	16	1	26	86
Murmansk	21	8	1	12	29
Pechengsky	17	7	0	10	41
Voronya River	5	1	0	4	16

Table 15: Number of data points and model scores for Western Siberia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	125	90	23	12	760
Lena Delta	60	60	0	0	285
New Siberian Islands	8	0	0	8	13
Olenyok Gulf	29	18	11	0	30
Severnaya Zemlya	16	5	11	0	325
West Laptev Sea	10	7	1	2	71
Zhokhov Island	2	0	0	2	36

Table 16: Number of data points and model scores for White Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	177	16	41	120	314
Belomorsk	8	0	7	1	0
Chupa Bay	15	0	3	12	82
Dvina Gulf	82	4	12	66	47
Eastern Kola Peninsula	5	0	5	0	0
Engozero	8	0	1	7	9
Kandalaksha	8	1	0	7	33
Kholmogorsky	3	0	3	0	0
Lesozavodskiy	13	5	0	8	22
Onega Peninsula	9	3	2	4	8
Rugozerskiy Peninsula	15	1	8	6	15
Umba	11	2	0	9	98

5.1.6 Europe

Table 17: Number of data points and model scores for Gulfs Of Riga - Finland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	315	38	174	103	4310
Helsinki	9	0	0	9	151
Hiiumaa	50	14	28	8	437
Lahemaa	7	0	0	7	55
Narva-Luga	58	11	37	10	438
Paldiski	7	0	0	7	80
Parnu	92	3	79	10	1811
Porvoo	10	0	0	10	125
Riga	20	7	13	0	91
Salo	18	0	0	18	343
South Saaremaa	7	0	6	1	156
St Petersburg	1	0	0	1	4
Tallinn	20	0	8	12	382
Virolahti	4	0	0	4	89
Vyborgsky District	6	0	0	6	110
West Gulf Of Riga	6	3	3	0	38

Table 18: Number of data points and model scores for North Baltic

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	76	0	2	74	860
Aland	3	0	0	3	28
Alvsbyn	6	0	2	4	37
Angermanland	14	0	0	14	106
Central Finland	1	0	0	1	20
Gastrikland	16	0	0	16	57
Gunnarsbyn	8	0	0	8	134
Oulu	2	0	0	2	28
Satakunta	1	0	0	1	21
South Lapland	4	0	0	4	29
South Ostrobothnia	3	0	0	3	58
Turku	18	0	0	18	342

Table 19: Number of data points and model scores for North Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	417	20	59	338	757
Belgium	22	0	0	22	65
Bremerhaven	51	0	0	51	41
Central Netherlands	27	0	0	27	105
Dogger Bank	1	0	0	1	16
Elbe	23	0	0	23	6
German Bight	13	0	0	13	49
Ho Bugt	20	0	0	20	26
Langeoog	1	0	0	1	0
Limfjord	27	20	7	0	23
Netherlands Wadden Sea	5	0	0	5	12
Norderney	56	0	0	56	33
Oyster Ground	2	0	0	2	3
Rotterdam	165	0	52	113	368
Southern Bight	4	0	0	4	10

Table 20: Number of data points and model scores for Skagerrak - Kattegat

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	339	200	107	32	346
Asa	5	0	0	5	64
Bohuslan	5	0	0	5	25
Goteborg	2	0	0	2	33
Halmstad	1	0	0	1	16
Kattegat	26	26	0	0	0
Kieler Bucht	3	3	0	0	19
Laesoe	3	2	0	1	1
Lillebaelt	25	14	11	0	67
Samso Belt	66	47	8	11	9
Storebaelt	65	25	38	2	46
Copenhagen	78	28	49	1	35
Treoa Moellebugt	4	4	0	0	0
Vendsyssel Thy	56	51	1	4	31

Table 21: Number of data points and model scores for South Baltic

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	489	112	206	171	1586
Achterwasser	26	0	6	20	76
Arkona Basin East	30	29	0	1	205
Arkona Basin West	24	12	11	1	52
Baltic South	2	2	0	0	7
Baltic Southwest	7	6	0	1	6
Blekinge	38	2	10	26	117
Curonian Spit	1	1	0	0	0
Fakse Bugt	11	7	4	0	132
Havang	54	1	43	10	84
Lithuania	43	25	18	0	142
Lubeck	69	18	36	15	290
Ostergotland	6	0	0	6	29
Rugen	53	5	8	40	211
Salt Meadows	43	0	1	42	110
Sodermanland	9	0	0	9	44
South Vistula	49	2	47	0	27
Ustka	2	0	2	0	0
Ventspils	5	1	4	0	48
West Gulf Of Gdansk	17	1	16	0	6

5.1.7 Greenland

Table 22: Number of data points and model scores for Northeast Greenland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	534	443	29	62	6881
Cape Morris Jesup	73	67	6	0	841
Danmarks Fjord	30	27	0	3	733
Frederick E Hyde Fjord	16	14	1	1	259
Germania Land	14	14	0	0	255
Hochstetter Forland	20	12	8	0	228
Hold With Hope	17	16	0	1	84
Independence Fjord	12	11	1	0	69
JP Koch Fjord	2	2	0	0	33
Jameson Land	17	12	5	0	57
Kap Clarence Wyckoff	32	29	0	3	795
Kempes Fjord	10	10	0	0	31
Kong Oscars Fjord	53	50	0	3	183
Nansen land	6	6	0	0	90
Nioghalvfjærdsfjorden	17	17	0	0	220
Prinsesse Ingeborg Halvø	67	63	1	3	1102
Renland	5	4	1	0	0
Schuchert Dal	97	63	0	34	1631
Traill Oe	19	18	0	1	94
Young Sound	27	8	6	13	176

Table 23: Number of data points and model scores for Northwest Greenland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	150	81	6	63	2035
Bessel Fjord	36	3	0	33	373
Cass Fjord	16	15	1	0	122
Hall Land	66	37	0	29	528
Inglefield Fjord	10	6	4	0	191
Nordvestøe	3	3	0	0	93
Thule	11	10	0	1	668
Tuttulissuaq	1	0	1	0	0
Warming Land	4	4	0	0	51
Wulff land	3	3	0	0	9

Table 24: Number of data points and model scores for Southeast Greenland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	6	0	2	4	20
Ammassalik	6	0	2	4	20

Table 25: Number of data points and model scores for Southwest Greenland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	320	114	59	147	11283
Akulliit	24	10	1	13	719
Alluttoq Island	10	0	2	8	284
Eqalussuit Tasiat	5	5	0	0	252
Ikertooq Fjord	7	5	0	2	416
Ilulissat	12	2	3	7	201
Itilleq	11	2	0	9	265
Kangerluk	9	0	0	9	447
Kangerlussuaq	34	20	4	10	935
Kannala	33	3	3	27	1125
Kapisillit	26	8	17	1	235
Maniitsoq	5	5	0	0	251
Nanortalik	24	0	0	24	917
Nuuk	44	25	19	0	1096
Paamiut	10	0	1	9	541
Qaqortoq	30	11	0	19	1410
Qeqertarsuatsiaat	11	11	0	0	730
Sisimiut	12	3	0	9	1215
Tasiussarsuaq	13	4	9	0	244

5.1.8 North America Arctic

Table 26: Number of data points and model scores for Hudson Bay

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr
Total	243	114	68	61	2508
Churchill	23	10	7	6	122
East James Bay	36	20	9	7	589
Inukjuak	21	11	2	8	72
Ivujivik	21	14	2	5	40
Kivalliq	31	21	5	5	226
Umiujaq	94	34	33	27	1358
West James Bay	17	4	10	3	101

Table 27: Number of data points and model scores for Hudson Strait

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr
Total	86	65	18	3	943
Kangiqtujuaq	14	13	1	0	138
Southern Ungava Bay	7	2	2	3	106
Sugluk	40	30	10	0	572
Western Ungava Bay	25	20	5	0	127

5.1.9 North America Atlantic

Table 28: Number of data points and model scores for Eastern United States

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr
Total	357	138	38	181	919
Eastern Shore	28	7	6	15	72
Inner Chesapeake	106	99	0	7	176
Inner Delaware	38	2	8	28	104
Northern North Carolina	60	23	6	31	225
Northern South Carolina	18	0	8	10	48
Outer Delaware	60	5	5	50	172
Southern North Carolina	24	2	3	19	40
Southern South Carolina	23	0	2	21	82

Table 29: Number of data points and model scores for Labrador

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM ₁ A _h ehgr
Total	61	16	45	0	230
Hamilton Inlet	15	3	12	0	0
Lake Melville	12	4	8	0	5
Nain	16	2	14	0	8
Torngat	18	7	11	0	217

Table 30: Number of data points and model scores for Maritimes

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	533	121	122	290	1654
Anticosti Island	24	13	3	8	252
Cape Breton	16	4	7	5	9
Chaleur Bay	15	10	5	0	5
Cumberland	112	6	15	91	54
Forestville	59	18	7	34	294
Halifax	48	15	4	29	11
Magdalen Islands	22	2	11	9	8
Passamaquoddy Bay	28	8	11	9	23
Prince Edward Island	31	9	6	16	27
Quebec City	69	18	28	23	148
Rimouski	90	17	15	58	818
Sable Island	10	1	6	3	3
Shelburne	9	0	4	5	2

Table 31: Number of data points and model scores for Newfoundland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	160	53	61	46	372
Avalon Peninsula	13	3	5	5	4
Bay Of Islands	16	5	3	8	18
Great Northern Peninsula	56	16	23	17	208
Notre Dame Bay	29	12	13	4	20
Port Aux Basques	46	17	17	12	122

Table 32: Number of data points and model scores for Northeastern United States

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	479	51	117	311	1273
Connecticut	95	0	41	54	85
Eastern Maine	49	0	4	45	104
Long Island	25	0	6	19	129
New Jersey	62	6	11	45	200
New York	76	6	19	51	260
Northern Massachusetts	43	3	16	24	70
Southern Maine	86	24	6	56	331
Southern Massachusetts	43	12	14	17	94

5.1.10 Pacific Islands

Table 33: Number of data points and model scores for French Polynesia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	191	0	0	191	157
Mururoa	12	0	0	12	119
Tahiti	179	0	0	179	38

Table 34: Number of data points and model scores for Melansia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	82	11	0	71	19
Vanuatu	82	11	0	71	19

5.1.11 Proxy Based Sea Level

Table 35: Number of data points and model scores for Red Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	165	0	0	165	29
Bab-el-Mandeb proxy	165	0	0	165	29

5.1.12 South Asia

Table 36: Number of data points and model scores for Bay of Bengal

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	5	4	0	1	5
Ganges Delta	5	4	0	1	5

5.1.13 Southeast Asia

Table 37: Number of data points and model scores for Java Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	72	18	2	52	319
Belitung Island	25	0	0	25	114
Central Java	6	0	0	6	31
South Sulawesi	41	18	2	21	174

Table 38: Number of data points and model scores for Papua New Guinea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	58	35	0	23	14
Huon Peninsula	58	35	0	23	14

Table 39: Number of data points and model scores for South China Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	2	0	2	0	0
Xisha Islands	2	0	2	0	0

Table 40: Number of data points and model scores for Sundaland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	375	88	104	183	606
Ca Na	18	7	8	3	37
Chao Phraya	33	5	9	19	89
East Malay Peninsula	4	3	1	0	7
Mekong Delta	71	2	24	45	49
Phuket	40	20	13	7	41
Southeast Malay Peninsula	13	12	0	1	36
Strait Of Malacca	137	29	45	63	164
Sunda Shelf	49	7	3	39	163
Thale Noi	3	0	1	2	6
Vietnam Shelf	5	1	0	4	12
West Malay Peninsula	2	2	0	0	2

5.2 MIS 3 and 4

5.2.1 Antarctica

Table 41: Number of data points and model scores for East Antarctica

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	68	62	6	0	2723
Langhovde	19	19	0	0	813
Larsemann Hills	5	1	4	0	50
Ongul Islands	35	35	0	0	1683
Rauer Group	9	7	2	0	177

5.2.2 Australia

Table 42: Number of data points and model scores for Northern Australia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	11	3	0	8	217
Bonaparte Gulf	4	1	0	3	81
Bonaparte Gulf SLI	4	2	0	2	55
Ishiwa2019					
Bonaparte Gulf SLI Yokoyama2000	3	0	0	3	81

Table 43: Number of data points and model scores for Queensland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	74	22	0	52	744
Cairns	45	11	0	34	646
Hydrographers Passage	28	11	0	17	82
Townsville	1	0	0	1	16

5.2.3 Caribbean

Table 44: Number of data points and model scores for Lesser Antilles

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	8	0	0	8	174
Barbados	8	0	0	8	174

5.2.4 East Asia

Table 45: Number of data points and model scores for Ryukyu Islands

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	76	70	0	6	8
Kikaijima 1.9 mm	38	35	0	3	0
Kikaijima 2.1 mm	38	35	0	3	8

Table 46: Number of data points and model scores for Sea of Japan - East Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	4	1	1	2	77
Tsushima-Korea Strait	4	1	1	2	77

Table 47: Number of data points and model scores for Yellow Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	11	11	0	0	2
South Bohai Sea	4	4	0	0	2
Yellow Sea	7	7	0	0	0

5.2.5 Greenland

Table 48: Number of data points and model scores for Northeast Greenland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	9	9	0	0	201
Cape Morris Jesup	4	4	0	0	82
Kap Clarence Wyckoff	4	4	0	0	78
Nansen land	1	1	0	0	41

5.2.6 North America Atlantic

Table 49: Number of data points and model scores for Eastern United States

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	23	5	15	3	104
Eastern Shore	6	1	5	0	13
Northern North Carolina	14	4	7	3	91
Southern North Carolina	3	0	3	0	0

5.2.7 Pacific Islands

Table 50: Number of data points and model scores for French Polynesia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	19	0	0	19	224
Mururoa	2	0	0	2	0
Tahiti	17	0	0	17	224

Table 51: Number of data points and model scores for Melansia

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	6	0	0	6	25
Vanuatu	6	0	0	6	25

5.2.8 Proxy Based Sea Level

Table 52: Number of data points and model scores for Java Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	15	0	15	0	0
Karimata Strait proxy	15	0	15	0	0

Table 53: Number of data points and model scores for Red Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	318	0	0	318	5175
Bab-el-Mandeb proxy	318	0	0	318	5175

5.2.9 South Asia

Table 54: Number of data points and model scores for Bay of Bengal

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	2	1	0	1	27
Ganges Delta	2	1	0	1	27

5.2.10 Southeast Asia

Table 55: Number of data points and model scores for Papua New Guinea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	52	0	0	52	115
Huon Peninsula	40	0	0	40	55
Huon Peninsula de Gelder	12	0	0	12	60

Table 56: Number of data points and model scores for South China Sea

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	1	0	1	0	19
Xisha Islands	1	0	1	0	19

Table 57: Number of data points and model scores for Sundaland

Location	number data	marine limiting	terrestrial limiting	index point	PM_1_A_h ehgr
Total	33	14	17	2	283
Berhala Strait	2	0	1	1	16
Chao Phraya	3	3	0	0	77
Mekong Delta	1	1	0	0	20
Strait Of Malacca	11	2	9	0	10
Sunda Shelf	15	7	7	1	160
Vietnam Shelf	1	1	0	0	0

6 MIS 1 and 2 (LGM to present) – Sea level Indicators and Proxies

The Holocene (roughly equivalent to MIS 1) spans from 11.65 kyr before present to present. MIS 2 encompasses the Last Glacial Maximum (27-19 kyr BP) and the deglacial period that goes until the end of the Younger Dryas. In general, paleo sea level proxies are abundant in the Holocene, when sea level was within 30 m of present, but are uncommon before that. The lack of proxies older than the Holocene is in a large part due to their inaccessibility (in water too deep for typical coring methods). In most cases, MIS 2 aged sea level proxies are from drowned coral reefs in tropical areas, or in relatively broad continental shelves.

6.1 Antarctica

6.1.1 East Antarctica

Figure 2: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Langhovde. References: Hayashi and Yoshida (1994); Hirakawa and Sawagaki (1998); Igarashi et al. (1995a,b); Ishiwa et al. (2021); Maemoku et al. (1997); Miura et al. (1998); Verleyen et al. (2017).

Figure 3: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Larsemann Hills. References: Hodgson et al. (2009); Ishiwa et al. (2021); Verleyen et al. (2005).

Figure 4: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Ongul Islands. References: Hirakawa and Sawagaki (1998); Ishiwa et al. (2021); Miura et al. (1998); Verleyen et al. (2017).

Figure 5: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Rauer Group. References: Berg et al. (2010a,b, 2016); Hodgson et al. (2016); Ishiwa et al. (2021).

Figure 6: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Southern Scott Coast. References: Briggs and Tarasov (2013); Hall et al. (2004).

Figure 7: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Terra Nova Bay. References: Baroni and Hall (2004); Briggs and Tarasov (2013).

Figure 8: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Vestfold Hills. References: Briggs and Tarasov (2013); Zhang and Peterson (1984); Zwartz et al. (1998).

Figure 9: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Windmill Islands. References: Briggs and Tarasov (2013); Goodwin (1993); Goodwin and Zweck (2000).

6.1.2 West Antarctica

Figure 10: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: West Antarctica, location: James Ross Island. References: Hjort et al. (1997).

Figure 11: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: West Antarctica, location: King George Island. References: Barsch and Mäusbacher (1986); Bentley et al. (2005); Briggs and Tarasov (2013); Del Valle et al. (2002); Martinez-Macchiavello et al. (1996); Schmidt et al. (1990).

Figure 12: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: West Antarctica, location: Marguerite Bay. References: Bentley et al. (2005); Briggs and Tarasov (2013); Emslie and McDaniel (2002); Wasell and Håkansson (1992).

Figure 13: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: West Antarctica, location: Pine Island Bay. References: Braddock et al. (2022); Johnson et al. (2008); Lindow et al. (2014).

6.2 Australia

6.2.1 New South Wales

Figure 14: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: New South Wales, location: Lord Howe Island. References: Lewis et al. (2013); Woodroffe et al. (2010).

Figure 15: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: New South Wales, location: Nambucca Heads. References: Baker et al. (2001a,b); Flood and Frankel (1989); Haworth et al. (2002); Lewis et al. (2013); Sloss et al. (2007).

Figure 16: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: New South Wales, location: Newcastle. References: Baker et al. (2001a,b); Gillespie and Temple (1976); Haworth et al. (2002); Lewis et al. (2013); Sloss et al. (2007); Thom and Chappell (1975); Thom and Roy (1983).

Figure 17: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: New South Wales, location: Sydney. References: Baker et al. (2001a); Baker and Haworth (2000, 1997); Baker et al. (2001b); Haworth et al. (2002); Lewis et al. (2013); Roy and Crawford (1981); Sloss et al. (2007); Thom and Chappell (1975); Thom and Roy (1983); Thom et al. (1969).

Figure 18: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: New South Wales, location: Ulladulla. References: Baker et al. (2001b); Haworth et al. (2002); Lewis et al. (2013); Sloss et al. (2004); Sloss (2005); Sloss et al. (2006, 2007, 2019); Thom and Chappell (1975).

Figure 19: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: New South Wales, location: Wollongong. References: Bryant et al. (1992); Carne (1981); Jones et al. (1979); Jones (1990); Lewis et al. (2013); Murray-Wallace et al. (2000); Panayotou (2004); Sloss et al. (2004); Sloss (2005); Sloss et al. (2006, 2007); Umitsu et al. (2001); Young et al. (1993).

6.2.2 Northern Australia

Figure 20: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Bonaparte Gulf. References: Hubbs and Bien (1967); Ishiwa et al. (2019); Lewis et al. (2013); Nicholas et al. (2014); van Andel et al. (1967); Yokoyama et al. (2000).

Figure 21: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Bonaparte Gulf (Ishiwa *et al.* 2019 interpretation). References: Ishiwa et al. (2019); Yokoyama et al. (2000).

Figure 22: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Bonaparte Gulf (Yokoyama *et al.* 2000 interpretation). References: Yokoyama *et al.* (2000).

Figure 23: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Cambridge Gulf. References: Lewis *et al.* (2013); Thom *et al.* (1975).

Figure 24: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Darwin. References: Lewis et al. (2013); Nott (1996).

Figure 25: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Eastern Timor Sea. References: Nicholas et al. (2014).

Figure 26: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Sahul Shelf (Ishiwa *et al.* 2019 interpretation). References: Yokoyama *et al.* (2000).

Figure 27: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Sahul Shelf (Yokoyama *et al.* 2000 interpretation). References: Yokoyama *et al.* (2000).

Figure 28: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: South Alligator River. References: Lewis et al. (2013); Woodroffe et al. (1986, 1985, 1987).

6.2.3 Queensland

Figure 29: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Bowen. References: Belperio (1978, 1979); Blake (1994); Chappell et al. (1983); Harris et al. (1990); Heap et al. (2002); Hopley (1980, 1983); Hopley et al. (1978, 1983); Larcombe et al. (1995); Lewis et al. (2013); Thom et al. (1969); Way (1987).

Figure 30: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Brisbane. References: Flood (1983); Hekel et al. (1979); Hofmann (1980); Jones et al. (1978); Lewis et al. (2013).

Figure 31: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Cairns. References: Bird (1971); Chappell et al. (1983); Crowley et al. (1990); Gagan (1990); Gagan et al. (1994); Grant-Taylor and Rafter (1963); Johnson and Carter (1987); Larcombe et al. (1995); Lewis et al. (2013); Partain and Hopley (1989); Yokoyama et al. (2018); Zwartz (1995).

Figure 32: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Cape Melville. References: Chappell et al. (1983); Higley (2000); Lewis et al. (2013); Salama (1991); Zwartz (1995).

Figure 33: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Gladstone. References: Flood (1983); Lewis et al. (2013); Yokoyama et al. (2006).

Figure 34: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Hydrographers Passage. References: Yokoyama et al. (2018).

Figure 35: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Sunshine Coast. References: Lewis et al. (2013); Thom et al. (1969); Wood (1972).

Figure 36: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Townsville. References: Beaman et al. (1994); Belperio (1978, 1979); Carter et al. (1993); Chappell et al. (1983); Gill and Hopley (1972); Grindrod and Rhodes (1984); Harris et al. (1990); Higley (2000); Hopley (1980, 1983); Hopley et al. (1983); Johnson et al. (1984); Johnson and Risk (1987); Larcombe and Carter (1998); Larcombe et al. (1995); Lewis et al. (2008, 2013, 2015); Ohlenbusch (1991); Pye and Rhodes (1985); Spenceley (1980); Tye (1992); Walbran (1991); Woodroffe (2009); Yu and Zhao (2010); Zwartz (1995).

6.2.4 South Australia

Figure 37: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Australia, location: Franklin Harbour. References: Belperio et al. (2002); Lewis et al. (2013); Short et al. (1986).

Figure 38: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Australia, location: Gulf St Vincent. References: Belperio (1993); Belperio et al. (1983, 2002); Cann et al. (1988, 1993); Lewis et al. (2013); Murray-Wallace et al. (1993).

Figure 39: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Australia, location: Port Lincoln. References: Belperio et al. (2002); Lewis et al. (2013); Short et al. (1986).

Figure 40: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Australia, location: Redcliff. References: Belperio et al. (1984, 2002); Harvey et al. (1999); Lewis et al. (2013).

Figure 41: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Australia, location: Smoky Bay. References: Belperio et al. (2002); Lewis et al. (2013); Murray-Wallace et al. (1993); Short et al. (1986).

6.2.5 Tasmania

Figure 42: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Tasmania, location: Circular Head. References: Morrison (2019); Murray-Wallace and Goede (1995).

Figure 43: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Tasmania, location: Flinders Island. References: Morrison (2019); Murray-Wallace and Goede (1995).

Figure 44: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Tasmania, location: Glamorgan-Spring Bay. References: Gehrels et al. (2012); Morrison (2019).

Figure 45: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Tasmania, location: Hobart. References: Clark et al. (2011); Morrison (2019).

Figure 46: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Tasmania, location: King Island. References: Morrison (2019); Murray-Wallace and Goede (1995).

6.2.6 Western Australia

Figure 47: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Albany. References: Baker et al. (2005); Lewis et al. (2013).

Figure 48: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Broome. References: Hearty et al. (2006); Lessa and Masselink (2006); Lewis et al. (2013).

Figure 49: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Bunbury. References: Baker et al. (2005); Buckley and Valdes-Pages (1981); Lewis et al. (2013); Searle and Logan (1978); Semeniuk (1985, 1996).

Figure 50: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Cape Leeuwin. References: Baker et al. (2005); Lewis et al. (2013); Sas (1974).

Figure 51: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Esperance. References: Baker et al. (2005); Lewis et al. (2013).

Figure 52: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Exmouth Gulf. References: Lewis et al. (2013); Logan et al. (1970); Twigg and Collins (2010).

Figure 53: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Geraldton. References: Collins et al. (2006); Eisenhauer et al. (1993); Lewis et al. (2013); Veeh and France (1988); Wyrwoll (1977).

Figure 54: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: King Sound. References: Jennings (1975); Lewis et al. (2013).

Figure 55: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Perth. References: Baker et al. (2001b, 2005); Brown et al. (1980); Deevey et al. (1959); Gillespie and Temple (1976); Kendrick (1977); Kigoshi et al. (1973); Lewis et al. (2013); Playford (1988); Searle and Woods (1986); Searle et al. (1988); Tamers et al. (1964).

Figure 56: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Rowley Shoals. References: James et al. (2004); Lewis et al. (2013).

Figure 57: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Australia, location: Shark Bay. References: Lewis et al. (2013); Logan et al. (1970); Noakes and Brandau (1971); Noakes et al. (1967, 1968); Read (1974).

6.3 Caribbean

6.3.1 Lesser Antilles

Figure 58: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Lesser Antilles, location: Barbados. References: Abdul et al. (2016); Fairbanks (1988); Fairbanks et al. (2005); Mortlock et al. (2005, 2016); Peltier and Fairbanks (2006).

6.4 East Asia

6.4.1 Ryukyu Islands

Figure 59: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Ryukyu Islands, location: Miyakojima. References: Sasaki et al. (2006).

6.4.2 Sea of Japan - East Sea

Figure 60: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sea of Japan - East Sea, location: Tsushima-Korea Strait. References: Park et al. (2000).

6.5 Eurasian Arctic

6.5.1 Franz Josef Land

Figure 61: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Franz Josef Land, location: Proliv Markama. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov et al. (2009); Forman and Polyak (1997); Forman et al. (1996, 2004); Grosswald (1963); Grosswald et al. (1973); Gusev et al. (2013b); Kovaleva (1974); Lubinski (1998); Weihe (1996).

Figure 62: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Franz Josef Land, location: Zemlya Georga. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov et al. (2009); Dibner (1965); Forman et al. (1996, 2004); Glazovskiy et al. (1992); Grosswald et al. (1973); Kovaleva (1974).

Figure 63: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Franz Josef Land, location: Zemlya Zichy. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov et al. (2009).

6.5.2 Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya

Figure 64: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Baydaratskaya Bay. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Belova (2012); Romanenko et al. (2007).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 65: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Gulf of Ob. References: Astakhov and Nazarov (2010); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Makeev (1988); Makeev et al. (1988).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 66: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Kara Sea shelf. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Levitan et al. (2007); Polyakova and Stein (2004).

Figure 67: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Khalmyer Bay. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a,b); Grigorieva (1987).

Figure 68: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Ostrov Sibiryakova. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Gusev et al. (2013a).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point ($\leq 10\text{m}$)
 - Index point ($> 10\text{m}$)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 69: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Pechora Sea. References: Astakhov et al. (2007); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Krapivner (2006); Polyak et al. (2000); Zhuravlev et al. (2013).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point ($\leq 10\text{m}$)
 - Index point ($> 10\text{m}$)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 70: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Severny Island North. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Forman et al. (1999, 2004); Gawronski and Zeeberg (1997); Zeeberg et al. (2001).

Figure 71: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Severny Island West. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov et al. (2009); Forman et al. (1999, 2004); Zeeberg et al. (2001).

Figure 72: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Vaygach Island. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Forman et al. (2004); Zeeberg et al. (2001).

Figure 73: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Kara Sea - Novaya Zemlya, location: Yuzhny Island. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov et al. (2006); Mangerud et al. (2008); Zhuravlev et al. (2013).

6.5.3 Southern Barents Sea

Figure 74: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southern Barents Sea, location: Murmansk. References: Arslanov et al. (1974); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Corner et al. (2001); Gurevich and Liyva (1975); Gurina (1971); Mityaev M. V. (2008); Tanner (1907).

Figure 75: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southern Barents Sea, location: Pechengsky. References: Arslanov et al. (1974); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Corner et al. (1999); Koshechkin (1979).

Figure 76: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southern Barents Sea, location: Voronya River. References: Arslanov et al. (1974); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Snyder et al. (1997).

6.5.4 Western Siberia

Figure 77: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Siberia, location: Lena Delta. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Makarov (2009).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 78: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Siberia, location: New Siberian Islands. References: Anisimov et al. (2009a); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov et al. (2013); Polyakova et al. (2005).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 79: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Siberia, location: Olenyok Gulf. References: Andreev et al. (2004); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov et al. (2013); Makarov (2009).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 80: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Siberia, location: Severnaya Zemlya. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bolshiyarov and Makeev (1995); Raab et al. (2003).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 81: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Siberia, location: West Laptev Sea. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Bauch et al. (1999); Bolshiyarov et al. (2013); Winterfeld et al. (2011).

Figure 82: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Western Siberia, location: Zhokhov Island. References: Anisimov et al. (2009b); Baranskaya et al. (2018a).

6.5.5 White Sea

Figure 83: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Belomorsk. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Devyatova and Liyva (1971); Koshechkin (1979); Lunkka et al. (2012).

Figure 84: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Chupa Bay. References: Baranskaya and Romanenko (2015); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Kolka et al. (2015).

Figure 85: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Dvina Gulf. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Koshechkin (1979); Zaretskaya et al. (2011).

Figure 86: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Eastern Kola Peninsula. References: Arslanov et al. (1974); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Koshechkin (1979).

Figure 87: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Engozero. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Kolka et al. (2013b).

Figure 88: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Kandalaksha. References: Arslanov et al. (1974); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Kolka and Korsakova (2010); Koshechkin (1979).

Figure 89: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Kholmogorsky. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Larsen et al. (2006).

Figure 90: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Lesozavodskiy. References: Arslanov et al. (1974); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Kolka et al. (2005); Koshechkin et al. (1973).

Figure 91: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Onega Peninsula. References: Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Boyarskaya et al. (1986); Koshechkin et al. (1973); Repkina et al. (in review).

Figure 92: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Rugozerkiy Peninsula. References: Baranskaya (2015); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Repkina and Romanenko (2016); Romanenko and Shilova (2012); Zaretskaya et al. (2013).

Figure 93: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: White Sea, location: Umba. References: Arslanov et al. (1974); Baranskaya et al. (2018a); Kolka et al. (2013a); Koshechkin (1979).

6.6 Europe

6.6.1 Gulfs Of Riga - Finland

Figure 94: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Helsinki. References: Alhonen (1972); Alhonen et al. (1978); Hyvärinen (1979, 1982, 1984); Rosentau et al. (2021); Seppä et al. (2000).

Figure 95: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Hiiumaa. References: Kriiska (2002); Kriiska and Lõugas (1999); Kriiska et al. (2005); Königsson et al. (1998); Liiva et al. (1966); Rosentau et al. (2020, 2021); Sarv (1981); Vassiljev et al. (2015).

Figure 96: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Lahemaa. References: Grudzinska et al. (2013); Muru et al. (2017); Rosentau et al. (2021); Saarse et al. (2009).

Figure 97: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Narva-Luga. References: Jaanits and Liiva (1973); Kessel (1963); Kriiska (1995, 1996); Lepland et al. (1996); Rosentau et al. (2013, 2021); Saarse et al. (2003); Sandgren et al. (2004).

Figure 98: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Paldiski. References: Grudzinska et al. (2013); Muru et al. (2017); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 99: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Parnu. References: H. (1975); Habicht et al. (2017); Haila and Raukas (1992); Hyvärinen et al. (1992); Ilves et al. (1974); Jaanits and Jaanits (1978); Jonuks (2013, 2016); Kessel and Punning (1969a,b, 1974); Kriiska (2001); Kriiska and Lõugas (2009); Kriiska et al. (2002); Nirgi et al. (2020); Orru et al. (1992); Poska and Veski (1999); Punning et al. (1971, 1977); Raukas et al. (1995, 1999); Rosentau et al. (2011, 2021); Saarse et al. (2003); Veski (1998); Veski et al. (2005).

Figure 100: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Porvoo. References: Donner and Eronen (1981); Eronen (1974); Haila et al. (1991); Jungner and Sonninen (1983); Miettinen et al. (1999); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 101: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Riga. References: Eberhards (2008); Grudzinska (2015); Grudzinska et al. (2017); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 102: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Salo. References: Eronen (1974); Eronen et al. (1993, 2001); Glückert (1976, 1978b); Leino (1973); Ristaniemi and Glückert (1988); Rosentau et al. (2021); Tolonen and Tolonen (1988).

Figure 103: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: South Saaremaa. References: Reintam et al. (2008); Rosentau et al. (2021); Saarse et al. (2009).

Figure 104: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: St Petersburg. References: Morozov (2014); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 105: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Tallinn. References: Grudzinska et al. (2014); Heinsalu (2000); Lõugas and Tomek (2013); Muru et al. (2017); Rosentau et al. (2021); Saarse et al. (2006, 2009); Veski (1998).

Figure 106: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Virolahti. References: Miettinen (2002); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 107: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: Vyborgsky District. References: Miettinen et al. (2007); Morozov (2014); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 108: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Gulfs Of Riga - Finland, location: West Gulf Of Riga. References: Eberhards (2006); Grudzinska (2011); Pujäte (2015); Punning et al. (1973); Rosentau et al. (2021); Veinbergs (1996).

6.6.2 North Baltic

Figure 109: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Aland. References: Glückert (1978a); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 110: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Alvsbyn. References: Lindén et al. (2006); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 111: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Angermanland. References: Berglund (2004, 2008); Rosentau et al. (2021); Wallin (1994).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 112: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Central Finland. References: Ristaniemi (1987); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 113: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Gastrikland. References: Berglund (2005, 2010, 2012); Hedenström and Risberg (2003); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 114: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Gunnarsbyn. References: Lindén et al. (2006); Rosentau et al. (2021).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 115: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Oulu. References: Eronen (1974); Rosentau et al. (2021).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 116: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Satakunta. References: Rosentau et al. (2021); Salomaa (1982).

Figure 117: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: South Lapland. References: Eronen (1974); Rosentau et al. (2021); Saarnisto (1981).

Figure 118: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: South Ostrobothnia. References: Eronen (1974); Glückert et al. (1993); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 119: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Baltic, location: Turku. References: Eronen (1974); Eronen et al. (1982, 1995, 2001); Glückert (1976); Glückert et al. (1992); Rosentau et al. (2021).

6.6.3 North Sea

Figure 120: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Belgium. References: Denys and Baeteman (1995); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 121: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Bremerhaven. References: Behre et al. (1975); Behre (2003, 2007); Behre and Kučan (1999); Brandt (1980, 1991); Ey (1995); Haarnagel (1979); Hanisch (1980); Körber-Grohne (1967); Ludwig et al. (1981); Preuss (1979); Schmid (1994); Schütte (1939); Sindowski (1969); Strahl (2002a,b); Streif (1981, 1984, 1985, 1986); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 122: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Central Netherlands. References: Bennema (1954); Jelgersma (1961); Louwe Kooijmans (1976); Makaske et al. (2003); Roeleveld and Gotjé (1993); van de Plassche (1982); van de Plassche et al. (2005); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 123: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Dogger Bank. References: Behre (2003, 2007); Behre and Menke (1969); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 124: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Elbe. References: Bantelmann (1960, 1966, 1975); Bantelmann et al. (1984); Behre (2003, 2007); Behre et al. (1979); Brandt (1980); Higelke et al. (1984); Linke (1982); Meier (2001a,b); Menke (1976, 1988); Rohde (1975); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 125: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: German Bight. References: Behre (2003, 2007); Ludwig et al. (1979); Menke (1996); Streif et al. (1983); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 126: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Ho Bugt. References: Gehrels et al. (2006).

Figure 127: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Langeoog. References: Barckhausen (1969); Behre (2003, 2007); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 128: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Limfjord. References: Jessen et al. (2019); Nielsen (2010, 2013); Petersen (1975, 1981, 1985, 1998); Petersen and von Platen-Hallermund (2018).

Figure 129: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Netherlands Wadden Sea. References: Griede (1978); Jelgersma (1961); Louwe Kooijmans (1976); van de Plassche (1982); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 130: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Norderney. References: Barckhausen (1984); Behre (1970, 2003, 2007); Brandt (1980); Freund and Streif (2000); Haarnagel (1957, 1969, 1980); Reinhardt (1965); Scheder et al. (2019, 2022); Streif (1986); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 131: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Oyster Ground. References: Behre and Irion (1984); Behre (2003); Jelgersma (1979); Kiden et al. (2002); Vink et al. (2007).

Figure 132: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Rotterdam. References: Bennema (1954); Berendsen et al. (2007); Hijma and Cohen (2010, 2019); Hijma et al. (2009); Jelgersma (1961); Kiden (1989, 1995); Louwe Kooijmans (1976); Louwe Kooijmans and van de Velde (1980); Slupik et al. (2013); van de Plassche (1982, 1995); van de Plassche et al. (2010); van Heteren et al. (2002); Vink et al. (2007); Vos (1992, 2013); Vos and Cohen (2014); Vos et al. (2010, 2011, 2015).

Figure 133: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: North Sea, location: Southern Bight. References: Jelgersma (1961); Kiden et al. (2002); Vink et al. (2007).

6.6.4 Skagerrak - Kattegat

Figure 134: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Asa. References: Mörner (1969); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 135: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Bohuslan. References: Persson (1973); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 136: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Goteborg. References: Mörner (1969); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 137: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Halmstad. References: Mörner (1969); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 138: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Kattegat. References: Bendixen et al. (2017); Bennike et al. (2000); Christiansen et al. (1993); Jensen et al. (2002); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 139: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Kieler Bucht. References: Bennike and Jensen (1998); Bennike et al. (2004); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 140: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Laesoe. References: Hansen (1977); Petersen and Rasmussen (1995); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 141: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Lillebaelt. References: Andersen (2013); Bennike and Jensen (2011); Krog (1979); Petersen and Rasmussen (1995); Rosentau et al. (2021); Skaarup and Grøn (2004); Tauber (1966).

Figure 142: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Samsø Belt. References: Fischer (2005); Hede et al. (2015); Jensen and Bennike (2009); Petersen (1993); Petersen and Rasmussen (1995); Rahbek and Rasmussen (1994); Rasmussen (1995); Rosentau et al. (2021); Sander et al. (2015).

Figure 143: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Storebaelt. References: Bennike et al. (2004); Christensen et al. (1997); Hede (2003); Krog (1979); Petersen (1978); Rosentau et al. (2021); Winn et al. (1986).

Figure 144: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Copenhagen. References: Bennike et al. (2012, 2017); Christensen (1982, 2014); Fischer (1993); Rasmussen (1992); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 145: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Treoa Moellebugt. References: Petersen and Rasmussen (1995); Rosentau et al. (2021).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 146: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Skagerrak - Kattegat, location: Vendsyssel Thy. References: Aaris-Sørensen and Petersen (1984); Christensen and Nielsen (2008); Knudsen (1978); Krog and Tauber (1974); Petersen (1991); Petersen and Rasmussen (1995); Richardt (1996); Rosentau et al. (2021).

6.6.5 South Baltic

Figure 147: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Achterwasser. References: Hoffmann et al. (2009); Lampe and Janke (2004); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 148: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Arkona Basin East. References: Bennike and Jensen (1998); Jensen et al. (1997); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 149: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Arkona Basin West. References: Bennike and Jensen (1998); Jensen et al. (1997); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 150: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Baltic South. References: Bennike and Lemke (2001); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 151: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Baltic Southwest. References: Bennike and Jensen (1998, 2013); Nielsen et al. (2004); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 152: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Blekinge. References: Berglund (1964, 1971); Hansson (2018); Hansson et al. (2019); Liljegren (1970); Nylander (1969); Rosentau et al. (2021); Yu et al. (2003, 2005, 2007).

Figure 153: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Curonian Spit. References: Rosentau et al. (2021); Sergeev et al. (2015).

Figure 154: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Fakse Bugt. References: Bennike and Jensen (1995, 1998); Jensen and Stecher (1992); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 155: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Havang. References: Berglund (1971); Hansson (2018); Hansson et al. (2018a,b); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 156: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Lithuania. References: Bitinas et al. (2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2017); Damušytė (2011); Gelumauskaitė (2009); Girininkas and Žulkus (2017); Rosentau et al. (2021); Trimonis et al. (2007); Žulkus and Girininkas (2012).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 157: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Lubeck. References: Bennike and Jensen (1998); Bennike and Lemke (2001); Harders et al. (2005); Heinrich et al. (2018); Jensen et al. (1997, 2002); Lampe et al. (2010); Rosentau et al. (2021); Winn et al. (1986).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 158: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Ostergotland. References: Persson (1979); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 159: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Rügen. References: Hoffmann et al. (2009); Lampe et al. (2010); Naumann and Lampe (2011); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 160: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Salt Meadows. References: Lampe and Janke (2004); Lampe et al. (2010); Naumann and Lampe (2011); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 161: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Sodermanland. References: Robertsson (1991); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 162: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: South Vistula. References: Miotk-Szpiganowicz (2016); Miotk-Szpiganowicz and Uścińowicz (2013); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 163: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Ustka. References: Miotk-Szpiganowicz et al. (2009); Rosentau et al. (2021).

Figure 164: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: Ventspils. References: Bērziņš et al. (2016); Murniece et al. (1999); Rosentau et al. (2021); Veinbergs (1996).

Figure 165: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South Baltic, location: West Gulf Of Gdansk. References: Rosentau et al. (2021); Uścińowicz et al. (2011, 2013).

6.7 Greenland

6.7.1 Northeast Greenland

Figure 166: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Cape Morris Jesup. References: Funder (1982); Funder et al. (2011); Ives et al. (1964); Möller et al. (2010).

Figure 167: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Danmarks Fjord. References: Bennike and Weidick (2001); Funder (1982); Funder et al. (2011); Hjort (1997); Håkansson (1982); Ives et al. (1964); Tauber (1960, 1961, 1964); Trautman (1963).

Figure 168: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Frederick E Hyde Fjord. References: Funder (1982); Landvik et al. (2001); Weidick (1972b, 1973, 1977).

Figure 169: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Germania Land. References: Landvik (1994).

Figure 170: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Hochstetter Forland. References: Björck et al. (1994b); Hjort (1979, 1981); Håkansson (1978, 1981); Weidick (1977).

Figure 171: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Hold With Hope. References: Hjort (1979); Hjort and Funder (1974); Håkansson (1975); Weidick (1976, 1977).

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 172: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Independence Fjord. References: Bennike (2002); Funder (1982); Funder and Abrahamsen (1988); Funder et al. (2011); Ives et al. (1964); Rubin and Alexander (1960); Tauber (1966); Weidick (1977).

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 173: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: JP Koch Fjord. References: Landvik et al. (2001).

Figure 174: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Jameson Land. References: Björck et al. (1994a); Funder (1971, 1972, 1973, 1978, 1990a); Funder and Hansen (1996); Hjort (1979); Ingólfsson et al. (1994); Weidick (1972b, 1973, 1974).

Figure 175: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Kap Clarence Wyckoff. References: Funder (1982); Funder and Abrahamsen (1988); Funder et al. (2011); Ives et al. (1964); Tauber (1964).

Figure 176: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Kempes Fjord. References: Hjort (1979); Hjort and Funder (1974); Håkansson (1973, 1974, 1976); Weidick (1977).

Figure 177: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Kong Oscars Fjord. References: Hjort (1979); Hjort and Funder (1974); Håkansson (1972, 1973, 1974, 1975, 1976); Lasca (1966); Trautman (1963); Washburn and Stuiver (1962).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 178: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Nansen land. References: Bennike and Kelly (1987); Kelly and Bennike (1985, 1992); Landvik et al. (2001); Weidick (1973).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 179: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Nioghalvfjærdsfjorden. References: Bennike and Weidick (2001).

Figure 180: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Prinsesse Ingeborg Halvøe. References: Bennike (1997); Funder (1982); Funder and Abrahamsen (1988); Funder et al. (2011); Hjort (1997); Håkansson (1987); Ives et al. (1964); Strunk et al. (2018); Tauber (1961).

Figure 181: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Renland. References: Funder (1971); Hjort and Funder (1974).

Figure 182: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Schuchert Dal. References: Funder (1972, 1978); Funder and Hansen (1996); Hall et al. (2008, 2010); Hjort (1979); Street (1977); Weidick (1972b).

Figure 183: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Traill Oe. References: Hjort (1973, 1979); Hjort and Funder (1974); Håkansson (1972, 1973, 1974).

Figure 184: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Young Sound. References: Bennike and Wagner (2012); Christiansen et al. (2002); Hjort (1979); Pedersen et al. (2011); Weidick (1977).

6.7.2 Northwest Greenland

Figure 185: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Bessel Fjord. References: Bennike (2002); Blake (1987); Glueder et al. (2022); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Weidick (1977).

Figure 186: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Cass Fjord. References: Bennike (2002); Blake (1987); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Weidick (1977).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 187: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Hall Land. References: Bennike and Kelly (1987); England (1985); Glueder et al. (2022); Kelly and Bennike (1985, 1992); McNeely and Brennan (2005); McNeely and McCuaig (1991); Rubin and Alexander (1960).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 188: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Inglefield Fjord. References: Blake et al. (1996); Fredskild (1985); Weidick (1976).

Figure 189: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Nordvestoe. References: Kelly et al. (1999).

Figure 190: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Thule. References: Funder (1990b); Kelly et al. (1999).

Figure 191: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Tuttulissuaq. References: Blake (1987); Fredskild (1985).

Figure 192: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Warming Land. References: Bennike and Kelly (1987); Kelly and Bennike (1985, 1992).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point ($\leq 10\text{m}$)
 - Index point ($> 10\text{m}$)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 193: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northwest Greenland, location: Wulff land. References: Bennike and Kelly (1987); Kelly and Bennike (1992).

6.7.3 Southeast Greenland

Figure 194: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southeast Greenland, location: Ammassalik. References: Long et al. (2008, 2011).

6.7.4 Southwest Greenland

Figure 195: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Akullit. References: Jungner (1979); Long and Roberts (2002); Long et al. (2011); Weidick (1972b, 1974, 1976).

Figure 196: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Alluttoq Island. References: Long et al. (2006, 1999, 2011).

Figure 197: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Eqalussuit Tasiat. References: Weidick (1972b, 1974).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Figure 198: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Ikertoq Fjord. References: Ten Brink (1975); Ten Brink and Weidick (1974); van Tatenhove et al. (1996); Weidick (1972b, 1973).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Figure 199: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Ilulissat. References: Long et al. (2006, 2011); Weidick (1972b, 1973).

Figure 200: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Itilleq. References: Long et al. (2009, 2011); Weidick (1972b).

Figure 201: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Kangerluk. References: Bennike (1995); Föged (1989); Long et al. (2011); Rasch (1997); Souza et al. (2021).

Figure 202: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Kangerlussuaq. References: Bierman et al. (2018); Storms et al. (2012); Ten Brink (1975); Ten Brink and Weidick (1974); van Tatenhove et al. (1996); Weidick (1972a,b, 1973).

Figure 203: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Kannala. References: Jungner (1979); Long and Roberts (2003); Long et al. (2003, 2011); Weidick (1974, 1976).

Figure 204: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Kapisillit. References: Fredskild (1973, 1983); Larsen et al. (2014); McGovern et al. (1996); Weidick (1968, 1972a, 1975, 1976); Weidick et al. (2012).

Figure 205: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Maniitsoq. References: Weidick (1973).

Figure 206: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Nanortalik. References: Bennike et al. (2002); Long et al. (2011); Sparrenbom et al. (2006b).

Figure 207: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Nuuk. References: Berglund (2003); Fredskild (1983); Hinnerson-Berglund (2004); Larsen et al. (2014, 2017); Weidick (1973, 1976).

Figure 208: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Paamiut. References: Woodroffe et al. (2014).

Figure 209: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Qaqortoq. References: Bennike et al. (2002); Bierman et al. (2018); Fredh (2008); Long et al. (2011); Randsalu (2008); Sparrenbom et al. (2006a); Weidick (1975).

Figure 210: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Qeqertarsuatsiaat. References: Larsen et al. (2014); Weidick (1975).

Figure 211: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Sisimiut. References: Bennike et al. (2011); Long et al. (2011); Weidick (1972b, 1973).

Figure 212: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Southwest Greenland, location: Tasiussarsuaq. References: Lasher et al. (2020).

6.8 North America Arctic

6.8.1 Hudson Bay

Figure 213: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Bay, location: Churchill. References: Anderson and Hodgetts (2007); Andrews and Falconer (1969); Blake (1982, 1988); Dyck and Fyles (1964); Hodgetts (2007); Kuhry (2008); Lowdon and Blake (1973); Lowdon et al. (1971); Meyer (1970); Morlan et al. (2000); Nash (1972); Simon et al. (2016); Vacchi et al. (2018); Wagner (1967).

Figure 214: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Bay, location: East James Bay. References: Beaulieu-Audy et al. (2009); Farrand (1962); Hardy (1976); Pendea et al. (2010); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 215: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Bay, location: Inukjuak. References: Andrews and Falconer (1969); Andrews and Short (1983); Buckley and Willis (1970); Harington (2003); Lauriol and Gray (1997); Lemieux et al. (2011); Lowdon and Blake (1968); Saint-Laurent and Filion (1992); Vacchi et al. (2018); Wagner (1967).

Figure 216: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Bay, location: Ivuujivik. References: Daigneault (2008); Harington (2003); Martindale et al. (2020); Matthews (1966, 1967); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Vacchi et al. (2018); Wagner (1967).

Figure 217: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Bay, location: Kivalliq. References: Aylsworth et al. (1981); Blake (1983, 1986, 1988); Dyck and Fyles (1962); Dyck et al. (1966); Lowdon and Blake (1970); Lowdon and Blake (1979); McNeely and Atkinson (1995); Morrison (1989); Ridler (1974); Rutherford et al. (1973, 1979); Simon et al. (2014, 2016); Vacchi et al. (2018); Walton et al. (1961).

Figure 218: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Bay, location: Umiujaq. References: Allard and Seguin (1985); Allard and Tremblay (1983a,b); Cayer (2003); Filion et al. (1991); Gajewski and Garralla (1992); Hillaire-Marcel (1976); Lajeunesse and Allard (2003); Lamarre et al. (2012); Lavoie et al. (2012); Lowdon and Blake (1980); Lowdon et al. (1967); McNeely (2006); Plumet (1974); Saulnier-Talbot and Pienitz (2001); Vacchi et al. (2018); Walcott and Craig (1975).

Figure 219: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Bay, location: West James Bay. References: Bunbury et al. (2012); Dyck et al. (1965); Dyke and Peltier (2000); Glaser et al. (2004); McAndrews et al. (1982); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Vacchi et al. (2018); Vogel and Waterbolk (1972); Webber et al. (1970).

6.8.2 Hudson Strait

Figure 220: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Strait, location: Kangiqsujuaq. References: Daigneault (2008); Dyke et al. (2003); Gray et al. (1993); Gray (2001); Lauriol and Gray (1987); McNeely (2002, 2005); McNeely and Atkinson (1995); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 221: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Strait, location: Southern Ungava Bay. References: Gray (2001); Pienitz et al. (1991); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 222: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Strait, location: Sugluk. References: Bartley and Matthews (1969); Daigneault (2008); Gray et al. (1993); Gray (2001); Gray and Lauriol (1985); Kasper and Allard (2001); Lauriol and Gray (1997); Lowdon and Blake (1968); Matthews (1966); McNeely and Brennan (2005); McNeely and McCuaig (1991); Ricard (1989); Simon et al. (2016); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 223: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Hudson Strait, location: Western Ungava Bay. References: Gray et al. (1980, 1993); Lauriol and Gray (1987); Lauriol et al. (1979); Løken (1978); Simon et al. (2016); Vacchi et al. (2018).

6.9 North America Atlantic

6.9.1 Eastern United States

Figure 224: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Eastern Shore. References: Engelhart and Horton (2012); Engelhart et al. (2009); Finkelstein and Ferland (1987); Newman and Rusnak (1965); van de Plassche (1990).

Figure 225: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Inner Chesapeake. References: Cinquemani et al. (1982); Colman et al. (2002); Engelhart and Horton (2012).

Figure 226: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Inner Delaware. References: Belknap (1975); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Kraft (1976); Leorri et al. (2006); Marx (1981); Nikitina et al. (2000); Ramsey and Baxter (1996); Rogers and Pizzuto (1994).

Figure 227: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Northern North Carolina. References: Emery et al. (1967); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Horton et al. (2009); Kemp (2009); Mallinson et al. (2005); Sears (1973); Stanton (2008).

Figure 228: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Northern South Carolina. References: Cinquemani et al. (1982); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Gayes et al. (1992).

Figure 229: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Outer Delaware. References: Belknap (1975); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Fletcher et al. (1993); Nikitina et al. (2000); Ramsey and Baxter (1996).

Figure 230: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Southern North Carolina. References: Cinquemani et al. (1982); Culver et al. (2007); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Field et al. (1979); Horton et al. (2009); Kemp (2009); Spaur and Snyder (1999).

Figure 231: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Southern South Carolina. References: Cinquemani et al. (1982); Engelhart and Horton (2012).

6.9.2 Labrador

Figure 232: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Labrador, location: Hamilton Inlet. References: Fitzhugh (1972, 1975); Lowdon and Blake (1975); Martindale et al. (2020); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 233: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Labrador, location: Lake Melville. References: Awadallah and Batterson (1990); Batterson (1996); Jordan (1975); King (1985); Liverman (1997); Lowdon and Blake (1975); Martindale et al. (2020); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 234: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Labrador, location: Nain. References: Clark and Fitzhugh (1990); Martindale et al. (2020); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 235: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Labrador, location: Torngat. References: Dyke et al. (2003); Evans and Rogerson (1988); Lowdon and Blake (1975); Martindale et al. (2020); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Savoie and Gangloff (1980); Vacchi et al. (2018).

6.9.3 Maritimes

Figure 236: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Anticosti Island. References: Dubois et al. (1988); Lavoie and Filion (2001); Painchaud et al. (1984); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 237: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Cape Breton. References: Blake and Lowdon (1976); Miller and Livingstone (1993); Shaw et al. (2009); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 238: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Chaleur Bay. References: McNeely and Brennan (2005); Rampton et al. (1984); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 239: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Cumberland. References: Dalrymple and Zaitlin (1994); Scott and Greenberg (1983); Shaw et al. (2010); Stea and Wightman (1987); Stuckenrath et al. (1966); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 240: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Forestville. References: Dietrich et al. (2017); Dionne (1996, 2001b); Dionne and Occhietti (1996); Dionne et al. (2004); Dubois et al. (1988); Martindale et al. (2020); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 241: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Halifax. References: Blake (1988); Edgecombe et al. (1999); Gehrels et al. (2004, 2005); Miller et al. (1982); Scott and Medioli (1982); Scott et al. (1995); Shaw et al. (1993); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 242: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Magdalen Islands. References: Barnett et al. (2017); Dredge et al. (1992); Rémillard et al. (2016, 2017); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 243: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Passamaquoddy Bay. References: Blake (1984); Gehrels et al. (2004); Martindale et al. (2020); McNeely (2005); Miller (1990); Nicks (1991); Rampton et al. (1984); Seaman (2004); Stea and Mott (1998); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 244: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Prince Edward Island. References: Kranck (1972); McCallum and Wittenberg (1965); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Ogden and Hart (1976); Scott et al. (1981, 1987); Stea and Mott (1989); Vacchi et al. (2018); Walton et al. (1961).

Figure 245: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Quebec City. References: Bhiry et al. (2000); Brodeur and Allard (1985); Dionne (1988, 1997, 1998); Filion (1987); Govare and Gangloff (1989); McNeely (2006); McNeely and Brennan (2005); Occhietti et al. (2001); Parent and Occhietti (1988); Samson et al. (1977); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 246: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Rimouski. References: Blake and Lowdon (1976); Dionne (1990, 1999, 2001a, 2005); Dionne and Coll (1995); Dyck and Fyles (1963); Harington (2003); Héту (1998); Héту and Bail (1996); Héту (1994); Locat (1977); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 247: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Sable Island. References: Amos and Miller (1990); Scott et al. (1984, 1989); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 248: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Maritimes, location: Shelburne. References: Blake (1983); Lowdon and Blake (1970); Scott and Greenberg (1983); Vacchi et al. (2018).

6.9.4 Newfoundland

Figure 249: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Newfoundland, location: Avalon Peninsula. References: Catto et al. (2000); Daly et al. (2007); MacPherson (1996); McNeely (2006); Shaw and Forbes (1995); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 250: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Newfoundland, location: Bay Of Islands. References: Brookes et al. (1985); Brookes and Stevens (1985); Daly et al. (2007); Grant (1994); McNeely and Brennan (2005); McNeely and McCuaig (1991); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 251: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Newfoundland, location: Great Northern Peninsula. References: Bell et al. (2005); Grant (1992, 1994); Martindale et al. (2020); McNeely and Jorgensen (1993); McNeely and McCuaig (1991); Nydal (1989); Tuck (1971); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 252: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Newfoundland, location: Notre Dame Bay. References: Blake (1983); Daly et al. (2007); Dyck and Fyles (1963); McNeely and Brennan (2005); McNeely and McCuaig (1991); Scott et al. (1991); Shaw and Edwardson (1994); Vacchi et al. (2018).

Figure 253: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Newfoundland, location: Port Aux Basques. References: Bell et al. (2003); Blake (1988); Brookes et al. (1985); Daly et al. (2007); Dyke et al. (2003); Forbes et al. (1993); Kemp et al. (2017); Lowdon and Blake (1980); Lowdon et al. (1971); McNeely (2002); McNeely and Atkinson (1995); McNeely and Brennan (2005); McNeely and Jorgensen (1992, 1993); McNeely and McCuaig (1991); Shaw and Forbes (1987, 1995); Shaw and Potter (2015); Vacchi et al. (2018).

6.9.5 Northeastern United States

Figure 254: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: Connecticut. References: Bloom (1963); Cinquemani et al. (1982); Donnelly et al. (2004); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Nydick et al. (1995); Redfield and Rubin (1962); van de Plassche (1991); van de Plassche et al. (1989, 1998, 2002).

Figure 255: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: Eastern Maine. References: Belknap et al. (1989); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Gehrels (1999); Gehrels and Belknap (1993); Gehrels et al. (1996).

Figure 256: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: Long Island. References: Bloom (1963); Cinquemani et al. (1982); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Field et al. (1979); Pardi and Newman (1980); Pardi et al. (1984); Redfield (1967); Redfield and Rubin (1962).

Figure 257: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: New Jersey. References: Cinquemani et al. (1982); Donnelly et al. (2001); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Field et al. (1979); Miller et al. (2009); Pardi et al. (1984); Psuty (1986); Stuiver and Daddario (1963).

Figure 258: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: New York. References: Engelhart and Horton (2012); Olson and Broecker (1961); Pardi et al. (1984); Slagle et al. (2006).

Figure 259: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: Northern Massachusetts. References: Donnelly (2006); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Kaye and Barghoorn (1964); Kirwan et al. (2011); Newman et al. (1980); Oldale et al. (1993); Redfield (1967); Redfield and Rubin (1962).

Figure 260: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: Southern Maine. References: Barnhardt et al. (1995); Belknap et al. (1989); Bloom (1963); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Gehrels et al. (1996, 2002); Kelley et al. (1992, 1995).

Figure 261: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeastern United States, location: Southern Massachusetts. References: Emery et al. (1967); Engelhart and Horton (2012); Field et al. (1979); Gutierrez et al. (2003); Oldale and O'Hara (1980); Redfield (1967); Redfield and Rubin (1962); Stuiver et al. (1963).

6.10 Pacific Islands

6.10.1 French Polynesia

Figure 262: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: French Polynesia, location: Mururoa. References: Camoin et al. (2001); Hibbert et al. (2016).

Figure 263: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: French Polynesia, location: Tahiti. References: Bard et al. (1996, 2010); Deschamps et al. (2012); Hibbert et al. (2016).

6.10.2 Melasia

Figure 264: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Melasia, location: Vanuatu. References: Cabioch et al. (2003); Cutler et al. (2004); Hibbert et al. (2016).

6.11 Proxy Based Sea Level

6.11.1 Red Sea

Figure 265: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Red Sea, location: Bab-el-Mandeb (Red Sea $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ Proxy). References: Grant et al. (2012, 2014).

6.12 South Asia

6.12.1 Bay of Bengal

Figure 266: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Bay of Bengal, location: Ganges Delta. References: Wiedicke et al. (1999).

6.13 Southeast Asia

6.13.1 Java Sea

Figure 267: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Java Sea, location: Belitung Island. References: Mann et al. (2019); Meltzner et al. (2017).

Figure 268: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Java Sea, location: Central Java. References: Azmy et al. (2010); Mann et al. (2019).

Figure 269: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Java Sea, location: South Sulawesi. References: de Klerk (1982); Mann et al. (2016, 2019); Tjia et al. (1972).

6.13.2 Papua New Guinea

Figure 270: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Papua New Guinea, location: Huon Peninsula. References: Chappell and Polach (1991); Cutler et al. (2003); Edwards et al. (1993); Hibbert et al. (2016); Mann et al. (2019).

6.13.3 South China Sea

Figure 271: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South China Sea, location: Xisha Islands. References: Yu et al. (2022).

6.13.4 Sundaland

Figure 272: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Ca Na. References: Mann et al. (2019); Statterger et al. (2013).

Figure 273: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Chao Phraya. References: Horton et al. (2005); Mann et al. (2019); Sinsakul (1992); Somboon (1988); Somboon and Thiramongkol (1992).

Figure 274: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: East Malay Peninsula. References: Mann et al. (2019); Parham et al. (2014); Tjia and Fujii (1992).

Figure 275: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Mekong Delta. References: Hanebuth et al. (2012); Mann et al. (2019); Statterger et al. (2013); Tamura et al. (2007, 2009).

Figure 276: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Phuket. References: Mann et al. (2019); Scheffers et al. (2012); Scoffin and Le Tissier (1998).

Figure 277: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Southeast Malay Peninsula. References: Hassan (2001); Horton et al. (2005); Mann et al. (2019); Tjia and Fujii (1992); Tjia et al. (1983).

Figure 278: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Strait Of Malacca. References: Bird et al. (2007, 2010); Geyh et al. (1979); Hassan (2001); Hesp et al. (1998); Horton et al. (2005); Mann et al. (2019); Tjia and Fujii (1992).

Figure 279: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Sunda Shelf. References: Hanebuth et al. (2000, 2003, 2009).

Figure 280: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Thale Noi. References: Horton et al. (2005); Mann et al. (2019).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 281: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Vietnam Shelf. References: Hanebuth et al. (2000).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point (≤10m)
- Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 282: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: West Malay Peninsula. References: Mann et al. (2019); Tjia and Fujii (1992); Tjia et al. (1972).

7 MIS 3 and 4 – Sea level Indicators and Proxies

MIS 3 is an interstadial period that stretches between about 55 and 27 kyr before present. MIS 4 is a glacial period when the ice sheets significantly expanded in North America and Europe, between about 70 and 55 kyr. There are few sea level proxies from this time interval for three main reasons. First, such deposits are hard to date, because the material is near or beyond the limits of radiocarbon dating. Second, the geological evidence in many areas was eroded by the subsequent rise in sea level during the MIS 1 and 2 deglaciation. As a result, many of the proxies are only preserved in places where there is a substantial tectonic uplift rate. Third, relative sea level during MIS 3 and 4 likely never exceeded -30 m, so the deposits are likely below the depth limit of most coring survey methods.

7.1 Antarctica

7.1.1 East Antarctica

Figure 283: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Langhovde. References: Igarashi et al. (1995a,b); Ishiwa et al. (2021); Maemoku et al. (1997); Miura et al. (1998).

Figure 284: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Larsemann Hills. References: Hodgson et al. (2009); Ishiwa et al. (2021).

Figure 285: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Ongul Islands. References: Hirakawa and Sawagaki (1998); Igarashi et al. (1995a,b); Ishiwa et al. (2021); Miura et al. (1998).

Figure 286: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: East Antarctica, location: Rauer Group. References: Berg et al. (2010a, 2016); Ishiwa et al. (2021).

7.2 Australia

7.2.1 Northern Australia

Figure 287: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Bonaparte Gulf. References: Ishiwa et al. (2019); Yokoyama et al. (2000).

Figure 288: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Bonaparte Gulf (Ishiwa *et al.* 2019 interpretation). References: Ishiwa et al. (2019); Yokoyama et al. (2000).

Figure 289: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northern Australia, location: Bonaparte Gulf (Yokoyama *et al.* 2000 interpretation). References: Yokoyama *et al.* (2000).

7.2.2 Queensland

Figure 290: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Cairns. References: Larcombe *et al.* (1995); Lewis *et al.* (2013); Yokoyama *et al.* (2018).

Figure 291: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Hydrographers Passage. References: Yokoyama et al. (2018).

Figure 292: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Queensland, location: Townsville. References: Larcombe et al. (1995); Lewis et al. (2013); Ohlenbusch (1991).

7.3 Caribbean

7.3.1 Lesser Antilles

Figure 293: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Lesser Antilles, location: Barbados. References: Abdul et al. (2016); Fairbanks (1988); Peltier and Fairbanks (2006).

7.4 East Asia

7.4.1 Ryukyu Islands

Figure 294: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Ryukyu Islands, location: Kikaijima (1.9 mm/yr uplift rate). References: Konishi et al. (1974); Omura (1988); Omura and Konishi (1970); Omura et al. (1985, 2000); Sasaki et al. (2004).

Figure 295: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Ryukyu Islands, location: Kikaijima (2.1 mm/yr uplift rate). References: Konishi et al. (1974); Omura (1988); Omura and Konishi (1970); Omura et al. (1985, 2000); Sasaki et al. (2004).

7.4.2 Sea of Japan - East Sea

Figure 296: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sea of Japan - East Sea, location: Tsushima-Korea Strait. References: Park et al. (2000).

7.4.3 Yellow Sea

Figure 297: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Yellow Sea, location: South Bohai Sea. References: Liu et al. (2009); Pico et al. (2016).

Figure 298: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Yellow Sea, location: Yellow Sea. References: Liu et al. (2010); Pico et al. (2016); Wang et al. (2014).

7.5 Greenland

7.5.1 Northeast Greenland

Figure 299: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Cape Morris Jesup. References: Funder et al. (2011).

Figure 300: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Kap Clarence Wyckoff. References: Funder et al. (2011).

Sea level proxy type

- ▲ Marine Limiting
- ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
- Index point ($\leq 10\text{m}$)
- Index point ($> 10\text{m}$)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 301: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Northeast Greenland, location: Nansen land. References: Landvik et al. (2001).

7.6 North America Atlantic

7.6.1 Eastern United States

Figure 302: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Eastern Shore. References: Engelhart and Horton (2012); Mixon et al. (1982); Parham et al. (2013); Scott (2006).

Figure 303: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Northern North Carolina. References: Culver et al. (2011); Mallinson et al. (2008); Parham et al. (2013); Pico et al. (2017); Scott (2006).

Figure 304: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Eastern United States, location: Southern North Carolina. References: Best (2010); Moore (2009); Parham et al. (2013); Pico et al. (2017).

7.7 Pacific Islands

7.7.1 French Polynesia

Figure 305: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: French Polynesia, location: Mururoa. References: Camoin et al. (2001); Hibbert et al. (2016).

Figure 306: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: French Polynesia, location: Tahiti. References: Hibbert et al. (2016); Thomas et al. (2009).

7.7.2 Melansia

Figure 307: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Melansia, location: Vanuatu. References: Cabioch and Ayliffe (2001).

7.8 Proxy Based Sea Level

7.8.1 Java Sea

Figure 308: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Java Sea, location: Karimata Strait (Sulu Sea $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ Proxy). References: Weiss et al. (2022).

7.8.2 Red Sea

Figure 309: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Red Sea, location: Bab-el-Mandeb (Red Sea $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ Proxy). References: Grant et al. (2012, 2014).

7.9 South Asia

7.9.1 Bay of Bengal

Figure 310: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Bay of Bengal, location: Ganges Delta. References: Wiedicke et al. (1999).

7.10 Southeast Asia

7.10.1 Papua New Guinea

Figure 311: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Papua New Guinea, location: Huon Peninsula. References: Chappell *et al.* (1996); Cutler *et al.* (2003); Hibbert *et al.* (2016); Yokoyama *et al.* (2001).

Figure 312: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Papua New Guinea, location: Huon Peninsula (Interpretation by de Gelder *et al.*). References: Chappell (2002); Chappell *et al.* (1996); de Gelder *et al.* (2022).

7.10.2 South China Sea

Figure 313: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: South China Sea, location: Xisha Islands. References: Yu et al. (2022).

7.10.3 Sundaland

Figure 314: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Berhala Strait. References: Geyh et al. (1979); Mann et al. (2019).

Figure 315: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Chao Phraya. References: Mann et al. (2019); Tanabe et al. (2003).

Figure 316: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Mekong Delta. References: Mann et al. (2019); Ta et al. (2002).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 317: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Strait Of Malacca. References: Geyh et al. (1979); Mann et al. (2019).

Sea level proxy type
 ▲ Marine Limiting ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 ■ Index point (≤10m) ■ Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 318: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Sunda Shelf. References: Hanebuth et al. (2003); Steinke et al. (2003).

- Sea level proxy type**
- ▲ Marine Limiting
 - ▼ Terrestrial Limiting
 - Index point (≤10m)
 - Index point (>10m)

Reference ice model: PM_1_A_h Reference Earth Model: ehgr

Figure 319: Paleo-sea level and comparison of six models for subregion: Sundaland, location: Vietnam Shelf. References: Schimanski and Statteger (2005).

Bibliography

- Aaris-Sørensen, K. and Petersen, K. S.: A Late Weichselian find of polar bear (*Ursus maritimus* Phipps) from Denmark and reflections on the paleoenvironment, *Boreas*, 13, 29–33, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1984.tb00056.x>, 1984.
- Abdul, N. A., Mortlock, R. A., Wright, J. D., and Fairbanks, R. G.: Younger Dryas sea level and meltwater pulse 1B recorded in Barbados reef crest coral *Acropora palmata*, *Paleoceanography*, 31, 330–344, <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015PA002847>, 2016.
- Alhonen, P.: Gallträsket: The geological development and palaeolimnology of a small polluted lake in southern Finland, *Commentationes biologicae*, 57, 5–24, 1972.
- Alhonen, P., Eronen, M., Núñez, M., Salomaa, R., and Uusinoka, R.: A contribution to Holocene shore displacement and environmental development in Vantaa, South Finland: the stratigraphy of Lake Lammaslampi, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Finland*, 50, 69–79, <https://doi.org/10.17741/bgsf/50.1-2.007>, 1978.
- Allard, M. and Seguin, M.: Deglaciation of Part of the Coastal Zone of Hudson Bay (Québec): Rivières Nastapoca, Sheldrake and à l'Eau Claire Basins, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 39, 13–24, <https://doi.org/10.7202/032581ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): La déglaciation d' une partie du versant hudsonien québécois : bassins des rivières Nastapoca, Sheldrake et à l' Eau Claire, 1985.
- Allard, M. and Tremblay, G.: Coastal dynamics of the Manitounuk Islands during the Holocene, in: Coastal and inland periglacial processes, Canadian Arctic, edited by Hagedorn, H., vol. 47 of *Zeitschrift für Geomorphologie. Supplementband*, pp. 61–95, Schweizerbart, title translated with DeepL, Language: French, Title (in original language): La dynamique littorale des îles Manitounuk durant l'Holocène, 1983a.
- Allard, M. and Tremblay, G.: Periglacial coastal erosion processes in the Port-de-la-Baleine and Manitounuk Islands area on the east coast of the Hudson Sea, Canada, in: Coastal and inland periglacial processes, Canadian Arctic, edited by Hagedorn, H., vol. 47 of *Zeitschrift für Geomorphologie. Supplementband*, pp. 27–60, Schweizerbart, title translated with DeepL, Language: French, Title (in original language): Les processus d'érosion littorale périglaciaire de la région de Port-de-la-Baleine et des îles Manitounuk sur la côte est de la mer d'Hudson, Canada, 1983b.
- Amos, C. L. and Miller, A. A.: The Quaternary stratigraphy of southwest Sable Island Bank, eastern Canada, *Geological Society of America Bulletin*, 102, 915–934, [https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606\(1990\)102<0915:TQSOSS>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606(1990)102<0915:TQSOSS>2.3.CO;2), 1990.
- Andersen, S.: Tybrind Vig: submerged mesolithic settlements in Denmark, no. 77 in Jutland Archaeological Society Publications, Jutland Archaeological Society/Moesgård Museum, Højbjerg, 2013.
- Anderson, J. M. and Hodgetts, L. M.: Pre-Dorset technological organization and land use in southwestern Hudson Bay, *Canadian Journal of Archaeology/Journal Canadien d'Archéologie*, 31, 224–249, URL <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41103301>, 2007.
- Andreev, A., Tarasov, P., Schwamborn, G., Ilyashuk, B., Ilyashuk, E., Bobrov, A., Klimanov, V., Rachold, V., and Hubberten, H.-W.: Holocene paleoenvironmental records from Nikolay Lake, Lena River Delta, Arctic Russia, *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 209, 197–217, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2004.02.010>, 2004.

- Andrews, J. T. and Falconer, G.: Late glacial and post-glacial history and emergence of the Ottawa Islands, Hudson Bay, Northwest Territories: Evidence on the deglaciation of Hudson Bay, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 6, 1263–1276, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e69-126>, 1969.
- Andrews, J. T. and Short, S. K.: Radiocarbon Date List V: Baffin Island N.W.T., Canada, and Radiocarbon Date List II: Labrador and Northern Quebec, Canada, Occasional Paper 40, Institute of Arctic and Alpine Research, University of Colorado, Boulder, Colorado, USA, URL <https://www.colorado.edu/instaar/research/publications/instaar-occasional-papers>, 1983.
- Anisimov, M. A., Ivanova, V. V., Pushina, Z. V., and Pitul'ko, V. V.: Lagoon Sediments of Jokhov Island: Age, Conditions of Formation and Meanings for Paleogeographical Reconstructions of the Region of Novosibirsk Islands, *Proceedings of the Russian Academy of Sciences (Geography Series)*, 5, 107–119, URL <http://www.evgenyusev.narod.ru/romox/anisimov-2009.html>, (in Russian), Language: Russian with English abstract, Authors (in original language): Анисимов, М. А., Иванова, В. В., Пушина, З. В., and Питулько, В. В., Title (in original language): Лагунные отложения острова Жохова: возраст, условия формирования и значение для палеогеографических реконструкций региона Новосибирских островов, *Journal/book* (in original language): Известия РАН. Серия географическая, 2009a.
- Anisimov, M. A., Pavlova, E. Y., and Pitulko, V. V.: Holocene of the New Siberian Islands. Fundamental problems of the Quaternary: results of investigations and future perspectives, in: *Proceedings of the VI All-Russian Quaternary Workshop*, pp. 38–40, Novosibirsk, Russia, URL <http://www.evgenyusev.narod.ru/xlii/anisimov-2009.html>, (In Russian), Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Анисимов, М. А., Павлова, Е. Ю., and Питулько, В. В., Title (in original language): Голоцен Новосибирских островов. Фундаментальные проблемы квартера: итоги изучения и основные направления дальнейших исследований., *Journal/book* (in original language): Материалы VI Всероссийского совещания по изучению четвертичного периода. Новосибирск, 2009b.
- Arslanov, X. A., Koshechkin, B. I., and Chernov, B. S.: (Absolute chronology of sediments of late- and postglacial marine basins, Kola Peninsula), in: *Bulletin of the Leningrad University*, vol. 12, pp. 132–138, Leningrad University, URL <http://www.evgenyusev.narod.ru/kola/arslanov-1974.html>, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Арсланов, Х.А., Кошечкин, Б.И., and Чернов, Б.С., Title (in original language): Абсолютная хронология осадков позднего и послеледниковых морских бассейнов на Кольском п-ове, *Journal/book* (in original language): Вестник Ленинградского ун-та, 1974.
- Astakhov, V. I. and Nazarov, D. V.: The stratigraphy of the upper Neopleistocene of western Siberia and its geochronometric justification, *Regional'naja geologija i metallogenija*, 43, 36–47, URL <http://www.evgenyusev.narod.ru/astahov/astahov-2010.html>, (in Russian), Language: Russian with English abstract, Authors (in original language): Астахов, В. И. and Назаров, Д. В., Title (in original language): Стратиграфия верхнего неоплейстоцена севера Западной Сибири и ее геохронометрическое обоснование, *Journal/book* (in original language): Региональная геология и металлогения, 2010.
- Astakhov, V. I., Mangerud, J., and Svendsen, J. I.: Transural Upper Pleistocene correlation of the North, *Regional Geology and Metallogeny*, 30-31, 190–206, URL <http://www.evgenyusev.narod.ru/astahov/astahov2007.html>, title translated with DeepL, Language: Russian with English abstract, Authors (in original language): Астахов, В. И., Мангеруд, Я., and Свенсен, Й.И., Title (in original language): Трансуральская корреляция верхнего плейстоцена Севера, *Journal/book* (in original language): Региональная геология и металлогения, 2007.

- Awadallah, S. A. and Batterson, M. J.: Comment on “Late Deglaciation of the Central Labrador Coast and Its Implications for the Age of Glacial Lakes Naskaupi and McLean and for Prehistory,” by PU Clark and WW Fitzhugh, *Quaternary Research*, 34, 372–373, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894\(90\)90048-P](https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894(90)90048-P), 1990.
- Aylsworth, J. M., Boydell, A. N., Cunningham, C. M., and Shilts, W. W.: Surficial Geology, Macquoid Lake, District of Keewatin, Preliminary Map 11-1980, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/109694>, scale 1:125 000, 1981.
- Azmy, K., Edinger, E., Lundberg, J., and Diegor, W.: Sea level and paleotemperature records from a mid-Holocene reef on the North coast of Java, Indonesia, *International Journal of Earth Sciences*, 99, 231–244, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00531-008-0383-3>, 2010.
- Baker, R., Haworth, R., and Flood, P.: Warmer or cooler late Holocene marine palaeoenvironments?: interpreting southeast Australian and Brazilian sea-level changes using fixed biological indicators and their $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ composition, *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 168, 249–272, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-0182\(01\)00202-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-0182(01)00202-4), 2001a.
- Baker, R. G. V. and Haworth, R.: Smooth or oscillating late Holocene sea-level curve? Evidence from the palaeo-zoology of fixed biological indicators in east Australia and beyond, *Marine Geology*, 163, 367–386, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227\(99\)00118-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227(99)00118-8), 2000.
- Baker, R. G. V. and Haworth, R. J.: Further evidence from relic shellcrust sequences for a late Holocene higher sea level for eastern Australia, *Marine Geology*, 141, 1–9, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227\(97\)00068-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227(97)00068-6), 1997.
- Baker, R. G. V., Haworth, R. J., and Flood, P. G.: Inter-tidal fixed indicators of former Holocene sea levels in Australia: a summary of sites and a review of methods and models, *Quaternary International*, 83–85, 257–273, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1040-6182\(01\)00044-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1040-6182(01)00044-1), *australian Quaternary Studies: A Tribute to Jim Bowler*, 2001b.
- Baker, R. G. V., Haworth, R. J., and Flood, P. G.: An oscillating Holocene sea-level? Revisiting Rottneest Island, Western Australia, and the Fairbridge Eustatic Hypothesis, *Journal of Coastal Research*, pp. 3–14, URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25736969>, 2005.
- Bantelmann, A.: The Imperial Period marsh settlement of Ostermoor near Brunsbüttelkoog, *Offa*, 16, 53–79, Language: German, Title (in original language): Die kaiserzeitliche Marschensiedlung Ostermoor bei Brunsbüttelkoog, 1960.
- Bantelmann, A.: Landscape development on the west coast of Schleswig-Holstein, illustrated by the example of North Friesland. A functional chronicle through five millennia, *Die Küste*, 14, 5–99, URL <https://izw.baw.de/publikationen/die-kueste/0/k014202.pdf>, title translated using DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Die Landschaftsentwicklung an der schleswig-holsteinischen Westküste, dargestellt am Beispiel Nordfriesland. Eine Funktionschronik durch fünf Jahrtausende, 1966.
- Bantelmann, A.: The Early Historic Marsh Settlement at Elisenhof in Eiderstedt. Landscape history and building findings, *Studien zur Küstenarchäologie Schleswig-Holsteins. Series A*, 1, 190, title translated by DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Die frühgeschichtliche Marschensiedlung beim Elisenhof in Eiderstedt. Landschaftsgeschichte und Baubefunde, 1975.
- Bantelmann, A., Hoffmann, D., and Menke, B.: Changes in the course of the coast: Schleswig-Holstein, in: *Archäologische und naturwissenschaftliche Untersuchungen an ländlichen und frühstädtischen Siedlungen im deutschen Küstengebiet vom 5. Jahrhundert v. Chr. bis zum 11. Jahrhundert n. Chr.*

- Handelsplätze des frühen und hohen Mittelalters, edited by Kossack, G., Behre, K.-E., and Schmid, P., vol. 1, pp. 54–68, Acta Humaniora, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Veränderungen des Küstenverlaufs: Schleswig-Holstein, 1984.
- Baranskaya, A. and Romanenko, F.: Differential vertical crustal movements and block tectonics of the coasts of Kandalaksha Gulf, White Sea, in: (Proceedings of the IV International Scientific and Practical Conference of Young Scientists and Specialists in Memory of Academician A.P. Karpinsky), pp. 3–6, VSEGEI. - VSEGEI St. Petersburg, St. Petersburg, Russia, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Баранская, А. В. and Романенко, Ф. А., Title (in original language): Дифференцированные вертикальные движения и блоковая тектоника побережий Кандалакшского залива Белого моря, Journal/book (in original language): Материалы IV Международной научно-практической конференции молодых ученых и специалистов памяти академика А.П. Карпинского, 2015.
- Baranskaya, A. V.: The Role of the Latest Tectonic Movements in the Formation of the Relief of the Coasts of the Russian Arctic, Ph.D. thesis, Saint Petersburg State University, Saint-Petersburg, Russia, summary of the Thesis for a Degree of Doctor of Philosophy (Geographical Science), Speciality 25.00.25 - Geomorphology and Evolutional Geography, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): В., Баранская А., Title (in original language): Роль новейших вертикальных тектонических движений в формировании рельефа побережий Российской Арктики, 2015.
- Baranskaya, A. V., Khan, N. S., Romanenko, F. A., Roy, K., Peltier, W. R., and Horton, B. P.: A postglacial relative sea-level database for the Russian Arctic coast, Quaternary Science Reviews, 199, 188–205, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2018.07.033>, 2018a.
- Baranskaya, A. V., Romanenko, F. A., Arslanov, H. A., Petrov, A. Y., Maksimov, F. E., Tikhonov, A. N., and Demidov, N. E.: Upper Quaternary sediments of Gydan Peninsula and Arctic islands: evidence of relative Kara Sea level changes since 50 ka, Vestnik Moskovskogo universiteta. Seriya 5, Geografiya, 6, 56–71, URL <https://vestnik5.geogr.msu.ru/jour/article/view/482>, Language: Russian with English abstract, Authors (in original language): Баранская, А. В., Романенко, Ф. А., Арсланов, Х. А., Петров, А. Ю., Максимов, Ф. Е., Пушина, З. В., Тихонов, А. Н., and Демидов, Н. Э., Title (in original language): ВЕРХНЕЧЕТВЕРТИЧНЫЕ ОТЛОЖЕНИЯ ГЫДАНА И АРКТИЧЕСКИХ ОСТРОВОВ: РЕКОНСТРУКЦИЯ ОТНОСИТЕЛЬНОГО УРОВНЯ КАРСКОГО МОРЯ ЗА ПОСЛЕДНИЕ 50 ТЫСЯЧ ЛЕТ, Journal/book (in original language): Вестник Московского университета. Серия 5. География, 2018b.
- Barckhausen, J.: Origin and development of the island of Langeoog – Examples of Quaternary geology and palaeogeography of an East Frisian coastal section, in: Oldenburger Jahrbuch, vol. 68, pp. 239–281, Oldenburger Landesverein für Geschichte, Natur- und Heimatkunde Oldenburg, URL <https://digital.lb-oldenburg.de/ihd/periodical/titleinfo/161602>, Language: German, Title (in original language): Entstehung und Entwicklung der Insel Langeoog – Beispiele zur Quartärgeologie und Paläogeographie eines ostfriesischen Küstenabschnittes, 1969.
- Barckhausen, J.: Explanatory notes on sheet no. 2609 Emden, Geologische karte von niedersachsen 1:25 000, Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Bodenforschung, Hannover, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Erläuterungen zu Blatt Nr. 2609 Emden, 1984.
- Bard, E., Hamelin, B., Arnold, M., Montaggioni, L., Cabioch, G., Faure, G., and Rougerie, F.: Deglacial sea-level record from Tahiti corals and the timing of global meltwater discharge, Nature, 382, 241–244, <https://doi.org/10.1038/382241a0>, 1996.

- Bard, E., Hamelin, B., and Delanghe-Sabatier, D.: Deglacial Meltwater Pulse 1B and Younger Dryas Sea Levels Revisited with Boreholes at Tahiti, *Science*, 327, 1235–1237, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1180557>, 2010.
- Barnett, R. L., Bernatchez, P., Garneau, M., and Juneau, M.-N.: Reconstructing late Holocene relative sea-level changes at the Magdalen Islands (Gulf of St. Lawrence, Canada) using multi-proxy analyses, *Journal of Quaternary Science*, 32, 380–395, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.2931>, 2017.
- Barnhardt, W. A., Roland Gehrels, W., and Kelley, J. T.: Late Quaternary relative sea-level change in the western Gulf of Maine: Evidence for a migrating glacial forebulge, *Geology*, 23, 317–320, [https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613\(1995\)023<0317:LQRSLS>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613(1995)023<0317:LQRSLS>2.3.CO;2), 1995.
- Baroni, C. and Hall, B. L.: A new Holocene relative sea-level curve for Terra Nova Bay, Victoria Land, Antarctica, *Journal of Quaternary Science*, 19, 377–396, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.825>, 2004.
- Barsch, D. and Mäusbacher, R.: Contributions to the glaciation history and relief development of the South Shetland Islands, *Zeitschrift für Geomorphologie, Supplementbände*, 61, 25–37, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Beiträge zur Vergletscherungsgeschichte und zur Reliefentwicklung der Südshetland Inseln, 1986.
- Bartley, D. D. and Matthews, B.: A palaeobotanical investigation of postglacial deposits in the Sugluk area of northern Ungava (Quebec, Canada), *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology*, 9, 45–61, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0034-6667\(69\)90012-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0034-6667(69)90012-8), 1969.
- Batterson, M.: Quaternary geology of parts of the central and southern Hopedale Block, Labrador, Current Research Report 96-1, Newfoundland Department of Mines and Energy, Geological Survey, URL <https://www.gov.nl.ca/iet/mines/geoscience/reports-maps/currentresearch/current-research-1996/>, 1996.
- Bauch, H. A., Kassens, H., Erlenkeuser, H., Grootes, P. M., and Thiede, J.: Depositional environment of the Laptev Sea (Arctic Siberia) during the Holocene, *Boreas*, 28, 194–204, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1999.tb00214.x>, 1999.
- Beaman, R., Larcombe, P., and Carter, R. M.: New evidence for the Holocene sea-level high from the inner shelf, central Great Barrier Reef, Australia, *Journal of Sedimentary Research*, 64, 881–885, <https://doi.org/10.1306/D4267EF1-2B26-11D7-8648000102C1865D>, 1994.
- Beaulieu-Audy, V., Garneau, M., Richard, P. J. H., and Asnong, H.: Holocene palaeoecological reconstruction of three boreal peatlands in the La Grande Rivière region, Québec, Canada, *The Holocene*, 19, 459–476, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683608101395>, 2009.
- Behre, K.-E and, B. J., Brandt, K., and Streif, H.: East Frisia/Germany, in: Excursion Guide INQUA Holocene Commission and Subcommission Shorelines of NW Europe, 1975.
- Behre, K.-E and, D. J. and Irion, G.: A dated sediment core from the Holocene of the southern North Sea, *Probleme der Küstenforschung im südlichen Nordseegebiet*, 15, 135–148, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Ein datierter Sedimentkern aus dem Holozän der südlichen Nordsee, 1984.
- Behre, K.-E.: The history of the development of natural vegetation in the Lower Ems area and its dependence on sea-level movements, *Probleme der Küstenforschung im südlichen Nordseegebiet*, 9, 13–48, title translated by DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Die Entwicklungsgeschichte der natürlichen Vegetation im Gebiet der unteren Ems und ihre Abhängigkeit von den Bewegungen des Meeresspiegels, 1970.

- Behre, K.-E.: A new sea level curve for the southern North Sea: transgressions and regressions over the last 10,000 years, *Probleme der Küstenforschung im südlichen Nordseegebiet*, 28, 2–63, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Eine neue Meeresspiegelkurve für die südliche Nordsee: Transgressionen und Regressionen in den letzten 10.000 Jahren, 2003.
- Behre, K.-E.: A new Holocene sea-level curve for the southern North Sea, *Boreas*, 36, 82–102, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2007.tb01183.x>, 2007.
- Behre, K.-E. and Kučan, D.: Neue Untersuchungen am Außendeichsmoor bei Sehestedt am Jadebusen, *Probleme der Küstenforschung im südlichen Nordseegebiet*, 26, 35–64, Language: German with English abstract, Title (in original language): Neue Untersuchungen am Außendeichsmoor bei Sehestedt am Jadebusen, 1999.
- Behre, K.-E. and Menke, B.: Pollen analysis of a drill core from the southern Dogger Bank, *Beiträge zur Meereskunde*, 24/25, 122–129, URL https://www.io-warnemuende.de/tl_files/forschung/beitraege-zur-meereskunde/1969_24-25_Beitraege_zur_Meereskunde.pdf, title translated by DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Pollenanalytische Untersuchungen an einem Bohrkern der südlichen Doggerbank, 1969.
- Behre, K.-E., Menke, B., and Streif, H.: The Quaternary geological development of the German part of the North Sea, in: *The Quarternary History of the North Sea*, edited by Oele, R., Schüttenheim, R. T. E., and Wiggers, A. J., vol. 2, pp. 85–113, Uppsala University, Uppsala, 1979.
- Belknap, D. F.: Dating of late Pleistocene and Holocene relative sea levels in coastal Delaware, Ph.D. thesis, University of Delaware, Newark, Delaware, United States, 1975.
- Belknap, D. F., Shipp, R. C., Stuckenrath, R., Kelley, J. T., and Borns Jr, H. W.: Holocene sea-level change in coastal Maine, in: *Neotectonics of Maine: studies in seismicity, crustal warping, and sea level change*, edited by Anderson, W. A. and Borns Jr, H. W., 40, pp. 85–105, Maine Geological Survey, URL https://digitalmaine.com/mgs_publications/187/, 1989.
- Bell, T., Batterson, M. J., Liverman, D. G. E., and Shaw, J.: A new late-glacial sea-level record for St. George's Bay, Newfoundland, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 40, 1053–1070, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e03-024>, Language: English with French abstract, 2003.
- Bell, T., Daly, J., Batterson, M., Liverman, D., Shaw, J., and Smith, I.: Late Quaternary relative sea-level change on the west coast of Newfoundland, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 59, 129–140, <https://doi.org/10.7202/014751ar>, Language: English with French abstract, 2005.
- Belova, N. G.: Massive ice beds of the southwestern Kara Sea coast, Summary of thesis for the degree of phd in geography, specialty 25.00.31 - glaciology and cryology of the earth, Moscow, Moscow, Russia, URL <https://istina.msu.ru/dissertations/819579/>, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Белова, Наталия Геннадиевна, Title (in original language): Пластовые льды юго-западного побережья Карского моря, 2012.
- Belperio, A. P.: An inner shelf sedimentation model for the Townsville region, Great Barrier Reef province, Ph.D. thesis, James Cook University of North Queensland, 1978.
- Belperio, A. P.: Negative evidence for a mid-Holocene high sea level along the coastal plain of the Great Barrier Reef Province, *Marine Geology*, 32, M1–M9, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(79\)90140-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(79)90140-3), 1979.
- Belperio, A. P.: Land subsidence and sea level rise in the Port Adelaide estuary: Implications for monitoring the greenhouse effect, *Australian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 40, 359–368, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08120099308728087>, 1993.

- Belperio, A. P., Hails, J. R., and Gostin, V. A.: A review of Holocene sea levels in South Australia, in: Australian Sea Levels in the Last 15,000 Years: A Review, edited by Hopley, D., vol. 3 of *Department of Geography Monograph Series, Occasional Paper*, pp. 37–47, James Cook University of North Queensland, Townsville, Queensland, Australia, 1983.
- Belperio, A. P., Smith, B. W., Polach, H. A., Nittrouer, C. A., DeMaster, D. J., Prescott, J. R., Hails, J. R., and Gostin, V. A.: Chronological studies of the Quaternary marine sediments of northern Spencer Gulf, South Australia, *Marine Geology*, 61, 265–296, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(84\)90171-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(84)90171-3), the Spencer Gulf Region, 1984.
- Belperio, A. P., Harvey, N., and Bourman, R. P.: Spatial and temporal variability in the Holocene sea-level record of the South Australian coastline, *Sedimentary Geology*, 150, 153–169, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0037-0738\(01\)00273-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0037-0738(01)00273-1), coastal Environment Change During Sea-Level Highstands, 2002.
- Bendixen, C., Jensen, J. B., Boldreel, L. O., Clausen, O. R., Bennike, O., Seidenkrantz, M.-S., Nyberg, J., and Hübscher, C.: The Holocene Great Belt connection to the southern Kattegat, Scandinavia: Ancylus Lake drainage and Early Littorina Sea transgression, *Boreas*, 46, 53–68, <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12154>, 2017.
- Bennema, J.: Holocene movements of land and sea-level in the coastal area of the Netherlands, *Geologie en Mijnbouw*, 16, 254–264, URL <https://www.kngmg.nl/geologie-en-mijnbouw-portal-pre-1961/>, 1954.
- Bennike, O.: Palaeoecology of two lake basins from Disko, West Greenland, *Journal of Quaternary Science*, 10, 149–155, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.3390100205>, 1995.
- Bennike, O.: Quaternary vertebrates from Greenland: A review, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 16, 899–909, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(97\)00002-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(97)00002-4), 1997.
- Bennike, O.: Late Quaternary history of Washington Land, North Greenland, *Boreas*, 31, 260–272, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2002.tb01072.x>, 2002.
- Bennike, O. and Jensen, J. B.: Near-shore Baltic Ice Lake deposits in Fakse Bugt, southeast Denmark, *Boreas*, 24, 185–195, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1995.tb00772.x>, 1995.
- Bennike, O. and Jensen, J. B.: Late-and postglacial shore level changes in the southwestern Baltic Sea, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark*, 45, 27–38, <https://doi.org/10.37570/bgsd-1998-45-04>, 1998.
- Bennike, O. and Jensen, J. B.: Postglacial, relative shore-level changes in Lillebælt, Denmark, *Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland Bulletin*, 23, 37–40, <https://doi.org/10.34194/geusb.v23.4834>, 2011.
- Bennike, O. and Jensen, J. B.: A Baltic Ice Lake lowstand of latest Allerød age in the Arkona basin, southern Baltic Sea, *Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland Bulletin*, 28, 17–20, <https://doi.org/10.34194/geusb.v28.4710>, 2013.
- Bennike, O. and Kelly, M.: Radiocarbon dating of samples collected during the 1984 expedition to North Greenland, *Rapport Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 135, 8–10, 1987.
- Bennike, O. and Lemke, W.: Late-glacial and early Postglacial finds of *Ancylus fluviatilis* from the southwestern Baltic Sea, *GFF*, 123, 81–84, <https://doi.org/10.1080/11035890101232081>, 2001.
- Bennike, O. and Wagner, B.: Deglaciation chronology, sea-level changes and environmental changes from Holocene lake sediments of Germania Havn Sø, Sabine Ø, northeast Greenland, *Quaternary Research*, 78, 103–109, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yqres.2012.03.004>, 2012.

- Bennike, O. and Weidick, A.: Late Quaternary history around Nioghalvfjærdsfjorden and Jøkelbugten, North-East Greenland, *Boreas*, 30, 205–227, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2001.tb01223.x>, 2001.
- Bennike, O., Jensen, J. B., Konradi, P. B., Lemke, W., and Heinemeier, J.: Early Holocene drowned lagoonal deposits from the Kattegat, southern Scandinavia, *Boreas*, 29, 272–286, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2000.tb01210.x>, 2000.
- Bennike, O., Björck, S., and Lambeck, K.: Estimates of South Greenland late-glacial ice limits from a new relative sea level curve, *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 197, 171–186, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0012-821X\(02\)00478-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0012-821X(02)00478-8), 2002.
- Bennike, O., Jensen, J. B., Lemke, W., Kuijpers, A., and Lomholt, S.: Late- and postglacial history of the Great Belt, Denmark, *Boreas*, 33, 18–33, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2004.tb00993.x>, 2004.
- Bennike, O., Wagner, B., and Richter, A.: Relative sea level changes during the Holocene in the Sisimiut area, south-western Greenland, *Journal of Quaternary Science*, 26, 353–361, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.1458>, 2011.
- Bennike, O., Andreasen, M. S., Jensen, J. B., Moros, M., and Noe-Nygaard, N.: Early Holocene sea-level changes in Øresund, southern Scandinavia, *Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland Bulletin*, 26, 29–32, <https://doi.org/10.34194/geusb.v26.4744>, 2012.
- Bennike, O., Pantmann, P., and Aarsleff, E.: Holocene development of the Arresø area, north-east Sjælland, Denmark, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark*, 65, 25–35, <https://doi.org/10.37570/bgsd-2017-65-02>, 2017.
- Bentley, M. J., Hodgson, D. A., Smith, J. A., and Cox, N. J.: Relative sea level curves for the South Shetland Islands and Marguerite Bay, Antarctic Peninsula, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 24, 1203–1216, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2004.10.004>, 2005.
- Berendsen, H. J. A., Makaske, B., van de Plassche, O., Van Ree, M. H. M., Das, S., van Dongen, M., Ploumen, S., and Schoenmakers, W.: New groundwater-level rise data from the Rhine-Meuse delta—implications for the reconstruction of Holocene relative mean sea-level rise and differential land-level movements, *Netherlands Journal of Geosciences/Geologie en Mijnbouw*, 86, 333–354, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0016774600023568>, 2007.
- Berg, S., Wagner, B., Cremer, H., Leng, M. J., and Melles, M.: Late Quaternary environmental and climate history of Rauer Group, East Antarctica, *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 297, 201–213, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2010.08.002>, 2010a.
- Berg, S., Wagner, B., White, D. A., and Melles, M.: No significant ice-sheet expansion beyond present ice margins during the past 4500 yr at Rauer Group, East Antarctica, *Quaternary Research*, 74, 23–25, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yqres.2010.04.004>, 2010b.
- Berg, S., White, D. A., Bennike, O., Fülöp, R.-H., Fink, D., Wagner, B., and Melles, M.: Unglaciaded areas in East Antarctica during the Last Glacial (Marine Isotope Stage 3) – New evidence from Rauer Group, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 153, 1–10, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2016.08.021>, 2016.
- Berglund, B. E.: The post-glacial shore displacement in eastern Blekinge, southeastern Sweden, Series C 599, Sveriges Geologiska Undersökning, Stockholm, Sweden, URL <https://apps.sgu.se/geologagret/GetMetaDataById?id=md-6535f148-fe08-4a7b-8d0e-3119f0f8ec91>, 1964.

- Berglund, B. E.: Littorina Transgressions in Blekinge, South Sweden a Preliminary Survey, *Geologiska Föreningen i Stockholm Förhandlingar*, 93, 625–652, <https://doi.org/10.1080/11035897109455389>, 1971.
- Berglund, M.: The architecture at three Saqqaq sites in the Nuuk Fjord, Greenland, *Études/Inuit/Studies*, 27, 329–346, <https://doi.org/10.7202/010807ar>, Language: English with French abstract, 2003.
- Berglund, M.: Holocene shore displacement and chronology in Ångermanland, eastern Sweden, the Scandinavian glacio-isostatic uplift centre, *Boreas*, 33, 48–60, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2004.tb00995.x>, 2004.
- Berglund, M.: The Holocene shore displacement of Gästrikland, eastern Sweden: a contribution to the knowledge of Scandinavian glacio-isostatic uplift, *Journal of Quaternary Science*, 20, 519–531, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.928>, 2005.
- Berglund, M.: Time-transgressive early Holocene vegetational succession following shore displacement: a case study from central Sweden, *Boreas*, 37, 87–101, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2007.00005.x>, 2008.
- Berglund, M.: Litorina Sea shore displacement and pollen analytical indications of forest succession during the Mid-Holocene in Gästrikland, east central Sweden, *GFF*, 132, 213–226, <https://doi.org/10.1080/11035897.2010.530352>, 2010.
- Berglund, M.: Early Holocene in Gästrikland, east central Sweden: shore displacement and isostatic recovery, *Boreas*, 41, 263–276, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2011.00228.x>, 2012.
- Best, K. M.: Quaternary geologic evolution of the Croatan beach ridge complex, Bogue Sound, and Bogue Banks, Carteret County, NC, Master's thesis, Department of Geological Sciences, East Carolina University, Greenville, NC, United States, URL <https://thescholarship.ecu.edu/handle/10342/2703>, 2010.
- Bhiry, N., Garneau, M., and Filion, L.: Macrofossil record of a middle Holocene drop in relative sea level at the St. Lawrence estuary, Québec, *Quaternary Research*, 54, 228–237, <https://doi.org/10.1006/qres.2000.2160>, 2000.
- Bierman, P. R., Rood, D. H., Shakun, J. D., Portenga, E. W., and Corbett, L. B.: Directly dating post-glacial Greenlandic land-surface emergence at high resolution using in situ ^{10}Be , *Quaternary Research*, 90, 110–126, <https://doi.org/10.1017/qua.2018.6>, 2018.
- Bird, E. C. F.: The fringing reefs near Yule Point, north Queensland, *Australian Geographical Studies*, 9, 107–115, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8470.1971.tb00254.x>, 1971.
- Bird, M. I., Fifield, L. K., Teh, T. S., Chang, C. H., Shirlaw, N., and Lambeck, K.: An inflection in the rate of early mid-Holocene eustatic sea-level rise: A new sea-level curve from Singapore, *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 71, 523–536, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2006.07.004>, 2007.
- Bird, M. I., Austin, W. E., Wurster, C. M., Fifield, L. K., Mojtahid, M., and Sargeant, C.: Punctuated eustatic sea-level rise in the early mid-Holocene, *Geology*, 38, 803–806, <https://doi.org/10.1130/G31066.1>, 2010.
- Bitinas, A., Damušytė, A., Hütt, G., Martma, T., Ruplėnaitė, G., Stančikaitė, M., Ūsaiytė, D., and Vaikmäe, R.: Stratigraphic correlation of Late Weichselian and Holocene deposits in the Lithuanian coastal region, *Proceedings of the Estonian Academy of Sciences, Geology*, 49, 200–217, <https://doi.org/10.3176/geol.2000.3.03>, Language: English with Estonian and Russian abstracts, 2000.

- Bitinas, A., Damušyte, A., Hütt, G., Jaek, I., and Kabailiene, M.: Application of the OSL dating for stratigraphic correlation of Late Weichselian and Holocene sediments in the Lithuanian Maritime Region, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 20, 767–772, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(00\)00011-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(00)00011-1), tL/ESR Special, 2001.
- Bitinas, A., Damušytė, A., Stančikaitė, M., and Aleksa, P.: Geological development of the Nemunas River Delta and adjacent areas, West Lithuania, *Geological Quarterly*, 46, 375–390, URL <http://yadda.icm.edu.pl/baztech/element/bwmeta1.element/baztech-article-BAT3-0013-0044>, 2002.
- Bitinas, A., Žulkus, V., Mažeika, J., Petrošius, R., and Kisielienė, D.: Tree remains on the Baltic seabed: first results, *Geologija*, 43, 43–46, title translated with DeepL, Language: Lithuanian with English and Russian abstracts, Title (in original language): Medžių liekanos Baltijos jūros dugne: pirmieji tyrimų rezultatai, 2003.
- Bitinas, A., Mažeika, J., Buynevich, I. V., Damušytė, A., Molodkov, A., and Grigienė, A.: Constraints of radiocarbon dating in southeastern Baltic lagoons: assessing the vital effects, in: *Coastline Changes of the Baltic Sea from South to East*, edited by Harff, J., Furmanczyk, K., and von Storch, H., vol. 19 of *Coastal Research Library*, pp. 137–171, Springer, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-49894-2_8, 2017.
- Björck, S., Bennike, O., Ingólfsson, Ó., Barnekow, L., and Penney, D. N.: Lake Boksehandsken's earliest postglacial sediments and their palaeoenvironmental implications, Jameson Land, East Greenland, *Boreas*, 23, 459–472, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1994.tb00613.x>, 1994a.
- Björck, S., Wohlfarth, B., Bennike, O., Hjort, C., and Persson, T.: Revision of the early Holocene lake sediment based chronology and event stratigraphy on Hochstetter Forland, NE Greenland, *Boreas*, 23, 513–523, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1994.tb00619.x>, 1994b.
- Blake, S. G.: Processes controlling sediment and nutrient concentrations in the Whitsunday Islands area: implications for fringing reef communities, Ph.D. thesis, James Cook University of North Queensland, Townsville, Queensland, Australia, 1994.
- Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XXII, Paper 82-7, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/109271>, 1982.
- Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XXIII, Paper 83-7, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/119723>, Language: English with French abstract, 1983.
- Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XXIV, Paper 84-7, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/120004>, 1984.
- Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XXV, Paper 85-7, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/120615>, Language: English with French abstract, 1986.
- Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XXVI, Paper 87-7, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/122368>, 1987.
- Blake, W.: Lake sediments and glacial history in the High Arctic; evidence from east-central Ellesmere Island, Arctic Canada, and from Inglefield Land, Greenland, *Polar Research*, 5, 341–343, <https://doi.org/10.3402/polar.v5i3.6909>, 1987.
- Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XXVII, Paper 87-7, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/126099>, Language: English with French abstract, 1988.

- Blake, W. and Lowdon, J. A.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XVI, Paper 76-7, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/102617>, Language: English with French abstract, 1976.
- Blake, W., Jackson, H. R., and Currie, C. G.: Seafloor evidence for glaciation, northernmost Baffin Bay, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark*, 43, 157–168, <https://doi.org/10.37570/bgds-1996-43-15>, 1996.
- Bloom, A. L.: Late-Pleistocene fluctuations of sealevel and postglacial crustal rebound in coastal Maine, *American Journal of Science*, 261, 862–879, <https://doi.org/10.2475/ajs.261.9.862>, 1963.
- Bolshiyarov, D. Y. and Makeev, V. M.: Severnaya Zemlya Archipelago, in: *Glaciations and Environmental History*, p. 21, *Gidrometeoizdat*, Saint-Petersburg, Russia, (In Russian), Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): БОЛЬШИЯРОВ, Д. Ю. and М., Макеев В., Title (in original language): Архипелаг Северная Земля, *Journal/book (in original language): Архипелаг Северная Земля – оледенение, история развития природной среды*, 1995.
- Bolshiyarov, D. Y., Anokhin, V. M., and Gusev, E. A.: New data on geomorphology and Quaternary geology of Novaya Zemlya archipelago, in: *Geologic-geophysical characteristics of the Arctic lithosphere*, vol. 210 of *Mater.VNI Okeangeologiya*, pp. 149–161, The name of the publisher, Saint-Petersburg, Russia, URL <http://www.evgengusev.narod.ru/nov/bolsh.html>, (In Russian), Language: Russian with English abstract, Authors (in original language): БОЛЬШИЯРОВ, Д. Ю., АНОХИН, В. М., and ГУСЕВ, Е. А., Title (in original language): НОВЫЕ ДАННЫЕ О СТРОЕНИИ РЕЛЬЕФА И ЧЕТВЕРТИЧНЫХ ОТЛОЖЕНИЙ АРХИПЕЛАГА НОВАЯ ЗЕМЛЯ, *Journal/book (in original language): ГЕОЛОГО-ГЕОФИЗИЧЕСКИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ЛИТОСФЕРЫ АРКТИЧЕСКОГО РЕГИОНА*, 2006.
- Bolshiyarov, D. Y., Pogodina, I. A., Gusev, E. A., Sharin, V. V., Alekseev, V. V., Dymov, V. A., Anokhin, V. M., Anikina, N. Y., and Derevianko, L. G.: New data on coastlines of archipelagos Franz-Josef land, Novaya Zemlya and Spitsbergen, *Arctic and Antarctic Research (Problemy Arktiki i Antarktiki)*, 82, 68–77, URL http://old.aari.ru/misc/publicat/paa_statia.php?arh=1&ns=139&jur=129, Language: Russian with English abstract, Authors (in original language): Ю.Большияров, Д., Погодина, И. А., А.Гусев, Е., Шарин, В. В., Алексеев, В. В., Дымов, В. А., Анохин, В. М., Аникина, Н. Ю., and Деревянко, Л. Г., Title (in original language): Новые данные по береговым линиям архипелагов Земля Франца Иосифа, Новая Земля и Шпицберген, *Journal/book (in original language): Проблемы Арктики и Антарктики*, 2009.
- Bolshiyarov, D. Y., Makarov, A. S., Schneider, V., and Stof, G.: Origin and Evolution of the Lena Delta, the Arctic and Antarctic Research Institute Publishing House, Saint-Petersburg, Russia, URL <http://www.evgengusev.narod.ru/laptev/bolshiyarov-2013.html>, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): БОЛЬШИЯРОВ, Д. Ю., Макаров, А. С., and Шнайдер В. abd Штоф, Г., Title (in original language): Происхождение и развитие дельты реки Лены, 2013.
- Boyarskaya, T. D., Polyakova, E. I., and Svitoch, A. A.: New data on the White Sea Holocene transgression, *Doklady of the USSR Academy of Sciences*, 290, 964–968, title translated with DeepL, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Боярская, Т Д, Полякова, Е И, and Свиточ, А А, Title (in original language): Новые данные о голоценовой трансгрессии Белого моря, *Journal/book (in original language): ДАН СССР*, 1986.
- Braddock, S., Hall, B. L., Johnson, J. S., Balco, G., Spoth, M., Whitehouse, P. L., Campbell, S., Goehring, B. M., Rood, D. H., and Woodward, J.: Relative sea-level data preclude major late Holocene ice-mass change in Pine Island Bay, *Nature Geoscience*, -, -, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-022-00961-y>, 2022.

- Brandt, K.: The elevation of prehistoric and early historic habitation in the marshlands of northwestern Germany as height indicators of former water levels, *E&G Quaternary Science Journal*, 30, 161–170, <https://doi.org/10.3285/eg.30.1.13>, Language: German with English abstract, Title (in original language): Die Höhenlage ur- und frühgeschichtlicher Wohnniveaus in nordwestdeutschen Marschengebieten als Höhenmarken ehemaliger Wasserstände, 1980.
- Brandt, K.: The results in the excavations of the Wurten Niens and Sievertsborch (Wesermarsch district), *Probleme der Küstenforschung im südlichen Nordseegebiet*, 18, 89–140, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Die Ergebnisse in den Grabungen der Wurten Niens und Sievertsborch (Kreis Wesermarsch), 1991.
- Briggs, R. D. and Tarasov, L.: How to evaluate model-derived deglaciation chronologies: a case study using Antarctica, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 63, 109–127, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2012.11.021>, 2013.
- Brodeur, D. and Allard, M.: Quaternary Stratigraphy of Île aux Coudres, Middle St. Lawrence Estuary, Québec, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 39, 183–197, <https://doi.org/10.7202/032601ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): Stratigraphie et Quaternaire de l' Île aux Coudres, estuaire moyen du Saint-Laurent, Québec, 1985.
- Bronk Ramsey, C.: Bayesian analysis of radiocarbon dates, *Radiocarbon*, 51, 337–360, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200033865>, 2009.
- Brookes, I., Scott, D. B., and McAndrews, J.: Postglacial relative sea-level change, Port au Port area, west Newfoundland, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 22, 1039–1047, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e85-107>, Language: English with French abstract, 1985.
- Brookes, I. A. and Stevens, R. K.: Radiocarbon age of rock-boring *Hiattella arctica* (Linné) and post-glacial sea-level change at Cow Head, Newfoundland, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 22, 136–140, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e85-012>, Language: English with French abstract, 1985.
- Brown, R. G., Treloar, J. M., and Clifton, P. M.: Sediments and organic detritus in the Peel-Harvey Estuary, Bulletin 90, Western Australia. Department of Conservation and Environment, 1980.
- Bryant, E. A., Young, R. W., Price, D. M., and Short, S. A.: Evidence for Pleistocene and Holocene raised marine deposits, Sandon Point, New South Wales, *Australian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 39, 481–493, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08120099208728040>, 1992.
- Buckley, J. and Valdes-Pages, C.: Teledyne Isotopes Radiocarbon Measurements XII, *Radiocarbon*, 23, 329–344, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200037747>, 1981.
- Buckley, J. D. and Willis, E. H.: Isotopes' radiocarbon measurements VIII, *Radiocarbon*, 12, 87–129, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200036225>, 1970.
- Bunbury, J., Finkelstein, S. A., and Bollmann, J.: Holocene hydro-climatic change and effects on carbon accumulation inferred from a peat bog in the Attawapiskat River watershed, Hudson Bay Lowlands, Canada, *Quaternary Research*, 78, 275–284, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yqres.2012.05.013>, 2012.
- Bungenstock, F., Freund, H., and Bartholomä, A.: Holocene relative sea-level data for the East Frisian barrier coast, NW Germany, southern North Sea, *Netherlands Journal of Geosciences*, 100, e16, <https://doi.org/10.1017/njg.2021.11>, 2021.
- Bērziņš, V., Lübke, H., B. L., Ceriņa, A., Kalniņa, L., Meadows, J., Muižniece, S., Paegle, S., Rudzīte, M., and Zagorska, I.: Recurrent Mesolithic–Neolithic occupation at Sise (western Latvia) and shoreline displacement in the Baltic Sea Basin, *The Holocene*, 26, 1319–1325, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683616638434>, 2016.

- Cabioch, G. and Ayliffe, L. K.: Raised Coral Terraces at Malakula, Vanuatu, Southwest Pacific, Indicate High Sea Level During Marine Isotope Stage 3, *Quaternary Research*, 56, 357–365, <https://doi.org/10.1006/qres.2001.2265>, 2001.
- Cabioch, G., Banks-Cutler, K. A., Beck, W. J., Burr, G. S., Corrège, T., Edwards, R. L., and Taylor, F. W.: Continuous reef growth during the last 23 cal kyr BP in a tectonically active zone (Vanuatu, SouthWest Pacific), *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 22, 1771–1786, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(03\)00170-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(03)00170-7), 2003.
- Camoin, G. F., Ebrén, P., Eisenhauer, A., Bard, E., and Faure, G.: A 300 000-yr coral reef record of sea level changes, Mururoa atoll (Tuamotu archipelago, French Polynesia), *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 175, 325–341, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-0182\(01\)00378-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0031-0182(01)00378-9), 2001.
- Cann, J. H., Belperio, A. P., Gostin, V. A., and Murray-Wallace, C. V.: Sea-level history, 45,000 to 30,000 yr B.P., inferred from Benthic foraminifera, Gulf St. Vincent, South Australia, *Quaternary Research*, 29, 153–175, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894\(88\)90058-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894(88)90058-0), 1988.
- Cann, J. H., Belperio, A. P., Gostin, V. A., and Rice, R. L.: Contemporary benthic foraminifera in Gulf St Vincent, South Australia, and a refined Late Pleistocene sea-level history, *Australian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 40, 197–211, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08120099308728074>, 1993.
- Carne, R. J.: Landform–vegetation relationship in the Minnamurra Estuary, New South Wales, BSc Honours thesis, University of Wollongong, 1981.
- Carter, R. M., Johnson, D. P., and Hooper, K. G.: Episodic post-glacial sea-level rise and the sedimentary evolution of a tropical continental embayment (Cleveland Bay, Great Barrier Reef shelf, Australia), *Australian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 40, 229–255, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08120099308728077>, 1993.
- Catto, N. R., Griffiths, H., Jones, S., and Porter, H.: Late Holocene sea level changes, eastern Newfoundland, Current Research Report 2000-1, Newfoundland Department of Mines and Energy, Geological Survey, URL <https://www.gov.nl.ca/iet/mines/geoscience/reports-maps/currentresearch/current-research-2000/>, 2000.
- Cayer, D.: Post-marine and Holocene history of a subarctic lake, sedimentology, mineralogy and isotope geochemistry, Master's thesis, Université Laval, Québec, Canada, URL <http://www.collectionscanada.gc.ca/obj/s4/f2/dsk4/etd/MQ76314.pdf>, title translated with DeepL, Language: French, Title (in original language): Histoire post-marine et Holocène d'un lac subarctique, sédimentologie, minéralogie et géochimie isotopique, 2003.
- Chappell, J.: Sea level changes forced ice breakouts in the Last Glacial cycle: new results from coral terraces, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 21, 1229–1240, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(01\)00141-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(01)00141-X), decadal-to-Millennial-Scale Climate Variability, 2002.
- Chappell, J. and Polach, H.: Post-glacial sea-level rise from a coral record at Huon Peninsula, Papua New Guinea, *Nature*, 349, 147–149, <https://doi.org/10.1038/349147a0>, 1991.
- Chappell, J., Chivas, A. R., Wallensky, E., Polach, H. A., and Aharon, P.: Holocene Palaeo-Environmental changes, central to north Great Barrier Reef inner zone, *BMR Journal of Australian Geology & Geophysics*, 8, 223–235, URL <https://researchdata.edu.au/holocene-palaeo-environmental-inner-zone>, 1983.

- Chappell, J., Omura, A., Esat, T., McCulloch, M., Pandolfi, J., Ota, Y., and Pillans, B.: Reconciliation of late Quaternary sea levels derived from coral terraces at Huon Peninsula with deep sea oxygen isotope records, *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 141, 227–236, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0012-821X\(96\)00062-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0012-821X(96)00062-3), 1996.
- Christensen, C.: Sea level changes 5500-2500 BC in the Vedbæk area, NØ-Sjælland, in: *Dansk Geologisk Forening Årsskrift 1981*, pp. 91–107, Dansk Geologisk Forening, URL <https://2dggf.dk/aarsskrift/dansk-geologisk-forening-aarsskrift-1981/>, title translated with DeepL, Language: Danish with English abstract, Title (in original language): Havniveauændringer 5500-2500 f.Kr. i Vedbækområdet, NØ-Sjælland, 1982.
- Christensen, C.: Sea level changes 6000-3000 BC in the Vedbæk area, NØ-Sjælland - continued geobotanical studies in the years 1982-1990, NNU-rapport 15, Nationalmuseets Naturvidenskabelige Undersøgelser, URL <https://natmus.dk/organisation/forskning-samling-og-bevaring/miljoearkæologi-materialeforskning/arkæobotanik/arkæobotanisk-rapportoversigt/rapportoversigt-2014/>, title translated with DeepL, Language: Danish, Title (in original language): Havniveauændringer 6000-3000 f.Kr. i Vedbæk-området, NØ-Sjælland - fortsatte geobotaniske undersøgelser i årene 1982-1990, 2014.
- Christensen, C. and Nielsen, A. B.: Dating Littorina Sea shore levels in Denmark on the basis of data from a Mesolithic coastal settlement on Skagens Odde, Northern Jutland, *Polish Geological Institute Special Papers*, 23, 27–38, URL <https://yadda.icm.edu.pl/yadda/element/bwmeta1.element.baztech-article-BUS6-0020-0021>, 2008.
- Christensen, C., Fischer, A., and Mathiasen, D. R.: The great sea rise in the Storebælt, in: *The Danish Storebælt since the Ice Age*, edited by Pedersen, L., Fischer, A., and Aaby, B., pp. 45–54 and 323–324, A/S Storebæltsforbindelsen, Copenhagen, 1997.
- Christiansen, C., Conradsen, K., Emelyanov, E., Trimonis, E., Heinemeier, J., and Rud, N.: Hydrographic changes in the southern Kattegat (Scandinavia) during the early Holocene transgression, *Boreas*, 22, 349–356, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1993.tb00198.x>, 1993.
- Christiansen, H. H., Bennike, O., Böcher, J., Elberling, B., Humlum, O., and Jakobsen, B. H.: Holocene environmental reconstruction from deltaic deposits in northeast Greenland, *Journal of Quaternary Science*, 17, 145–160, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.665>, 2002.
- Cinquemani, L. J., Newman, W. S., Sperling, J. A., Marcus, L. F., and Pardi, R. R.: Holocene sea level fluctuations, magnitudes and causes, in: *IGCP Annual Meeting*, Columbia, South Carolina, 1982.
- Clark, K., Cochran, U., and Mazengarb, C.: Holocene coastal evolution and evidence for paleotsunami from a tectonically stable region, Tasmania, Australia, *The Holocene*, 21, 883–895, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683610391317>, 2011.
- Clark, P. U. and Fitzhugh, W. W.: Late deglaciation of the central Labrador coast and its implications for the age of glacial lakes Naskaupi and McLean and for prehistory, *Quaternary Research*, 34, 296–305, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894\(90\)90042-J](https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894(90)90042-J), 1990.
- Collins, L. B., Zhao, J.-X., and Freeman, H.: A high-precision record of mid-late Holocene sea-level events from emergent coral pavements in the Houtman Abrolhos Islands, southwest Australia, *Quaternary International*, 145-146, 78–85, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2005.07.006>, quaternary sea-level changes: contributions from the 32nd IGC, 2006.

- Colman, S. M., Baucom, P. C., Bratton, J. F., Cronin, T. M., McGeehin, J. P., Willard, D., Zimmerman, A. R., and Vogt, P. R.: Radiocarbon dating, chronologic framework, and changes in accumulation rates of Holocene estuarine sediments from Chesapeake Bay, *Quaternary Research*, 57, 58–70, <https://doi.org/10.1006/qres.2001.2285>, 2002.
- Corner, G. D., Yevzerov, V. Y., Kolka, V. V., and Møller, J. J.: Isolation basin stratigraphy and Holocene relative sea-level change at the Norwegian—Russian border north of Nikel, northwest Russia, *Boreas*, 28, 146–166, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1999.tb00211.x>, 1999.
- Corner, G. D., Kolka, V. V., Yevzerov, V. Y., and Møller, J. J.: Postglacial relative sea-level change and stratigraphy of raised coastal basins on Kola Peninsula, northwest Russia, *Global and Planetary Change*, 31, 155–177, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-8181\(01\)00118-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-8181(01)00118-7), 2001.
- Crowley, G. M., Anderson, P., Kershaw, A., and Grindrod, J.: Palynology of a Holocene marine transgressive sequence, lower Mulgrave River valley, north-east Queensland, *Australian Journal of Ecology*, 15, 231–240, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1442-9993.1990.tb01532.x>, 1990.
- Culver, S. J., Pre, C. G., Mallinson, D. J., Riggs, S. R., Corbett, D. R., Foley, J., Hale, M., Metger, L., Ricardo, J., Rosenberger, J., Smith, C. G., Smith, C. W., Snyder, S. W., and Twamley, D.: Late Holocene barrier island collapse: Outer Banks, North Carolina, USA, *The Sedimentary Record*, 5, 4–8, <https://doi.org/10.2110/sedred.2007.4.4>, 2007.
- Culver, S. J., Farrell, K. M., Mallinson, D. J., Willard, D. A., Horton, B. P., Riggs, S. R., Thieler, E. R., Wehmiller, J. F., Parham, P., Snyder, S. W., and Hillier, C.: Micropaleontologic record of Quaternary paleoenvironments in the Central Albemarle Embayment, North Carolina, U.S.A., *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 305, 227–249, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2011.03.004>, 2011.
- Cutler, K. B., Edwards, R. L., Taylor, F. W., Cheng, H., Adkins, J., Gallup, C. D., Cutler, P. M., Burr, G. S., and Bloom, A. L.: Rapid sea-level fall and deep-ocean temperature change since the last interglacial period, *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 206, 253–271, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0012-821X\(02\)01107-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0012-821X(02)01107-X), 2003.
- Cutler, K. B., Gray, S. C., Burr, G. S., Edwards, R. L., Taylor, F. W., Cabioch, G., Beck, J. W., Cheng, H., and Moore, J.: Radiocarbon calibration and comparison to 50 kyr BP with paired ^{14}C and ^{230}Th dating of corals from Vanuatu and Papua New Guinea, *Radiocarbon*, 46, 1127–1160, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200033063>, 2004.
- Daigneault, R. A.: Géologie du Quaternaire du nord de la péninsule d'Ungava, Québec, Bulletin 533, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/224807>, Language: French with English abstract, 2008.
- Dalrymple, R. W. and Zaitlin, B. A.: High-resolution sequence stratigraphy of a complex, incised valley succession, Cobequid Bay—Salmon River estuary, Bay of Fundy, Canada, *Sedimentology*, 41, 1069–1091, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3091.1994.tb01442.x>, 1994.
- Daly, J. F., Belknap, D. F., Kelley, J. T., and Bell, T.: Late Holocene sea-level change around Newfoundland, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 44, 1453–1465, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e07-036>, Language: English with French abstract, 2007.
- Damušytė, A.: Post-glacial geological history of the Lithuanian coastal area, Summaries of doctoral thesis, Vilnius University, URL <https://epublications.vu.lt/object/elaba:2045985/>, Language: English with Lithuanian summary, 2011.

- de Gelder, G., Husson, L., Pastier, A.-M., Fernández-Blanco, D., Pico, T., Chauveau, D., Authemayou, C., and Pedoja, K.: High interstadial sea levels over the past 420ka from the Huon Peninsula, Papua New Guinea, *Communications Earth & Environment*, 3, 1–12, <https://doi.org/10.31223/X5C03Z>, 2022.
- de Klerk, L. G.: Sea levels, reefs and coastal plains of southwest Sulawesi, Indonesië; a morphogenetic-pedological study, Ph.D. thesis, Department of Geography, University of Utrecht, Utrecht, Netherlands, Language: Dutch with abstracts in English and Indonesian, Title (in original language): Zeespiegels, riffen en kustvlakten in zuidwest Sulawesi, Indonesië; een morfogenetisch-bodemkundige studie, 1982.
- Deevey, E. S., Gralenski, L. J., and Hoffren, V.: Yale Natural Radiocarbon Measurements IV, *Radiocarbon*, 1, 144–172, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200020440>, 1959.
- Del Valle, R. A., Montalti, D., and Inbar, M.: Mid-Holocene macrofossil-bearing raised marine beaches at Potter Peninsula, King George Island, South Shetland Islands, *Antarctic Science*, 14, 263–269, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0954102002000081>, 2002.
- Denys, L. and Baeteman, C.: Holocene evolution of relative sea level and local mean high water spring tides in Belgium—a first assessment, *Marine Geology*, 124, 1–19, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(95\)00029-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(95)00029-X), coastal Evolution in the Quarternary: IGCP Project 274, 1995.
- Deschamps, P., Durand, N., Bard, E., Hamelin, B., Camoin, G., Thomas, A. L., Henderson, G. M., Okuno, J., and Yokoyama, Y.: Ice-sheet collapse and sea-level rise at the Bølling warming 14,600 years ago, *Nature*, 483, 559–564, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature10902>, 2012.
- Devyatova, E. I. and Liyva, A. A.: Towards a late- and post-glacial history of the White Sea, in: Nature, coastal formations and development history of inland waters and seas of the Eastern Baltic and Karelia, pp. 15–16, Petrozavodsk, title translated with DeepL, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Девятова, Э.И. and А., Лийва А., Title (in original language): К поздне- и послеледниковой истории Белого моря, *Journal/book (in original language): Природа, береговые образования и история развития внутренних водоемов и морей Восточной Прибалтики и Карелии*, 1971.
- Dibner, V. D.: The history of late Pleistocene and Holocene sedimentation in Franz Josef Land, *Transactions of the Scientific Research Institute of the Geology of the Arctic*, 143, 300–318, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Дибнер, В.Д., Title (in original language): История формирования позднеплейстоценовых и голоценовых отложений Земли Франца-Иосифа, *Journal/book (in original language): Антропогенный период в Арктике и субарктике*, 1965.
- Dietrich, P., Ghienne, J.-F., Schuster, M., Lajeunesse, P., Nutz, A., Deschamps, R., Roquin, C., and Düringer, P.: From outwash to coastal systems in the Portneuf–Forestville deltaic complex (Québec North Shore): Anatomy of a forced regressive deglacial sequence, *Sedimentology*, 64, 1044–1078, <https://doi.org/10.1111/sed.12340>, 2017.
- Dionne, J.-C.: Holocene Relative Sea-Level Fluctuations in the St. Lawrence Estuary, Québec, Canada, *Quaternary Research*, 29, 233–244, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894\(88\)90032-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894(88)90032-4), 1988.
- Dionne, J.-C.: Observations on the Relative Sea Level During the Holocene, at Rivière-du-Loup, St. Lawrence Estuary, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 44, 43–53, <https://doi.org/10.7202/032797ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): Observations sur le niveau marin relatif à l' Holocène, à Rivière-du-Loup, estuaire du Saint-Laurent, Québec, 1990.

- Dionne, J.-C.: The Mitis Terrace at Pointe aux Alouettes, North Shore of the Middle St. Lawrence Estuary, Québec, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 50, 57–72, <https://doi.org/10.7202/033075ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): La terrasse Mitis à la pointe aux Alouettes, côte nord du moyen estuaire du Saint-Laurent, Québec, 1996.
- Dionne, J.-C.: Additional Evidence for the Laurentian Transgression on the South Shore of the Middle St. Lawrence Estuary, Québec, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 51, 201–210, <https://doi.org/10.7202/033118ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): Nouvelles données sur la transgression Laurentienne, côte sud du moyen estuaire du Saint-Laurent, Québec, 1997.
- Dionne, J.-C.: Discovery of a middle Holocene fossilized landslide, at Montmagny, south shore of the St. Lawrence estuary, Québec, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 52, 123–130, <https://doi.org/10.7202/004796ar>, Language: French with English abstract, Title (in original language): Découverte d' un glissement de terrain fossilisé d' âge mi-holocène, à Montmagny, moyen estuaire du Saint-Laurent, Québec, 1998.
- Dionne, J.-C.: Geomorphic observations on the tidal flat and the low terrace at Isle-Verte, south shore of the St. Lawrence estuary, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 53, 277–285, <https://doi.org/10.7202/004860ar>, Language: French with English abstract, Title (in original language): Indices de fluctuations mineures du niveau marin relatif à l' Holocène supérieur, à l' Isle-Verte, côte sud de l' estuaire du Saint-Laurent, Québec, 1999.
- Dionne, J.-C.: Relict Tree Logs on the Tidal Flat at Anse de Bellechasse (Québec): Evidence for a Minor Relative Sea Level Fluctuation in Late Holocene, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 55, 301–306, URL <https://id.erudit.org/iderudit/006857ar>, Language: French with English abstract, Title (in original language): Troncs d' arbres fossiles sur la batture de l'anse de Bellechasse (Québec) : indice d' une fluctuation mineure du niveau marin relatif à l' Holocène supérieur, 2001a.
- Dionne, J.-C.: Dolostone erratics at Cap Colombier, North Shore of the Lower St. Lawrence estuary, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 55, 101–107, <https://doi.org/10.7202/005656ar>, Language: French with English abstract, Title (in original language): Erratiques de dolomie au Cap Colombier, sur la haute Côte-Nord du Saint-Laurent estuarien, 2001b.
- Dionne, J.-C.: Geomorphic aspects of baie du Haha, Bic National Park, Lower St. Lawrence estuary (Québec), *Bulletin de recherche 177*, Département de géomatique appliquée, Université de Sherbrooke, URL https://www.usherbrooke.ca/geomatique/fileadmin/sites/flsh/geomatique/bulletin_177.pdf, Language: French with English abstract, Title (in original language): Aspects géomorphologiques de la baie du Haha, parc national du Bic, Bas-Saint-Laurent (Québec), 2005.
- Dionne, J.-C. and Coll, D.: The Relative Sea Level in the Area of Matane (Québec), from the Deglaciation to Present Day, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 49, 363–380, <https://doi.org/10.7202/033060ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): Le niveau marin relatif dans la région de Matane (Québec), de la déglaciation à nos jours, 1995.
- Dionne, J.-C. and Occhietti, S.: An Outline of the Quaternary of the Saguenay at its Entry, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 50, 5–34, <https://doi.org/10.7202/033072ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): Aperçu du Quaternaire à l' embouchure du Saguenay, Québec, 1996.

- Dionne, J.-C., Dubois, J.-M., and Bernatchez, P.: The Mitis Terrace at pointe de Mille-Vaches (Portneuf Peninsula), North Shore of the Lower St. Lawrence Estuary: Nature of Deposits and Evolution of the Relative Sea Level During the Holocene, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 58, 281–295, <https://doi.org/10.7202/013143ar>, Language: French with English abstract, Title (in original language): La terrasse Mitis à la pointe de Mille-Vaches (Péninsule de Portneuf), rive nord de l' estuaire maritime du Saint-Laurent: nature des dépôts et évolution du niveau marin relatif à l' Holocène, 2004.
- Donnelly, J. P.: A revised late Holocene sea-level record for northern Massachusetts, USA, *Journal of Coastal Research*, 22, 1051–1061, <https://doi.org/10.2112/04-0207.1>, 2006.
- Donnelly, J. P., Roll, S., Wengren, M., Butler, J., Lederer, R., and Webb, Thompson, I.: Sedimentary evidence of intense hurricane strikes from New Jersey, *Geology*, 29, 615–618, [https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613\(2001\)029<0615:SEOIHS>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613(2001)029<0615:SEOIHS>2.0.CO;2), 2001.
- Donnelly, J. P., Cleary, P., Newby, P., and Ettinger, R.: Coupling instrumental and geological records of sea-level change: evidence from southern New England of an increase in the rate of sea-level rise in the late 19th century, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 31, –, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2003GL018933>, 2004.
- Donner, J. and Eronen, M.: Stages of the Baltic Sea and Late Quaternary Shoreline Displacement in Finland: Excursion Guide, in: Excursion in Southern Finland with a Symposium at Lammi Biological Station 9.-14. September 1981, p. 44, University of Helsinki. Department of Geology. Division of Geology and Palaeontology, University of Helsinki, 1981.
- Dredge, L. A., Mott, R. J., and Grant, D. R.: Quaternary stratigraphy, paleoecology, and glacial geology, Îles de la Madeleine, Quebec, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 29, 1981–1996, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e92-154>, 1992.
- Dubois, J. M. M., Occhietti, S., Pichet, P., Pagé, P., Jacob, C., and Bigras, P.: Université du Québec a Montréal GEOTOP Radiocarbon Dates I, *Radiocarbon*, 30, 355–365, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200044404>, 1988.
- Dyck, W. and Fyles, J. G.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates I, *Radiocarbon*, 4, 13–26, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200036468>, 1962.
- Dyck, W. and Fyles, J. G.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates II, *Radiocarbon*, 5, 39–55, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200036778>, 1963.
- Dyck, W. and Fyles, J. G.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates III, *Radiocarbon*, 6, 167–181, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200010638>, 1964.
- Dyck, W., Fyles, J. G., and Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates IV, *Radiocarbon*, 7, 24–46, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200037061>, 1965.
- Dyck, W., Lowdon, J., Fyles, J. G., and Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates V, *Radiocarbon*, 8, 96–127, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200000072>, 1966.
- Dyke, A. S. and Peltier, W. R.: Forms, response times and variability of relative sea-level curves, glaciated North America, *Geomorphology*, 32, 315–333, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-555X\(99\)00102-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-555X(99)00102-6), 2000.
- Dyke, A. S., Moore, A., and Robertson, L.: Deglaciation of North America, Open File 1574, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/214399>, Language: English with French abstract, 2003.

- Eberhards, G.: Relief, geological structure and development of the Pūrciems area, in: Neolīta apmetnes Ziemeļkurzemes kāpās, edited by Loze, I., pp. 12–28, Latvijas vēstures institūta apgāds, Rīga, title translated with DeepL, Language: Latvian, Title (in original language): Pūrciemā apkārtnes reljefs, ģeoloģiskā uzbūve un attīstība, 2006.
- Eberhards, G.: Overview of geological and palaeoenvironmental research at area of Stone Age settlement Priedaine, Unpublished report, Repository of archaeological Material, Institute of Latvian History, University of Latvia, Rīga, Language: Latvian, Title (in original language): Pārskats par ģeoloģiskiem un paleovides pētījumiem Priedaines akmens laikmeta apmetnes rajonā, 2008.
- Edgecombe, R. B., Scott, D. B., and Fader, G. B.: New data from Halifax Harbour: paleoenvironment and a new Holocene sea-level curve for the inner Scotian Shelf, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 36, 805–817, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e99-083>, 1999.
- Edwards, R. L., Beck, J. W., Burr, G., Donahue, D. J., Chappell, J. M. A., Bloom, A. L., Druffel, E. R. M., and Taylor, F. W.: A large drop in atmospheric $^{14}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ and reduced melting in the Younger Dryas, documented with ^{230}Th ages of corals, *Science*, 260, 962–968, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.260.5110.962>, 1993.
- Eisenhauer, A., Wasserburg, G. J., Chen, J. H., Bonani, G., Collins, L. B., Zhu, Z. R., and Wyrwoll, K. H.: Holocene sea-level determination relative to the Australian continent: U/Th (TIMS) and ^{14}C (AMS) dating of coral cores from the Abrolhos Islands, *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 114, 529–547, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0012-821X\(93\)90081-J](https://doi.org/10.1016/0012-821X(93)90081-J), 1993.
- Emery, K. O., Wigley, R. L., Bartlett, A. S., Rubin, M., and Barghoorn, E. S.: Freshwater peat on the continental shelf, *Science*, 158, 1301–1307, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.158.3806.1301>, 1967.
- Emslie, S. D. and McDaniel, J. D.: Adélie penguin diet and climate change during the middle to late Holocene in northern Marguerite Bay, Antarctic Peninsula, *Polar Biology*, 25, 222–229, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00300-001-0334-y>, 2002.
- Engelhart, S. E. and Horton, B. P.: Holocene sea level database for the Atlantic coast of the United States, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 54, 12–25, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2011.09.013>, 2012.
- Engelhart, S. E., Horton, B. P., Douglas, B. C., Peltier, W. R., and Törnqvist, T. E.: Spatial variability of late Holocene and 20th century sea-level rise along the Atlantic coast of the United States, *Geology*, 37, 1115–1118, <https://doi.org/10.1130/G30360A.1>, 2009.
- England, J.: The late Quaternary history of Hall Land, northwest Greenland, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 22, 1394–1408, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e85-147>, 1985.
- Eronen, M.: The history of the Litorina Sea and associated Holocene events – Pollen and Diatom Diagrams, *Commentationes Physico Mathematicae*, 44, 1974.
- Eronen, M., Heikkinen, O., and Tikkanen, M.: Holocene development and present hydrology of Lake Pyhäjärvi in Satakunta, southwestern Finland, *Fennia - International Journal of Geography*, 160, 195–223, URL <https://fennia.journal.fi/article/view/9115>, 1982.
- Eronen, M., Glückert, G., van de Plassche, O., van der Plicht, J., Rajala, P., and Rantala, P.: The postglacial radiocarbon-dated shoreline data in Finland for the Nordic Data Base of Land Uplift and Shorelines, Tech. rep., Swedish Nuclear Power Inspectorate (SKI), Project NKS/KAN, subproject 3.2.4.2, 1992–93, Stencil, 1993.

- Eronen, M., Glückert, G., Rantala, P., van de Plassche, O., and van der Plicht, J.: Land uplift in the Olkiluoto-Pyhäjärvi area, southwestern Finland, during the last 8000 years, Report YJT-95-17, Nuclear Waste Commission of Finnish Power Companies, Helsinki, Finland, 1995.
- Eronen, M., Gluckert, G., Hatakka, L., Plassche, O. v. d., Plicht, J. v. d., and Rantala, P.: Rates of Holocene isostatic uplift and relative sea-level lowering of the Baltic in SW Finland based on studies of isolation contacts, *Boreas*, 30, 17–30, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2001.tb00985.x>, 2001.
- Evans, D. J. and Rogerson, R. J.: A radiocarbon-dated gelifluction lobe in the Nachvak Fiord area, northern Labrador, Canada, *Earth surface processes and landforms*, 13, 657–662, <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3290130708>, 1988.
- Ey, J.: The medieval fort Neuwarfen, Gde. Wangerland, Ldkr. Friesland. The results of the excavations in 1991 and 1992, *Probleme der Küstenforschung im südlichen Nordseegebiet*, 23, 265–315, Language: German, Title (in original language): Die mittelalterliche Wurt Neuwarfen, Gde. Wangerland, Ldkr. Friesland. Die Ergebnisse der Grabungen 1991 und 1992, 1995.
- Fairbanks, R. G.: Barbados off shore drilling program cruise report, techreport, Lamont-Doherty Geological Observatory of Columbia University, Palisades, New York, <https://doi.org/10.7916/d8-nc5b-sa43>, r/V Ranger Cruise 88-13, 18/Nov/88 - 6/Dec/88, 1988.
- Fairbanks, R. G., Mortlock, R. A., Chiu, T.-C., Cao, L., Kaplan, A., Guilderson, T. P., Fairbanks, T. W., Bloom, A. L., Grootes, P. M., and Nadeau, M.-J.: Radiocarbon calibration curve spanning 0 to 50,000 years BP based on paired $^{230}\text{Th}/^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ and ^{14}C dates on pristine corals, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 24, 1781–1796, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2005.04.007>, 2005.
- Farrand, W. R.: Postglacial uplift in North America, *American Journal of Science*, 260, 181–199, <https://doi.org/10.2475/ajs.260.3.181>, 1962.
- Field, M. E., Meisburger, E. P., Stanley, E. A., and Williams, S. J.: Upper Quaternary peat deposits on the Atlantic inner shelf of the United States, *GSA Bulletin*, 90, 618–628, [https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606\(1979\)90<618:UQPDOT>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606(1979)90<618:UQPDOT>2.0.CO;2), 1979.
- Filion, L.: Holocene development of parabolic dunes in the central St. Lawrence Lowland, Québec, *Quaternary Research*, 28, 196–209, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894\(87\)90059-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894(87)90059-7), 1987.
- Filion, L., Saint-Laurent, D., Despons, M., and Payette, S.: The late Holocene record of aeolian and fire activity in northern Québec, Canada, *The Holocene*, 1, 201–208, <https://doi.org/10.1177/095968369100100302>, 1991.
- Finkelstein, K. and Ferland, M. A.: Back-barrier response to sea-level rise, eastern shore of Virginia, in: *Special Publications of SEPM*, edited by Nummedal, D., Pilkey, O. H., and Howard, J. D., vol. 41, pp. 145–155, The Society of Economic Paleontologists and Mineralogists, <https://doi.org/10.2110/pec.87.41.0145>, 1987.
- Fischer, A.: Stone Age settlements at the bottom of Øresund. Testing a model Part 1, the central Øresund, *Marinarkæologiske forundersøgelser forud for etablering af en fast Øresundsforbindelse*, Miljøministeriet, Skov- og Naturstyrelsen, title translated with DeepL, Language: Danish, Title (in original language): Stenalderboplads på bunden af Øresund. Afprøvning af en model Del 1, det centrale Øresund, 1993.
- Fischer, A.: Man and the sea in the Palaeolithic, in: *Arkeologi och Naturvetenskap*, edited by Larsson, L., Berglund, B., and Bunte, C., vol. 6 of *Gyllenstjernska Krapperupsstiftelsens symposium*, pp. 277–297, Gyllenstiernska Krapperupsstiftelsen, Lund, title translated by DeepL, Language: Danish, Title (in original language): Mennesket og havet i ældre stenalder, 2005.

- Fitzhugh, W. W.: Environmental archeology and cultural systems in Hamilton Inlet, Labrador: A survey of the central Labrador coast from 3000 BC to the present, *Smithsonian Contributions to Anthropology* 16, Smithsonian Institution, <https://doi.org/10.5479/si.00810223.16.1>, 1972.
- Fitzhugh, W. W.: A maritime archaic sequence from Hamilton Inlet, Labrador, *Arctic Anthropology*, 12, 117–138, URL <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40315878>, 1975.
- Fletcher, C. H., Van Pelt, J. E., Brush, G. S., and Sherman, J.: Tidal wetland record of Holocene sea-level movements and climate history, *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 102, 177–213, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-0182\(93\)90067-S](https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-0182(93)90067-S), 1993.
- Flood, P. G.: Holocene sea level data from the southern Great Barrier Reef and southeastern Queensland – A review, in: *Australian Sea Levels in the Last 15,000 Years: A Review*, edited by Hopley, D., vol. 3 of *Department of Geography Monograph Series, Occasional Paper*, pp. 85–92, James Cook University of North Queensland, Townsville, Queensland, Australia, 1983.
- Flood, P. G. and Frankel, E.: Late Holocene higher sea level indicators from eastern Australia, *Marine Geology*, 90, 193–195, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(89\)90041-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(89)90041-8), 1989.
- Forbes, D. L., Shaw, J., and Eddy, B. G.: Late Quaternary sedimentation and the postglacial sea-level minimum in Port au Port Bay and vicinity, west Newfoundland, *Atlantic Geology*, 29, 1–26, <https://doi.org/10.4138/1986>, Language: English with French abstract, 1993.
- Forman, S. L. and Polyak, L.: Radiocarbon content of pre-bomb marine mollusks and variations in the ¹⁴C Reservoir age for coastal areas of the Barents and Kara Seas, Russia, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 24, 885–888, <https://doi.org/10.1029/97GL00761>, 1997.
- Forman, S. L., Lubinski, D., Miller, G. H., Matishov, G. G., Korsun, S., Snyder, J., Herlihy, F., Weihe, R., and Myslivets, V.: Postglacial emergence of western Franz Josef Land, Russian, and retreat of the Barents Sea Ice Sheet, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 15, 77–90, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-3791\(95\)00090-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-3791(95)00090-9), 1996.
- Forman, S. L., Lubinski, D. J., Zeeberg, J. J., Polyak, L., Miller, G. H., Matishov, G., and Tarasov, G.: Postglacial emergence and late Quaternary glaciation on northern Novaya Zemlya, Arctic Russia, *Boreas*, 28, 133–145, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1999.tb00210.x>, 1999.
- Forman, S. L., Lubinski, D. J., Ingólfsson, Ó., Zeeberg, J. J., Snyder, J. A., Siegert, M. J., and Matishov, G. G.: A review of postglacial emergence on Svalbard, Franz Josef Land and Novaya Zemlya, northern Eurasia, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 23, 1391–1434, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2003.12.007>, 2004.
- Fredh, D.: Holocene relative sea-level changes in the Tasiusaq area, southern Greenland, with focus on the Ta4 basin, Master's thesis, Lund University, URL <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/2334019>, *Dissertations in Geology at Lund University*, Language: English with Swedish abstract, 2008.
- Fredskild, B.: Studies in the vegetational history of Greenland. Palaeobotanical investigations of some Holocene lake and bog deposits, vol. 198, Museum Tusulanum Press, Copenhagen, Denmark, 1973.
- Fredskild, B.: The Holocene vegetational development of the Godthåbsfjord area, West Greenland, vol. 232 of *Geoscience. 10*, Museum Tusulanum Press, Copenhagen, Denmark, 1983.
- Fredskild, B.: The Holocene vegetational development of Tugtulisssuaq and Qeqertat, northwest Greenland, *Meddelelser om Grønland. Geoscience*, 14, 20, 1985.

- Freund, H. and Streif, H.: Natural sea-level indicators documenting the fluctuations of the mean high tide level over the last 2000 years around the Island of Juist (German North-Sea coast), *Petermanns Geographische Mitteilungen*, 143, 34–45, URL <https://www.klett.de/produkt/isbn/A053-08070002>, Language: German with English abstract, Title (in original language): *Natürliche Pegelmarken für Meeresspiegelschwankungen der letzten 2000 Jahre im Bereich der Insel Juist*, 2000.
- Funder, S.: C¹⁴ dates from the Scoresby Sund region, 1971, *Rapport Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 37, 57–59, <https://doi.org/10.34194/rapggu.v37.7277>, 1971.
- Funder, S.: C¹⁴ dates from the Scoresby Sund region, 1972, *Rapport Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 48, 115–117, <https://doi.org/10.34194/rapggu.v48.7316>, 1972.
- Funder, S.: C¹⁴ dates from the Scoresby Sund region, 1973, *Rapport Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 58, 75–76, <https://doi.org/10.34194/rapggu.v58.7368>, 1973.
- Funder, S.: Holocene stratigraphy and vegetation history in the Scoresby Sund area, East Greenland, *Bulletin Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 129, 1–66, <https://doi.org/10.34194/bullggu.v129.6671>, 1978.
- Funder, S.: 14C-dating of samples collected during the 1979 expedition to North Greenland, *Rapport Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 110, 9–14, <https://doi.org/10.34194/rapggu.v110.7787>, 1982.
- Funder, S.: Descriptive text to Quaternary map of Greenland 1: 500,000, Scoresby Sund, sheet 12, *Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, Copenhagen, Denmark, 1990a.
- Funder, S.: Late Quaternary stratigraphy and glaciology in the Thule area, Northwest Greenland, *Meddelelser om Grønland, Geoscience*, 22, 63, 1990b.
- Funder, S. and Abrahamsen, N.: Palynology in a polar desert, eastern North Greenland, *Boreas*, 17, 195–207, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1988.tb00546.x>, 1988.
- Funder, S. and Hansen, L.: The Greenland ice sheet - a model for its culmination and decay during and after the last glacial maximum, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark*, 42, 137–152, <https://doi.org/10.37570/bgsd-1995-42-12>, 1996.
- Funder, S., Goosse, H., Jepsen, H., Kaas, E., Kjær, K. H., Korsgaard, N. J., Larsen, N. K., Linderson, H., Lyså, A., Möller, P., Olsen, J., and Willerslev, E.: A 10,000-Year record of Arctic Ocean sea-ice variability—view from the beach, *Science*, 333, 747–750, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1202760>, 2011.
- Föged, N.: The subfossil diatom flora of four geographically widely separated cores in Greenland, vol. 268 of *Meddelelser om Grønland*, Commission for Scientific Research in Greenland, 1989.
- Gagan, M. K.: Terrigenous sedimentation and the geologic impact of cyclone Winifred, Innisfail Area, Central Great Barrier Reef Province, Ph.D. thesis, James Cook University of North Queensland, Townsville, Queensland, Australia, 1990.
- Gagan, M. K., Johnson, D. P., and Crowley, G. M.: Sea level control of stacked late Quaternary coastal sequences, central Great Barrier Reef, *Sedimentology*, 41, 329–351, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3091.1994.tb01409.x>, 1994.
- Gajewski, K. and Garralla, S.: Holocene vegetation histories from three sites in the tundra of northwestern Quebec, Canada, *Arctic and Alpine Research*, 24, 329–336, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00040851.1992.12002965>, 1992.

- Gawronski, J. H. and Zeeberg, J. J.: The wrecking of Barents' ship, in: *Northbound with Barents*, edited by Boyarsky, P. V. and Gawronski, J. H. G., pp. 89–92, Jan Mets, Amsterdam, 1997.
- Gayes, P. T., Scott, D. B., Collins, E. S., and Nelson, D. D.: A late Holocene sea-level fluctuation in South Carolina, *Special Publications of SEPM*, 48, 155–160, <https://doi.org/10.2110/pec.92.48.0155>, 1992.
- Gehrels, W. R.: Middle and late Holocene sea-level changes in eastern Maine reconstructed from foraminiferal saltmarsh stratigraphy and AMS 14C dates on basal peat, *Quaternary Research*, 52, 350–359, <https://doi.org/10.1006/qres.1999.2076>, 1999.
- Gehrels, W. R. and Belknap, D. F.: Neotectonic history of eastern Maine evaluated from historic sea-level data and 14C dates on salt-marsh peats, *Geology*, 21, 615–618, [https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613\(1993\)021<0615:NHOEME>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613(1993)021<0615:NHOEME>2.3.CO;2), 1993.
- Gehrels, W. R., Belknap, D. F., and Kelley, J. T.: Integrated high-precision analyses of Holocene relative sea-level changes: lessons from the coast of Maine, *Geological Society of America Bulletin*, 108, 1073–1088, [https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606\(1996\)108<1073:IHPAOH>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606(1996)108<1073:IHPAOH>2.3.CO;2), 1996.
- Gehrels, W. R., Belknap, D. F., Black, S., and Newnham, R. M.: Rapid sea-level rise in the Gulf of Maine, USA, since AD 1800, *The Holocene*, 12, 383–389, <https://doi.org/10.1191/0959683602hl555ft>, 2002.
- Gehrels, W. R., Milne, G. A., Kirby, J. R., Patterson, R. T., and Belknap, D. F.: Late Holocene sea-level changes and isostatic crustal movements in Atlantic Canada, *Quaternary International*, 120, 79–89, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2004.01.008>, 2004.
- Gehrels, W. R., Kirby, J. R., Prokoph, A., Newnham, R. M., Achterberg, E. P., Evans, H., Black, S., and Scott, D. B.: Onset of recent rapid sea-level rise in the western Atlantic Ocean, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 24, 2083–2100, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2004.11.016>, 2005.
- Gehrels, W. R., Sz Kornik, K., Bartholdy, J., Kirby, J. R., Bradley, S. L., Marshall, W. A., Heinemeier, J., and Pedersen, J. B. T.: Late Holocene sea-level changes and isostasy in western Denmark, *Quaternary Research*, 66, 288–302, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yqres.2006.05.004>, 2006.
- Gehrels, W. R., Callard, S. L., Moss, P. T., Marshall, W. A., Blaauw, M., Hunter, J., Milton, J. A., and Garnett, M. H.: Nineteenth and twentieth century sea-level changes in Tasmania and New Zealand, *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 315–316, 94–102, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2011.08.046>, *sea Level and Ice Sheet Evolution: A PALSEA Special Edition*, 2012.
- Gelumbauskaitė, L. Ž.: Character of sea level changes in the subsiding south-eastern Baltic Sea during Late Quaternary, *Baltica*, 22, 23–36, URL <https://baltica.gamtclt/en/publication/72/p-classsonormalcharacter-of-sea-level-changes-in-the-subsidingsouth-eastern-baltic-sea-during-late-quaternaryopopp>, 2009.
- Geyh, M. A., Streif, H., and Kudrass, H.-R.: Sea-level changes during the late Pleistocene and Holocene in the Strait of Malacca, *Nature*, 278, 441–443, <https://doi.org/10.1038/278441a0>, 1979.
- Gill, E. D. and Hopley, D.: Holocene sea levels in eastern Australia – A discussion, *Marine Geology*, 12, 223–233, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(72\)90041-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(72)90041-2), 1972.
- Gillespie, R. and Temple, R. B.: Sydney University natural radiocarbon measurements III, *Radiocarbon*, 18, 96–109, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200002393>, 1976.

- Girininkas, A. and Žulkus, V.: The shores and people of the Baltic Sea in the early Holocene, in: *Jūros ir krantų tyrimai 2017, Konferencijos medžiaga*, pp. 69–72, URL <http://apc.ku.lt/krantai2017/index.php/svarbiausios-datos/>, Language: Lithuanian, Title (in original language): Baltijos jūros krantai ir žmonės ankstyvajame holocene, 2017.
- Glaser, P. H., Hansen, B. C., Siegel, D. I., Reeve, A. S., and Morin, P. J.: Rates, pathways and drivers for peatland development in the Hudson Bay Lowlands, northern Ontario, Canada, *Journal of Ecology*, 92, 1036–1053, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0022-0477.2004.00931.x>, 2004.
- Glazovskiy, A., Näslund, J.-O., and Zale, R.: Deglaciation and shoreline displacement on Alexandra Land, Franz Josef Land, *Geografiska Annaler: Series A, Physical Geography*, 74, 283–293, <https://doi.org/10.1080/04353676.1992.11880371>, 1992.
- Glueder, A., Mix, A. C., Milne, G. A., Reilly, B. T., Clark, J., Jakobsson, M., Mayer, L., Fallon, S. J., Southon, J., Padman, J., Ross, A., Cronin, T., and McKay, J. L.: Calibrated relative sea levels constrain isostatic adjustment and ice history in northwest Greenland, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 293, 107–170, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2022.107700>, 2022.
- Glückert, G.: Post-Glacial Shore-Level Displacement of the Baltic in SW Finland, *Annales Academiae Scientiarum Fennicae Series A. III, Geologica-geographica*, 118, 1–92, 1976.
- Glückert, G.: The Kiikalannummi Delta Complex on the 3rd Salpausselkä in Southwest Finland, Publication of the Department of Quaternary Geology 35, University of Turku, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Das Deltakomplex von Kiikalannummi am 3. Salpausselkä in Südwestfinland, 1978a.
- Glückert, G.: The post-glacial shoreline shift of the Baltic Sea and the history of forests in Åland, vol. 34 of *Turun yliopiston maaperägeologian osaston julkaisuja*, Turun yliopisto, title translated with DeepL, Language: Swedish, Title (in original language): Östersjöns postglaciala strandförskjutning och skogens historia på Åland, 1978b.
- Glückert, G., Illmer, K., Kankainen, T., Rantala, P., and Räsänen, M.: Evolution of the surrounding vegetation of Lake Littoistenjärvi after the Ice Age and natural acidification of the lake, *Turun yliopiston maaperägeologian osaston julkaisuja*, 75, 1–27, title translated with deepL, Language: Finnish, Title (in original language): Littoistenjärven ympäristön kasvillisuuden kehitys jääkauden jälkeen ja järven luonnollinen happamoituminen, 1992.
- Glückert, G., Rantala, P., and Ristaniemi, O.: Postglacial shore-level displacement of the Baltic in Ostrobothnia, *Turun yliopiston maaperägeologian osaston julkaisuja*, 77, 5–36, Language: Finnish, Title (in original language): Itämeren jääkauden jälkeinen rannansiirtyminen Pohjanmaalla, 1993.
- Goodwin, I. D.: Holocene deglaciation, sea-level change, and the emergence of the Windmill Islands, Budd Coast, Antarctica, *Quaternary Research*, 40, 55–69, <https://doi.org/10.1006/qres.1993.1057>, 1993.
- Goodwin, I. D. and Zweck, C.: Glacio-isostasy and Glacial Ice Load at Law Dome, Wilkes Land, East Antarctica, *Quaternary Research*, 53, 285–293, <https://doi.org/10.1006/qres.1999.2125>, 2000.
- Govare, É. and Gangloff, P.: Lateglacial Beach Paleoenvironment Dated 10 580 yr BP in the Charlevoix Region, Québec, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 43, 147–160, <https://doi.org/10.7202/032766ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): Paléoenvironnement d' une plage tardiglaciaire de 10 580 ans BP dans la région de Charlevoix, Québec, 1989.

- Gowan, E. J., Tregoning, P., Purcell, A., Montillet, J.-P., and McClusky, S.: A model of the western Laurentide Ice Sheet, using observations of glacial isostatic adjustment, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 139, 1–16, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2016.03.003>, 2016.
- Gowan, E. J., Zhang, X., Khosravi, S., Rovere, A., Stocchi, P., Hughes, A. L. C., Gyllencreutz, R., Mangerud, J., Svendsen, J., and Lohmann, G.: A new global ice sheet reconstruction for the past 80 000 years, *Nature Communications*, 12, 1199, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-21469-w>, 2021.
- Gowan, E. J., Zhang, X., Khosravi, S., Rovere, A., Stocchi, P., Hughes, A. L. C., Gyllencreutz, R., Mangerud, J., Svendsen, J.-I., and Lohmann, G.: Reply to: Towards solving the missing ice problem and the importance of rigorous model data comparisons, *Nature Communications*, 13, 6264, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-33954-x>, 2022.
- Grant, D. R.: Quaternary geology of St. Anthony - Blanc-Sablon area, Newfoundland and Quebec, Memoir 427, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/183880>, Language: English with French abstract, 1992.
- Grant, D. R.: Quaternary geology of Port Saunders map area, Newfoundland, Paper 91-20, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/194038>, Language: English with French abstract, 1994.
- Grant, K. M., Rohling, E. J., Bar-Matthews, M., Ayalon, A., Medina-Elizalde, M., Bronk Ramsey, C., Satow, C., and Roberts, A. P.: Rapid coupling between ice volume and polar temperature over the past 150,000 years, *Nature*, 491, 744–747, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11593>, 2012.
- Grant, K. M., Rohling, E. J., Bronk Ramsey, C., Cheng, H., Edwards, R. L., Florindo, F., Heslop, D., Marra, F., Roberts, A. P., Tamisiea, M. E., and Williams, F.: Sea-level variability over five glacial cycles, *Nature Communications*, 5, 1–9, <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms6076>, 2014.
- Grant-Taylor, T. L. and Rafter, T. A.: New Zealand Natural Radiocarbon Measurements I-V, *Radiocarbon*, 5, 118–162, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200036845>, 1963.
- Gray, J., de Boutray, B., Hillaire-Marcel, C., and Lauriol, B.: Postglacial emergence of the west coast of Ungava Bay, Quebec, Arctic and Alpine Research, 12, 19–30, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00040851.1980.12004160>, 1980.
- Gray, J., Lauriol, B., Bruneau, D., and Ricard, J.: Postglacial emergence of Ungava Peninsula, and its relationship to glacial history, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 30, 1676–1696, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e93-147>, 1993.
- Gray, J. T.: Patterns of ice flow and deglaciation chronology for southern coastal margins of Hudson Strait and Ungava Bay, in: Marine geology of Hudson Strait and Ungava Bay, Eastern Arctic Canada: Late Quaternary sediments, depositional environments, and late glacial–deglacial history derived from marine and terrestrial studies, edited by MacLean, B., vol. 566 of *Bulletin*, pp. 201–213, Geological Survey of Canada, Ottawa, Ontario, <https://doi.org/10.4095/212207>, Language: English with French abstract, 2001.
- Gray, J. T. and Lauriol, B.: Dynamics of the late Wisconsin ice sheet in the Ungava Peninsula interpreted from geomorphological evidence, *Arctic and Alpine Research*, 17, 289–310, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00040851.1985.12004037>, 1985.
- Griede, J. W.: The origin of Friesland’s north corner: a physical-geographical study of the Holocene development of a sea clay area, Ph.D. thesis, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, title translated with DeepL, Language: Dutch with abstracts in English, German and Frisian, Title (in original language): Het

ontstaan van Frieslands noordhoek: een fysisch-geografisch onderzoek naar de holocene ontwikkeling van een zeekleigebied, 1978.

- Grigorieva, A. K.: Palynological Characteristics of the Late Pleistocene Sediments of West-siberian Polar Regions, Ph.D. thesis, Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow, Soviet Union, summary of the Thesis for a Degree of Doctor of Philosophy (Geographical Science), Speciality 25.00.25 - Geomorphology and Evolutional Geography (In Russian), 1987.
- Grindrod, J. and Rhodes, E. G.: Holocene sea level history of a tropical estuary: Missionary Bay, North Queensland, in: Coastal Geomorphology in Australia, pp. 151–178, Academic Press, 1984.
- Grosswald, M. E.: Raised beaches in Franz Josef Land and the Late-Quaternary history of its ice sheets, *Glaciological studies*, 9, 283–293, (in Russian), Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Гросвальд, М. Г., Title (in original language): Древние береговые линии Земли Франца-Иосифа и поздне-антропогенная история ее ледниковых покровов, *Journal/book (in original language): Гляциологические исследования*, 1963.
- Grosswald, M. G., Krenke, A. H., Vinogradov, O. N., Markin, V. A., Psareva, T. V., Razumeiko, N. G., and Sukhodrovsky, V. L.: Glaciation of Franz Josef Land, Nauka, Moscow, Soviet Union, title translated with DeepL, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Гросвальд, М Г, Кренке, А Н, Виноградов, О Н, Маркин, В А, Псарева, Т В, Разумейко, Н Г, and Суходровский, В Л, Title (in original language): Оледенение Земли Франца-Иосифа, *Journal/book (in original language): Наука*, 1973.
- Grudzinska, I.: Paleoenvironmental changes in lake sediments of different genesis, Master's thesis, University of Latvia, Faculty of Geography and Earth Sciences, Department of Environmental Sciences, Riga, Latvia, title translated with DeepL, Language: Latvian, Title (in original language): Paleovides izmaiņu atspoguļojums dažādas ģenēzes ezeru nogulumos, 2011.
- Grudzinska, I.: Diatom stratigraphy and relative sea level changes of the eastern Baltic Sea over the Holocene, Ph.D. thesis, Tallinn University of Technology, URL <https://digikogu.taltech.ee/et/Item/fcf2d9e2-8f9d-49a7-aa53-990e22afe2dd>, 2015.
- Grudzinska, I., Saarse, L., Vassiljev, J., and Heinsalu, A.: Mid- and late- Holocene shoreline changes along the southern coast of the Gulf of Finland, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Finland*, 85, 19–34, <https://doi.org/10.17741/bgsf/85.1.002>, 2013.
- Grudzinska, I., Saarse, L., Vassiljev, J., and Heinsalu, A.: Biostratigraphy, shoreline changes and origin of the Limnea Sea lagoons in northern Estonia: the case study of Lake Harku, *Baltica*, 27, 15–24, <https://doi.org/10.5200/baltica.2014.27.02>, 2014.
- Grudzinska, I., Vassiljev, J., Saarse, L., Reitalu, T., and Veski, S.: Past environmental change and seawater intrusion into coastal Lake Lilaste, Latvia, *Journal of Paleolimnology*, 57, 257–271, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10933-017-9945-3>, 2017.
- Gurevich, V. I. and Liyva, A. A.: The age of Lake Mogilnoye, *Relic lake Mogilnoye*, -, 102–104, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Гуревич, В И and Лийва, А А, Title (in original language): Возраст оз. Могильного, *Journal/book (in original language): Реликтовое озеро Могильное*, 1975.
- Gurina, N. N.: New studies in the northwestern part of Kola Peninsula, *Brief Communications of the Institute of Archaeology*, 126, 94–99, URL http://www.archaeolog.ru/media/books_

- ksia/ksia_126.pdf, title translated with DeepL, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Гурина, Н. Н., Title (in original language): Новые исследования в северо-западной части Кольского полуострова, Journal/book (in original language): Краткие сообщения Института археологии, 1971.
- Gusev, E. A., Anikina, N. J., Arslanov, K. A., Bondarenko, S. A., Derevjanko, L. G., Molod'kov, A. N., Pushina, Z. V., Rekant, P. V., and Stepanova, G. V.: Quaternary sediments and palaeogeography of Sibiriyakov Island in the last 50 000 years, Proceedings of the Russian Geographical Society, 145, 65–79, (in Russian), Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Гусев, Е. А., Аникина, Н. Ю., Арсланов, Х. А., Бондаренко, С. А., Деревянко, Л. Г., Молодьков, А. Н., Пушина, З. В., Рекант, П. В., and Степанова, Г. В., Title (in original language): Четвертичные отложения и палеогеография острова Сибирякова за последние 50 000 лет, Journal/book (in original language): Известия русского географического общества, 2013а.
- Gusev, E. A., Bolshiyarov, D. Y., Dymov, V. A., Sharin, V. V., and Arslanov, K. A.: Holocene marine terraces of the southern Franz-Josef Land Islands, Проблемы Арктики и Антарктики, 97, 103, URL <http://www.evgenyusev.narod.ru/zfi/gusev-2013.html>, Language: Russian with English abstract, Authors (in original language): Гусев, Е.А., Большианов, Д. Ю., Дымов, В. А., Шарин, В. В., and А., Арсланов Х., Title (in original language): Голоценовые морские террасы южных островов Земли Франца-Иосифа, Journal/book (in original language): Проблемы Арктики и Антарктики, 2013b.
- Gutierrez, B. T., Uchupi, E., Driscoll, N. W., and Aubrey, D. G.: Relative sea-level rise and the development of valley-fill and shallow-water sequences in Nantucket Sound, Massachusetts, Marine Geology, 193, 295–314, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227\(02\)00665-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227(02)00665-5), 2003.
- H., K.: Geological evolution of the Baltic Sea in the Late Palaeolithic and Holocene on Estonian territory, Tech. rep., ENSV TA Geologia Instituut, unpublished report in State Archives, Title translated with DeepL, Language: Estonian, Title (in original language): Läänemere geoloogiline areng hilisglatsiaalis ja holotseenis Eesti territooriumil, 1975.
- Haarnagel, W.: The Late Bronze Age, Early Iron Age farmstead settlement of Jemgum b. Leer on the left bank of the Ems, Die Kunde Neue Folge, 8, 2–44, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Die spätbronze-, früheisenzeitliche Gehöftsiedlung Jemgum b. Leer auf dem linken Ufer der Ems, 1957.
- Haarnagel, W.: The results of the excavation at the Early Iron Age settlement of Boomborg/Hatzum, Leer district, in the years from 1965 to 1967, Neue Ausgrabungen und Forschungen in Niedersachsen, 4, 58–97, title translated by DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Die Ergebnisse der Grabung auf der ältereisenzeitlichen Siedlung Boomborg/Hatzum, Kreis Leer, in den Jahren von 1965 bis 1967, 1969.
- Haarnagel, W.: The Feddersen Wierde excavation. Method, house construction, settlement and economic form as well as social structure, in: Feddersen Wierde, vol. 2, pp. 1–364, Steiner, title translated by DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Die Grabung Feddersen Wierde. Methode, Hausbau, Siedlungs- und Wirtschaftsform sowie Sozialstruktur, 1979.
- Haarnagel, W.: Settlement in the north-west German coastal area in its dependence on sea-level fluctuations and storm surges, in: Transgression en occupatiegeschiedenis in de kustgebieden van Nederland en België, edited by Verhulst, A. and Gottschalk, M. K. E., pp. 209–239, Belgisch Centrum voor Landelijke Geschiedenis, Language: German, Title (in original language): Die Besiedlung im nord-westdeutschen Küstengebiet in ihrer Abhängigkeit von Meeresspiegelschwankungen und Sturmfluten, 1980.

- Habicht, H.-L., Rosentau, A., Jöeleht, A., Heinsalu, A., Kriiska, A., Kohv, M., Hang, T., and Aunap, R.: GIS-based multiproxy coastline reconstruction of the eastern Gulf of Riga, Baltic Sea, during the Stone Age, *Boreas*, 46, 83–99, <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12157>, 2017.
- Haila, H. and Raukas, A.: Ancylus Lake, in: *Geology of the Gulf of Finland*, edited by Raukas, A. and Hyvärinen, H., pp. 283–296, Estonian Academy of Sciences, Tallinn, URL <https://www.etera.ee/s/kEO9W5w8ph>, Language: Russian, Title (in original language): Анциловое озеро, Journal/book (in original language): Геология Финского залива, 1992.
- Haila, H., Sarmaja-Korjonen, K., and Uutela, A.: Development of a Litorina Bay at Espoo, near Porvoo, southern Finland, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Finland*, 63, 105–119, <https://doi.org/10.17741/bgsf/63.2.004>, 1991.
- Hall, B. L., Baroni, C., and Denton, G. H.: Holocene relative sea-level history of the Southern Victoria Land Coast, Antarctica, *Global and Planetary Change*, 42, 241–263, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2003.09.004>, ice sheets and neotectonics, 2004.
- Hall, B. L., Baroni, C., and Denton, G. H.: The most extensive Holocene advance in the Stauning Alper, East Greenland, occurred in the Little Ice Age, *Polar Research*, 27, 128–134, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-8369.2008.00058.x>, 2008.
- Hall, B. L., Baroni, C., and Denton, G. H.: Relative sea-level changes, Schuchert Dal, East Greenland, with implications for ice extent in late-glacial and Holocene times, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 29, 3370–3378, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2010.03.013>, aPEX: Arctic Palaeoclimate and its Extremes, 2010.
- Hanebuth, T., Stattegger, K., and Grootes, P. M.: Rapid flooding of the Sunda Shelf: A late-glacial sea-level record, *Science*, 288, 1033–1035, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.288.5468.1033>, 2000.
- Hanebuth, T. J. J., Stattegger, K., Schimanski, A., Lüdmann, T., and Wong, H. K.: Late Pleistocene forced-regressive deposits on the Sunda Shelf (Southeast Asia), *Marine Geology*, 199, 139–157, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227\(03\)00129-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227(03)00129-4), 2003.
- Hanebuth, T. J. J., Stattegger, K., and Bojanowski, A.: Termination of the Last Glacial Maximum sea-level lowstand: The Sunda-Shelf data revisited, *Global and Planetary Change*, 66, 76–84, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2008.03.011>, quaternary sea-level changes : Records and Processes, 2009.
- Hanebuth, T. J. J., Proske, U., Saito, Y., Nguyen, V. L., and Ta, T. K. O.: Early growth stage of a large delta – Transformation from estuarine-platform to deltaic-progradational conditions (the northeastern Mekong River Delta, Vietnam), *Sedimentary Geology*, 261-262, 108–119, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sedgeo.2012.03.014>, 2012.
- Hanisch, J.: New sea level data from the region of Wangerooge, *E&G Quaternary Science Journal*, 30, 221–228, <https://doi.org/10.3285/eg.30.1.18>, Language: German with English abstract, Title (in original language): Neue Meeresspiegeldaten aus dem Raum Wangerooge, 1980.
- Hansen, J. M.: Sedimentary history of the island Læsø, Denmark, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark*, 26, 217–236, <https://doi.org/10.37570/bgsd-1977-26-17>, Language: English with Danish summary, 1977.
- Hansson, A.: Submerged Landscapes in the Hanö Bay : Early Holocene shoreline displacement and human environments in the southern Baltic Basin, Ph.D. thesis, Lund University, URL https://lup.lub.lu.se/search/files/43355942/Lundqua_thesis_85_Hansson_kappa.pdf, Language: eng, 2018.

- Hansson, A., Björck, S., Heger, K., Holmgren, S., Linderson, H., Magnell, O., Nilsson, B., Rundgren, M., Sjöström, A., and Hammarlund, D.: Shoreline displacement and human resource utilization in the southern Baltic Basin coastal zone during the early Holocene: New insights from a submerged Mesolithic landscape in south-eastern Sweden, *The Holocene*, 28, 721–737, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683617744262>, 2018a.
- Hansson, A., Nilsson, B., Sjöström, A., Björck, S., Holmgren, S., Linderson, H., Magnell, O., Rundgren, M., and Hammarlund, D.: A submerged Mesolithic lagoonal landscape in the Baltic Sea, south-eastern Sweden – Early Holocene environmental reconstruction and shore-level displacement based on a multiproxy approach, *Quaternary International*, 463, 110–123, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2016.07.059>, advances in Geoarchaeology Research - Landscape Evolution, Environmental Change & Human Activities, 2018b.
- Hansson, A., Hammarlund, D., Landeschi, G., Sjöström, A., and Nilsson, B.: A new early Holocene shoreline displacement record for Blekinge, southern Sweden, and implications for underwater archaeology, *Boreas*, 48, 57–71, <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12339>, 2019.
- Harders, R., Dehde, B., Diesing, M., Gelhardt, M., and Schwarzer, K.: Postglacial development of Neustadt Bay in the western Baltic Sea, *Meyniana*, 57, 37–60, 2005.
- Hardy, L.: Contribution to the geomorphological study of the Quebec portion of the James Bay Lowlands, Ph.D. thesis, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada, URL <https://escholarship.mcgill.ca/concern/theses/4x51hk00r>, title translated with DeepL, Language: French with English abstract, Title (in original language): Contribution à l'étude géomorphologique de la portion québécoise des basses terres de la Baie de James, 1976.
- Harrington, C.: Quaternary Vertebrates of Québec: a Summary, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 57, 85–94, <https://doi.org/10.7202/010332ar>, Language: English with French abstract, 2003.
- Harris, P. T., Davies, P. J., and Marshall, J. F.: Late Quaternary sedimentation on the Great Barrier Reef continental shelf and slope east of Townsville, Australia, *Marine Geology*, 94, 55–77, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(90\)90103-Q](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(90)90103-Q), 1990.
- Harvey, N., Barnett, E. J., Bourman, R. P., and Belperio, A. P.: Holocene sea-level change at Port Pirie, South Australia: A contribution to global sea-level rise estimates from tide gauges, *Journal of Coastal Research*, 15, 607–615, URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4298977>, 1999.
- Hassan, K. b.: Holocene sea level changes in Kelang and Kuantan, Peninsular Malaysia, Ph.D. thesis, Durham University, Durham, United Kingdom, URL <http://etheses.dur.ac.uk/3786/>, 2001.
- Haworth, R. J., Baker, R. G. V., and Flood, P. G.: Predicted and observed Holocene sea-levels on the Australian coast: what do they indicate about hydro-isostatic models in far-field sites?, *Journal of Quaternary Science*, 17, 581–591, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.718>, 2002.
- Hayashi, M. and Yoshida, Y.: Holocene raised beaches in the Lützw-Holm Bay region, *Memoirs of National Institute of Polar Research. Special issue*, 50, 49–84, URL <http://id.nii.ac.jp/1291/00002261/>, 1994.
- Heap, A. D., Dickens, G. R., Stewart, L. K., and Woolfe, K. J.: Holocene storage of siliciclastic sediment around islands on the middle shelf of the Great Barrier Reef Platform, north-east Australia, *Sedimentology*, 49, 603–621, <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-3091.2002.00464.x>, 2002.

- Hearty, P., O'Leary, M., Donald, A., and Lachlan, T.: The enigma of 3400 years BP coastal oolites in tropical northwest Western Australia...why then, why there?, *Sedimentary Geology*, 186, 171–185, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sedgeo.2005.11.014>, 2006.
- Heaton, T. J., Köhler, P., Butzin, M., Bard, E., Reimer, R. W., Austin, W. E. N., Bronk Ramsey, C., Grootes, P. M., Hughen, K. A., Kromer, B., Reimer, P. J., Adkins, J., Burke, A., Cook, M. S., Olsen, J., and Skinner, L. C.: Marine20—The Marine Radiocarbon Age Calibration Curve (0–55,000 cal BP), *Radiocarbon*, 62, 779–820, <https://doi.org/10.1017/RDC.2020.68>, 2020.
- Hede, M. U., Sander, L., Clemmensen, L. B., Kroon, A., Pejrup, M., and Nielsen, L.: Changes in Holocene relative sea-level and coastal morphology: A study of a raised beach ridge system on Samsø, southwest Scandinavia, *The Holocene*, 25, 1402–1414, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683615585834>, 2015.
- Hede, S. U.: Prehistoric settlements and Holocene relative sea-level changes in northwest Sjælland, Denmark, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark*, 50, 141–149, <https://doi.org/10.37570/bgsd-2003-50-11>, 2003.
- Hedenström, A. and Risberg, J.: Shore displacement in northern Uppland during the last 6500 calendar years, SKB Technical Report 03-17, Svensk Kärnbränslehantering AB, URL <https://www.skb.com/publication/20970>, 2003.
- Heinrich, C., Anders, S., and Schwarzer, K.: Late Pleistocene and early Holocene drainage events in the eastern Fehmarn Belt and Mecklenburg Bight, SW Baltic Sea, *Boreas*, 47, 754–767, <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12298>, 2018.
- Heinsalu, A.: Diatom stratigraphy and palaeoenvironment of the Yoldia Sea in northern Estonia, *Proceedings of the Estonian Academy of Sciences, Geology*, 49, 218–243, <https://doi.org/10.3176/geol.2000.3.04>, Language: English with Estonian and Russian abstracts, 2000.
- Hekel, H., Ward, W. T., and Jones, M.: Geological development of northern Moreton Bay, in: Northern Moreton Bay Symposium, edited by Bailey, A. and Stevens, N. C., pp. 7–18, Royal Society of Queensland, St. Lucia, Queensland, Australia, the Proceedings of a Symposium held at the Abel Smith Lecture Theatre, University of Queensland, September 23-24, 1978, 1979.
- Hesp, P. A., Hung, C. C., Hilton, M., Ming, C. L., and Turner, I. M.: A first tentative Holocene sea-level curve for Singapore, *Journal of Coastal Research*, 14, 308–314, URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4298779>, 1998.
- Héту, B.: Deglaciation of the Rimouski area, Lower St. Lawrence (Québec): stratigraphical evidences of a glacial readvance into the Goldthwait Sea between 12,400 and 12,000 yr BP, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 52, 325–347, <https://doi.org/10.7202/004832ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): La déglaciation de la région de Rimouski, Bas-Saint-Laurent (Québec) : indices d' une récurrence glaciaire dans la Mer de Goldthwait entre 12 400 et 12 000 BP, 1998.
- Héту, B. and Bail, P.: Postglacial Hydrogeomorphological Changes and Rates of Surface Lowering in a Small Appalachian Catchment near Rimouski (Bas-Saint-Laurent, Québec), *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 50, 351–363, <https://doi.org/10.7202/033105ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): Évolution postglaciaire du régime hydrosédimentaire et vitesse de l' ablation dans un petit bassin-versant des Appalaches près de Rimouski (Bas-Saint-Laurent, Québec), 1996.

- Hibbert, F. D., Rohling, E. J., Dutton, A., Williams, F. H., Chutcharavan, P. M., Zhao, C., and Tamisiea, M. E.: Coral indicators of past sea-level change: A global repository of U-series dated benchmarks, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 145, 1–56, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2016.04.019>, 2016.
- Higelke, B., Kühn, H.-J., and Müller-Wille, M.: Settlement areas: Schleswig-Holstein, in: *Archäologische und naturwissenschaftliche Untersuchungen an ländlichen und städtischen Siedlungen im deutschen Küstengebiet vom 5. Jh. v. Chr. bis zum 11. Jh. n. Chr. 1, Ländliche Siedlungen*, edited by Kossack, G., Behre, K.-E., and Schmid, P., Verlag Chemie, Weinheim, Language: German, Title (in original language): Siedelräume: Schleswig-Holstein, 1984.
- Higley, M.: Fossil oyster beds of the Mid-Holocene highstand of relative sea level: GBR Shelf, Unpublished honours thesis, School of Earth Sciences, James Cook University, Townsville, Australia., 2000.
- Hijma, M. P. and Cohen, K. M.: Timing and magnitude of the sea-level jump preluding the 8200 yr event, *Geology*, 38, 275–278, <https://doi.org/10.1130/G30439.1>, 2010.
- Hijma, M. P. and Cohen, K. M.: Holocene sea-level database for the Rhine-Meuse Delta, The Netherlands: implications for the pre-8.2 ka sea-level jump, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 214, 68–86, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2019.05.001>, 2019.
- Hijma, M. P., Cohen, K. M., Hoffmann, G., Van der Spek, A. J. F., and Stouthamer, E.: From river valley to estuary: the evolution of the Rhine mouth in the early to middle Holocene (western Netherlands, Rhine-Meuse delta), *Netherlands Journal of Geosciences*, 88, 13–53, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0016774600000986>, 2009.
- Hillaire-Marcel, C.: Deglaciation and isostatic uplift on the eastern coast of Hudson Bay, *Cahiers de géographie du Québec*, 20, 185–220, <https://doi.org/10.7202/021319ar>, Language: French with English abstract, Title (in original language): La déglaciation et le relèvement isostatique sur la côte est de la baie d' Hudson, 1976.
- Hinnerson-Berglund, M.: Mobility and aesthetics: The Nuuk Fjord on the west coast of Greenland as a human life-world 4000 years ago, phdthesis, Göteborgs universitet/University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden, URL <http://hdl.handle.net/2077/16433>, Language: Swedish with English and Greenlandic summaries, Title (in original language): Mobilitet och estetik. Nuukfjorden på Grönlands västkust som människornas livsvärld för 4000 år sedan, 2004.
- Hirakawa, K. and Sawagaki, T.: Radiocarbon dates of fossil shells from raised beach sediments along the Sôya Coast, East Antarctica –A report on a geomorphological survey during JARE-35 (1993-94)–, *Antarctic Record*, 42, 151–167, <https://doi.org/10.15094/00009042>, Language: Japanese (With English abstract and captions), Authors (in original language): 平川, 一臣 and 澤柿, 教伸, Title (in original language): 宗谷海岸の隆起海成堆積物から得られた貝化石の 14C 年代 –JARE-35 (1993-94) の資料—, Journal/book (in original language): 南極資料, 1998.
- Hjort, C.: The Vega Transgression – a hypsithermal event in Central East Greenland, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark*, 22, 25–38, Language: English with Danish abstract, 1973.
- Hjort, C.: Glaciation in northern East Greenland during the Late Weichselian and Early Flandrian, *Boreas*, 8, 281–296, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1979.tb00812.x>, 1979.
- Hjort, C.: A glacial chronology for northern East Greenland, *Boreas*, 10, 259–274, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1981.tb00487.x>, 1981.

- Hjort, C.: Glaciation, climate history, changing marine levels and the evolution of the Northeast Water polynya, *Journal of Marine Systems*, 10, 23–33, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-7963\(96\)00068-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-7963(96)00068-1), 1997.
- Hjort, C. and Funder, S.: The subfossil occurrence of *Mytilus edulis* L. in central East Greenland, *Boreas*, 3, 23–33, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1974.tb00664.x>, 1974.
- Hjort, C., Ingólfsson, Ó., Möller, P., and Lirio, J. M.: Holocene glacial history and sea-level changes on James Ross Island, Antarctic Peninsula, *Journal of Quaternary Science*, 12, 259–273, [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1417\(199707/08\)12:4<259::AID-JQS307>3.0.CO;2-6](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1417(199707/08)12:4<259::AID-JQS307>3.0.CO;2-6), 1997.
- Hodgetts, L. M.: The changing Pre-Dorset landscape of SW Hudson Bay, Canada, *Journal of Field Archaeology*, 32, 353–367, <https://doi.org/10.1179/009346907791071467>, 2007.
- Hodgson, D. A., Verleyen, E., Vyverman, W., Sabbe, K., Leng, M. J., Pickering, M. D., and Keely, B. J.: A geological constraint on relative sea level in Marine Isotope Stage 3 in the Larsemann Hills, Lambert Glacier region, East Antarctica (31 366–33 228 cal yr BP), *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 28, 2689–2696, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2009.06.006>, 2009.
- Hodgson, D. A., Whitehouse, P. L., De Cort, G., Berg, S., Verleyen, E., Tavernier, I., Roberts, S. J., Vyverman, W., Sabbe, K., and O'Brien, P.: Rapid early Holocene sea-level rise in Prydz Bay, East Antarctica, *Global and Planetary Change*, 139, 128–140, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2015.12.020>, 2016.
- Hoffmann, G., Schmedemann, N., and Schafmeister, M.-T.: Relative sea-level curve for SE Rugen and Usedom Island (SW Baltic Sea coast, Germany) using decompacted profiles, *Zeitschrift der Deutschen Gesellschaft für Geowissenschaften*, 160, 69–78, <https://doi.org/10.1127/1860-1804/2009/0160-0069>, Language: English with German abstract, 2009.
- Hofmann, G. W.: Quaternary sediments and geological history of the Pine Rivers area, South-east Queensland, *Queensland Government Mining Journal*, 81, 502–512, URL <https://geoscience.data.qld.gov.au/data/report/cr048830>, 1980.
- Hogg, A. G., Heaton, T. J., Hua, Q., Palmer, J. G., Turney, C. S. M., Southon, J., Bayliss, A., Blackwell, P. G., Boswijk, G., Bronk Ramsey, C., Pearson, C., Petchey, F., Reimer, P., Reimer, R., and Wacker, L.: SHCal20 Southern Hemisphere calibration, 0–55,000 years cal BP, *Radiocarbon*, 62, 759–778, <https://doi.org/10.1017/RDC.2020.59>, 2020.
- Hopley, D.: Mid-Holocene high sea levels along the coastal plain of the Great Barrier Reef Province: A discussion, *Marine Geology*, 35, M1–M9, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(80\)90117-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(80)90117-6), 1980.
- Hopley, D.: Evidence of 15000 years of sea-level change in tropical Queensland, in: Australian sea levels in the last 15,000 years: a review, edited by Hopley, D., vol. 3 of *Monograph Series*, pp. 93–104, Department of Geography, James Cook University of North Queensland, 1983.
- Hopley, D., Mclean, R. F., Marshall, J., and Smith, A. S.: Holocene-Pleistocene boundary in a fringing reef: Hayman Island, North Queensland, *Search*, 9, 323–325, 1978.
- Hopley, D., Slocombe, A. M., Muir, F., and Grant, C.: Nearshore fringing reefs in north Queensland, *Coral Reefs*, 1, 151–160, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00571192>, 1983.
- Horton, B. P., Gibbard, P. L., Mine, G. M., Morley, R. J., Purintavaragul, C., and Stargardt, J. M.: Holocene sea levels and palaeoenvironments, Malay-Thai Peninsula, southeast Asia, *The Holocene*, 15, 1199–1213, <https://doi.org/10.1191/0959683605hl891rp>, 2005.

- Horton, B. P., Peltier, W. R., Culver, S. J., Drummond, R., Engelhart, S. E., Kemp, A. C., Mallinson, D., Thieler, E. R., Riggs, S. R., Ames, D. V., and Thomson, K. H.: Holocene sea-level changes along the North Carolina Coastline and their implications for glacial isostatic adjustment models, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 28, 1725–1736, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2009.02.002>, *quaternary Ice Sheet-Ocean Interactions and Landscape Responses*, 2009.
- Hubbs, C. L. and Bien, G. S.: La Jolla Natural Radiocarbon Measurements V, *Radiocarbon*, 9, 261–294, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200000564>, 1967.
- Hyvärinen, H., Raukas, A., and Kessel, H.: Mastogloia and Litorina Seas, in: *Geology of the Gulf of Finland*, edited by Raukas, A. and Hyvärinen, H., pp. 296–311, Estonian Academy of Sciences, Tallinn, URL <https://www.etera.ee/s/кЕ09W5w8ph>, Language: Russian, Title (in original language): Мастоглойное и Литориновое моря, *Journal/book (in original language): Геология Финского залива*, 1992.
- Hyvärinen, H.: Coastal migration in the Helsinki region during the Litorina period in the light of a sample series from Sipoo, *Terra*, 91, 15–20, title translated with DeepL, Language: Finnish, Title (in original language): Helsingin seudun rannansiirtyminen Litorina-aikana Sipoosta tutkitun näytesarjan valossa, 1979.
- Hyvärinen, H.: Interpretation of stratigraphical evidence of sea-level history: a Litorina site near Helsinki, southern Finland, in: *Annales Academiae Scientiarum Fennicae Series A. III. Geologica - Geographica*, vol. 134, pp. 139–149, Suomalainen tiedeakatemia, Helsinki, studies on the Baltic shorelines and sediments indicating relative sea-level changes : proceedings of the symposium of INQUA subcommission on shorelines of northwestern Europe, Lammi 13th September 1981, 1982.
- Hyvärinen, H.: The Mastogloia stage in the Baltic Sea history: diatom evidence from southern Finland, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Finland*, 56, 99–115, <https://doi.org/10.17741/bgsf/56.1-2.007>, 1984.
- Håkansson, S.: University of Lund Radiocarbon Dates V, *Radiocarbon*, 14, 380–00, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200059440>, 1972.
- Håkansson, S.: University of Lund Radiocarbon Dates VI, *Radiocarbon*, 15, 493–513, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200008961>, 1973.
- Håkansson, S.: University of Lund Radiocarbon Dates VII, *Radiocarbon*, 16, 307–330, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200059634>, 1974.
- Håkansson, S.: University of Lund Radiocarbon Dates VIII, *Radiocarbon*, 17, 174–195, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200002034>, 1975.
- Håkansson, S.: University of Lund Radiocarbon Dates IX, *Radiocarbon*, 18, 290–320, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200003179>, 1976.
- Håkansson, S.: University of Lund Radiocarbon Dates XI, *Radiocarbon*, 20, 416–435, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200009218>, 1978.
- Håkansson, S.: University of Lund Radiocarbon Dates XIV, *Radiocarbon*, 23, 384–403, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200037784>, 1981.
- Håkansson, S.: University of Lund Radiocarbon Dates XV, *Radiocarbon*, 24, 194–213, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S003382220000504X>, 1982.

- Håkansson, S.: University of Lund Radiocarbon Dates XX, *Radiocarbon*, 29, 353–379, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200043769>, 1987.
- Héту, B.: Deglaciation, land emersion and late glacial permafrost in the Rimouski region, Quebec, in: *Il y a 8000 ans à Rimouski…Paléoécologie et archéologie d’ un site de la culture plano*, vol. 22 of *Paléo-Québec*, pp. 5–48, Recherches amérindiennes au Québec, Montréal, QC, Canada, URL <https://recherches-amerindiennes.qc.ca/site/produit/il-y-a-8000-ans-a-rimouski-paleoecologie-et-archeologie-dun-site-de-la-culture-plano-version-pdf-1994/>, title translated with DeepL, Language: French, Title (in original language): *Déglaciation, émersion des terres et pergélisol tardiglaciaire dans la région de Rimouski, Québec*, 1994.
- Igarashi, A., Harada, N., and Moriwaki, K.: Marine fossils of 30–40 ka in raised beach deposits, and late pleistocene glacial history around Lützow Holm Bay, East Antarctica, *Proceedings of the NIPR Symposium on Antarctic Geosciences*, 8, 219–229, <https://doi.org/10.15094/00002799>, 1995a.
- Igarashi, A., Numanami, H., Tsuchiya, Y., Harada, N., Fukuchi, M., and Saito, T.: Radiocarbon ages of molluscan shell and fossils in raised beach deposits along the east coast of Lützow Holm Bay, Antarctica, determined by accelerator mass-spectrometry, *Proceedings of the NIPR Symposium on Polar Biology*, 8, 154–162, <https://doi.org/10.15094/00005277>, 1995b.
- Ilves, E., Liiva, A., and Punning, J. M.: *Radiocarbon Method and Its Application in Estonian Quaternary Geology and Archaeology*, Academy of Sciences of the ESSR, Tallinn, Estonia, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Ильвес, Э., Лийва, А., and Я.-М., Пуннинг, Title (in original language): *Радиоуглеродный метод и его применение в четвертичной геологии и археологии Эстонии*, 1974.
- Ingólfsson, Ó., Lyså, A., Funder, S., Möller, P., and Björck, S.: Late Quaternary glacial history of the central west coast of Jameson Land, East Greenland, *Boreas*, 23, 447–458, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1994.tb00612.x>, 1994.
- Ishiwa, T., Yokoyama, Y., Okuno, J., Obrochta, S., Uehara, K., Ikehara, M., and Miyairi, Y.: A sea-level plateau preceding the Marine Isotope Stage 2 minima revealed by Australian sediments, *Scientific reports*, 9, 6449, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-42573-4>, 2019.
- Ishiwa, T., Okuno, J., and Suganuma, Y.: Excess ice loads in the Indian Ocean sector of East Antarctica during the last glacial period, *Geology*, 49, 1182–1186, <https://doi.org/10.1130/G48830.1>, 2021.
- Ives, P. C., Levin, B., Robinson, R. D., and Rubin, M.: U. S. Geological Survey Radiocarbon Dates VII, *Radiocarbon*, 6, 37–76, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200010547>, 1964.
- Jaanits, L. and Jaanits, K.: Excavations of the early Mesolithic settlement of Pulli, *Eesti NSV Teaduste Akadeemia Toimetised, Ühiskonnateadused*, 27, 56–63, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): *Ausgrabungen der frühmesolithischen Siedlung von Pulli*, 1978.
- Jaanits, L. and Liiva, A.: Chronology of the oldest Estonian history and the radiocarbon method, *Eesti NSV Teaduste Akadeemia aastail 1965-1972*, pp. 157–161, title translated using DeepL, Language: Estonian, Title (in original language): *Eesti vanima ajaloo kronoloogia ja radiosüsiniku meetod*, 1973.
- James, N. P., Bone, Y., Kyser, T. K., Dix, G. R., and Collins, L. B.: The importance of changing oceanography in controlling late Quaternary carbonate sedimentation on a high-energy, tropical, oceanic ramp: north-western Australia, *Sedimentology*, 51, 1179–1205, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3091.2004.00666.x>, 2004.

- Jelgersma, S.: Holocene sea-level changes in the Netherlands, Mededelingen geologische stichting, 7, Leiden University, 1961.
- Jelgersma, S.: Sea-level changes in the North Sea basin, Acta Universitatis Upsaliensis, Symposia Universitatis Upsaliensis Annum Quingentesimum Celebrantis, 2, 233–248, 1979.
- Jennings, J. N.: Desert dunes and estuarine fill in the Fitzroy estuary (North-Western Australia), CATENA, 2, 215–262, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0341-8162\(75\)80015-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0341-8162(75)80015-4), Language: English with German abstract, 1975.
- Jensen, J. B. and Bennike, O.: Geological setting as background for methane distribution in Holocene mud deposits, Århus Bay, Denmark, Continental Shelf Research, 29, 775–784, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csr.2008.08.007>, 2009.
- Jensen, J. B. and Stecher, O.: Paraglacial barrier–lagoon development in the late pleistocene Baltic Ice Lake, southwestern Baltic, Marine Geology, 107, 81–101, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(92\)90070-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(92)90070-X), 1992.
- Jensen, J. B., Bennike, O., Witkowski, A., Lemke, W., and Kuijpers, A.: The Baltic Ice Lake in the southwestern Baltic: sequence-, chrono- and biostratigraphy, Boreas, 26, 217–236, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1997.tb00853.x>, 1997.
- Jensen, J. B., Petersen, K. S., Konradi, P., Kuijpers, A., Bennike, O., Lemke, W., and Endler, R.: Neotectonics, sea-level changes and biological evolution in the Fennoscandian Border Zone of the southern Kattegat Sea, Boreas, 31, 133–150, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2002.tb01062.x>, 2002.
- Jessen, C., Christensen, C., and Nielsen, B. H.: Postglacial relative sea-level rise in the Limfjord region, northern Jutland, Denmark, Boreas, 48, 119–130, <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12350>, 2019.
- Johnson, D., Cuff, C., and Rhodes, E.: Holocene reef sequences and geochemistry, Britomart Reef, central Great Barrier Reef, Australia, Sedimentology, 31, 515–529, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3091.1984.tb01817.x>, 1984.
- Johnson, D. P. and Carter, R. M.: Sedimentary framework of mainland fringing reef development, Cape Tribulation Area, Tech. rep., Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority, Townsville, URL <http://hdl.handle.net/11017/122>, 1987.
- Johnson, D. P. and Risk, M. J.: Fringing reef growth on a terrigenous mud foundation, Fantome Island, central Great Barrier reef, Australia, Sedimentology, 34, 275–287, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3091.1987.tb00777.x>, 1987.
- Johnson, J. S., Bentley, M. J., and Gohl, K.: First exposure ages from the Amundsen Sea Embayment, West Antarctica: The Late Quaternary context for recent thinning of Pine Island, Smith, and Pope Glaciers, Geology, 36, 223–226, <https://doi.org/10.1130/G24207A.1>, 2008.
- Jones, B. G., Young, R. W., and Eliot, I. G.: Stratigraphy and chronology of receding barrier-beach deposits on the northern Illawarra coast of New South Wales, Journal of the Geological Society of Australia, 26, 255–264, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00167617908729089>, 1979.
- Jones, M., Hekel, H., and Searle, D. E.: Late Quaternary sedimentation in Moreton Bay, Papers (University of Queensland. Dept. of Geology), 8, 6–17, URL <https://espace.library.uq.edu.au/view/UQ:320268>, 1978.

- Jones, R. L.: Late Holocene vegetational changes on the Illawarra coastal plain, New South Wales, Australia, *Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology*, 65, 37–46, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0034-6667\(90\)90054-M](https://doi.org/10.1016/0034-6667(90)90054-M), proceedings of the Seventh International Palynological Congress - Part II, 1990.
- Jonuks, T.: An antler object from the Pärnu River—an axe, a god or a decoy, in: *Man, His Time, Artefacts, and Places: Collection of Articles Dedicated to Richard Indreko*, edited by Johanson, K. and Tõrv, M., vol. 19 of *Muinasaja Teadus*, pp. 225–246, Tartu Ülikooli ajaloo ja arheoloogia instituut, 2013.
- Jonuks, T.: A mesolithic human figurine from River Pärnu, South-West Estonia: A century-old puzzle of idols, goddesses and ancestral symbols, *Estonian Journal of Archaeology*, 20, 111–127, <https://doi.org/10.3176/ARCH.2016.2.01>, 2016.
- Jordan, R.: Pollen diagrams from Hamilton Inlet, central Labrador, and their environmental implications for the northern Maritime Archaic, *Arctic Anthropology*, 12, 92–116, URL <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40315877>, 1975.
- Jungner, H.: Radiocarbon dates I, Tech. rep., Dating Laboratory, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland, URL <http://hdl.handle.net/10013/epic.ea2eff4a-ff59-4639-a921-7dda7392d5e1>, 1979.
- Jungner, H. and Sonninen, E.: Radiocarbon dates II, Tech. rep., University of Helsinki, URL <https://hdl.handle.net/10013/epic.6f6dc652-48ac-4232-8acc-51caf9aac37b>, 1983.
- Kasper, J. N. and Allard, M.: Late-Holocene climatic changes as detected by the growth and decay of ice wedges on the southern shore of Hudson Strait, northern Québec, Canada, *The Holocene*, 11, 563–577, <https://doi.org/10.1191/095968301680223512>, 2001.
- Kaye, C. A. and Barghoorn, E. S.: Late Quaternary sea-level change and crustal rise at Boston, Massachusetts, with notes on the autocompaction of peat, *Geological Society of America Bulletin*, 75, 63–80, [https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606\(1964\)75\[63:LQSCAC\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0016-7606(1964)75[63:LQSCAC]2.0.CO;2), 1964.
- Kelley, J. T., Dickson, S. M., Belknap, D. F., and Stuckenrath Jr, R.: Sea-level change and late Quaternary sediment accumulation on the southern Maine inner continental shelf, in: *Quaternary Coasts of the United States*, edited by Wehmiller, J. and Fletcher, C., vol. 48 of *Special Publications of SEPM*, pp. 23–34, SEPM Society for Sedimentary Geology, <https://doi.org/10.2110/pec.92.48.0023>, 1992.
- Kelley, J. T., Gehrels, W. R., and Belknap, D. F.: Late Holocene relative sea-level rise and the geological development of tidal marshes at Wells, Maine, USA, *Journal of Coastal Research*, 11, 136–153, URL <https://journals.flvc.org/jcr/article/view/79515>, 1995.
- Kelly, M. and Bennike, O.: Quaternary geology of parts of central and western North Greenland: a preliminary account, *Rapport Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 126, 111–116, <https://doi.org/10.34194/rapgggu.v126.7917>, 1985.
- Kelly, M. and Bennike, O.: Quaternary geology of western and central North Greenland, *Rapport Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 153, 1–34, <https://doi.org/10.34194/rapgggu.v153.8164>, Language: English with Danish and Greenlandic abstracts, 1992.
- Kelly, M., Funder, S., Houmark-Nielsen, M., Knudsen, K. L., Kronborg, C., Landvik, J., and Sorby, L.: Quaternary glacial and marine environmental history of northwest Greenland: a review and reappraisal, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 18, 373–392, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(98\)00004-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(98)00004-3), 1999.

- Kemp, A. C.: High resolution studies of late Holocene relative sea-level change (North Carolina, USA), Ph.D. thesis, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, Pennsylvania, United States, URL <https://repository.upenn.edu/dissertations/AAI3363375/>, 2009.
- Kemp, A. C., Wright, A. J., Barnett, R. L., Hawkes, A. D., Charman, D. J., Sameshima, C., King, A. N., Mooney, H. C., Edwards, R. J., Horton, B. P., et al.: Utility of salt-marsh foraminifera, testate amoebae and bulk-sediment $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values as sea-level indicators in Newfoundland, Canada, *Marine Micropaleontology*, 130, 43–59, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marmicro.2016.12.003>, 2017.
- Kendrick, G. W.: Middle Holocene marine molluscs from near Guildford, Western Australia, and evidence for climatic change, *Journal of the Royal Society of Western Australia*, 59, 97–104, URL <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/part/238236>, 1977.
- Kessel, H.: On the age of Holocene transgressions of the Baltic Sea in Estonia by palynological analysis, *Baltica*, 1, 101–115, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Кессел, Х. Я., Title (in original language): Возраст трансгрессий голоценовых бассейнов Балтики в Эстонии по палинологическим данным, *Journal/book (in original language): Балтика*, 1963.
- Kessel, H. and Punning, J. M.: On the absolute age of Holocene transgressions of the Baltic Sea in the Estonian Territory, *Eesti NSV Teaduste Akadeemia Toimetised. Keemia. Geoloogia*, 18, 141–153, <https://doi.org/10.3176/chem.geol.1969.2.04>, title translated with DeepL, Language: Russian with Estonian and German abstracts, Title (in original language): ОБ АБСОЛЮТНОМ ВОЗРАСТЕ ГОЛОЦЕНОВЫХ ТРАНСГРЕССИЙ БАЛТИКИ НА ТЕРРИТОРИИ ЭСТОНИИ, 1969a.
- Kessel, H. and Punning, J.-M.: On the distribution and stratigraphy of the Yoldia Sea sediments in Estonian Territory, *Eesti NSV Teaduste Akadeemia Toimetised. Keemia. Geoloogia*, 18, 154–163, <https://doi.org/10.3176/chem.geol.1969.2.05>, title translated with DeepL, Language: Russian with Estonian and German abstract, Title (in original language): О РАСПРОСТРАНЕНИИ И СТРАТИГРАФИИ ОТЛОЖЕНИЙ ИОЛЬДИЕВОГО МОРЯ НА ТЕРРИТОРИИ ЭСТОНИИ, 1969b.
- Kessel, H. and Punning, J.-M.: About the age of the Ancyclus Stage in Estonia (radiometric datings), *Eesti NSV Teaduste Akadeemia Toimetised. Keemia. Geoloogia*, 23, 59–64, <https://doi.org/10.3176/chem.geol.1974.1.09>, Language: Russian with abstracts in Estonian and English, Title (in original language): О ВОЗРАСТЕ АНЦИЛОВОЙ СТАДИИ В ЭСТОНИИ (ПО РАДИОМЕТРИЧЕСКИМ ДАННЫМ), 1974.
- Khan, N. S., Horton, B. P., Engelhart, S., Rovere, A., Vacchi, M., Ashe, E. L., Törnqvist, T. E., Dutton, A., Hijma, M. P., and Shennan, I.: Inception of a global atlas of sea levels since the Last Glacial Maximum, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 220, 359–371, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2019.07.016>, 2019.
- Kiden, P.: Holocene water level movements in the lower Scheldt perimarine area, in: *Quaternary sea-level investigations from Belgium: a contribution to IGCP Project 200*, edited by Baeteman, C., vol. 200 of *Professional Paper*, pp. 1–19, Geological Survey of Belgium, Brussel, URL <https://www.vliz.be/nl/open-marien-archief?module=ref&refid=53772>, 1989.
- Kiden, P.: Holocene relative sea-level change and crustal movement in the southwestern Netherlands, *Marine Geology*, 124, 21–41, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(95\)00030-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(95)00030-3), 1995.
- Kiden, P., Denys, L., and Johnston, P.: Late Quaternary sea-level change and isostatic and tectonic land movements along the Belgian–Dutch North Sea coast: geological data and model results, *Journal of Quaternary Science*, 17, 535–546, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.709>, 2002.

- Kigoshi, K., Suzuki, N., and Fukatsu, H.: Gakushuin Natural Radiocarbon Measurements VIII, Radiocarbon, 15, 42–67, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200058598>, 1973.
- King, G.: A Standard Method for Evaluating Radiocarbon Dates of Local Deglaciation: Application to the Deglaciation History of Southern Labrador and Adjacent Québec, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 39, 163–182, <https://doi.org/10.7202/032600ar>, Language: English with French and German abstracts, 1985.
- Kirwan, M. L., Murray, A. B., Donnelly, J. P., and Corbett, D. R.: Rapid wetland expansion during European settlement and its implication for marsh survival under modern sediment delivery rates, *Geology*, 39, 507–510, <https://doi.org/10.1130/G31789.1>, 2011.
- Knudsen, K. L.: Middle and Late Weichselian marine deposits at Nørre Lyngby, northern Jutland, Denmark, and their foraminiferal faunas, *Danmarks Geologiske Undersøgelse II. Række*, 112, 1–44, <https://doi.org/10.34194/raekke2.v112.6903>, Language: English with Danish summary, 1978.
- Kolka, V. V. and Korsakova, O. P.: Age of archaeological stone labyrinths and relative movement of White Sea's strand line in late-glacial and Holocene epochs, *Proceedings of the Russian Geographical Society*, 142, 52–63, URL <https://izv.rgo.ru/jour/article/view/136>, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Колька, В. В. and Корсакова, О. П., Title (in original language): Возраст археологических объектов - каменных лабиринтов и относительное перемещение береговой линии Белого моря в позднеледниковье и голоцене, *Journal/book (in original language): Известия Русского географического общества*, 2010.
- Kolka, V. V., Evzerov, V. Y., Møller, J. J., and Corner, G. D.: Postglacial Glacioisostatic Movements in the north-east of the Baltic Shield, in: *New Data on Geology and mineral Resources of Kola Peninsula (Collected Essays)*, edited by Mitrofanov, F. P., pp. 15–25, Kola Research Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences Publishing House, Apatity, Russia, (In Russian), Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Колька, В. В., Евзеров, В. Я., Мёллер, Я., and Корнер, Д., Title (in original language): Последледниковые гляциоизостатические движения на северо-востоке Балтийского щита, *Journal/book (in original language): Новые данные по геологии и полезным ископаемым Кольского полуострова : сб. ст.*, 2005.
- Kolka, V. V., Evzerov, V. Y., Møller, J. J., and Corner, G. D.: The late Weichselian and Holocene relative sea-level change and isolation basin stratigraphy at the Umba Settlement, southern coast of Kola Peninsula, *Izvestiya Rossiiskoi Akademii Nauk. Seriya Geograficheskaya*, 1, 73–88, <https://doi.org/10.15356/0373-2444-2013-1-73-88>, (In Russian), Language: Russian with English abstract, Authors (in original language): Колька, В. В., Евзеров, В. Я., Мёллер, Я. Й., and Д., Корнер Г., Title (in original language): ЕРЕМЕЩЕНИЕ УРОВНЯ МОРЯ В ПОЗДНЕМ ПЛЕЙСТОЦЕНЕ – ГОЛОЦЕНЕ И СТРАТИГРАФИЯ ДОННЫХ ОСАДКОВ ИЗОЛИРОВАННЫХ ОЗЕР НА ЮЖНОМ БЕРЕГУ КОЛЬСКОГО ПОЛУОСТРОВА, В РАЙОНЕ ПОСЕЛКА УМБА, *Journal/book (in original language): Известия Российской академии наук. Серия географическая*, 2013a.
- Kolka, V. V., Korsakova, O. P., Shelekhova, T. S., Lavrova, N. B., and Arslanov, K. A.: Reconstruction of the relative level of the White Sea during the Holocene on the Karelian coast near Engozero settlement, Northern Karelia, *Doklady Earth Sciences*, 449, 434–438, URL [10.1134/S1028334X13040107](https://doi.org/10.1134/S1028334X13040107), 2013b.
- Kolka, V. V., Korsakova, O. P., Shelekhova, T. S., and Tolstobrova, A. N.: Reconstruction of the relative level of the White Sea during the Lateglacial – Holocene according to lithological, diatom analyses and radiocarbon dating of small lakes bottom sediments in the area of the Chupa settlement (North Karelia, Russia), *Vestnik of MGTU*, 18, 255–268, URL <http://vestnik.mstu.edu.ru/show->

- eng.shtml?art=1676, Language: Russian with English abstract, Authors (in original language): Колька, В. В., Корсакова, О. П., Шелехова, Т. С., and Толстоброва, А. Н., Title (in original language): Восстановление относительного положения уровня Белого моря в позднеледниковье и голоцене по данным литологического, диатомового анализов и радиоуглеродного датирования донных отложений малых озер в районе пос. Чупа (северная Карелия), Journal/book (in original language): Вестник МГТУ, 2015.
- Konishi, K., Omura, A., and Nakamichi, O.: Radiometric coral ages and sea level records from the late Quaternary reef complexes of the Ryukyu Islands, in: Proceedings of the Second International Coral Reef Symposium, edited by Cameron, A. M., Cambell, B. M., Cribb, A. B., Endean, R., Jell, J. S., Jones, O. A., Mather, P., and Talbot, F. H., vol. 2, The Great Barrier Reef Committee, Brisbane, Australia, 1974.
- Koshechkin, B. I.: Holocene Tectonics of the Eastern Baltic Shield, Nauka, Leningrad, Soviet Union, URL <https://www.geokniga.org/authors/43831>, title translated with DeepL, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Кошечкин, Б И, Title (in original language): Голоценовая тектоника восточной части Балтийского щита, Journal/book (in original language): Наука, 1979.
- Koshechkin, B. I., Kagan, L. Y., Kudlaeva, A. L., Malyasova, E. S., and Pervuninskaya, N. A.: Coastal formations of late - and postglacial marine basins in the south of Kola Peninsula, Paleogeography and morphostructures of the Kola Peninsula, -, 87–133, URL <https://www.geokniga.org/books/21012>, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Кошечкин, Б. И., Каган, Л. Я., Кудлаева, А. Л., Малясова, Е. С., and Первунинская, Н. А., Title (in original language): Береговые образования поздне-и послеледниковых морских бассейнов на юге Кольского полуострова, Journal/book (in original language): Палеогеография и морфоструктуры Кольского полуострова, 1973.
- Kovaleva, G.: Modern crustal movements of the Admiralty Peninsula (North Island of Novaya Zemlya), in: Geotectonic prerequisites for the search for minerals on the shelves of the Arctic Ocean, pp. 87–93, Niiga, Leningrad, Soviet Union, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Ковалева, Г.А., Title (in original language): Современные движения полуострова Адмиралтейства (Северный остров Новой Земли), Journal/book (in original language): Геотектонические предпосылки к поискам полезных ископаемых на шельфах Северного Ледовитого океана, 1974.
- Kraft, J. C.: Radiocarbon dates in the Delaware coastal zone (eastern Atlantic Coast of North America), University of Delaware Sea Grant Publication DEL-SG-19-76, College of Marine Studies, University of Delaware, URL <https://repository.library.noaa.gov/view/noaa/39849>, 1976.
- Kranck, K.: Geomorphological development and post-Pleistocene sea level changes, Northumberland Strait, Maritime Provinces, Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences, 9, 835–844, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e72-067>, Language: English with French abstract, 1972.
- Krapivner, R. B.: Rapid Sagging of the Barents Shelf over the Last 15–16 ka, Geotectonics, 40, 197–207, <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0016852106030046>, 2006.
- Kriiska, A.: New Neolithic settlements in Riigiküla, Proceedings of the Estonian Academy of Sciences. Humanities and Social Sciences, 44, 448–454, Language: English with Estonian and Russian abstracts, 1995.
- Kriiska, A.: Stone Age settlements in the lower reaches of the Narva River, North-eastern Estonia, in: PACT, vol. 51, pp. 359–169, Conseil de l'Europe, URL <http://webdoc.sub.gwdg.de/>

ebook/o/2004/ethesis.helsinki.fi/julkaisut/hum/kultt/vk/kriiska/tekstid/02.html, 1996.

- Kriiska, A.: Archaeological field work on Stone Age settlement site of SW Estonia, in: Archaeological fieldwork in Estonia 2000, pp. 19–33, University of Tartu Department of Archaeology, 2001.
- Kriiska, A.: Settlement of the West Estonian islands and the development of a permanent population, *Muinasaja teadus*, 11, 29–60, title translated with DeepL, Language: Estonian, Title (in original language): Lääne-Eesti saarte asustamine ja püsielanikkonna kujunemine, 2002.
- Kriiska, A. and Lõugas, L.: Late Mesolithic and Early Neolithic seasonal settlement at Kõpu, Hiiumaa Island, Estonia, in: Environmental and Cultural History of the Eastern Baltic Region (PACT), vol. 57, pp. 157–172, Conseil de l'Europe, Rixensart, URL <http://webdoc.sub.gwdg.de/ebook/o/2004/ethesis.helsinki.fi/julkaisut/hum/kultt/vk/kriiska/tekstid/02.html>, 1999.
- Kriiska, A. and Lõugas, L.: Stone Age settlement sites on an environmentally sensitive coastal area along the lower reaches of the River Pärnu (south-western Estonia), as indicators of changing settlement patterns, technologies and economies, in: *Mesolithic Horizons*, edited by McCartan, S., Schulting, R., Warren, G., and Woodman, P., vol. 1, pp. 167–175, Oxford-Oakville: Oxbow Books, URL <https://www.etis.ee/Portal/Publications/Display/8f056b6b-2268-4fcd-afd2-8a337d471f2e>, 2009.
- Kriiska, A., Saluäär, U., Lõugas, L., Johanson, K., and Hanni, H.: Archaeological excavations in Sindi-Lodja, in: Archaeological fieldwork in Estonia 2001, edited by Tamla, U., pp. 27–40, University of Tartu Department of Archaeology, 2002.
- Kriiska, A., Lavento, M., and Peets, J.: New AMS dates of the Neolithic and Bronze Age ceramics in Estonia: preliminary results and interpretations, *Estonian Journal of Archaeology*, 9, 3–31, URL <https://www.ceeol.com/search/article-detail?id=177964>, Language: English with Estonian abstract, 2005.
- Krog, H.: The Quaternary history of the Baltic, Denmark, in: *The Quaternary history of the Baltic*, edited by Gudelis, V. and Königsson, L.-K., vol. 1, pp. 207–217, Uppsala University, 1979.
- Krog, H. and Tauber, H.: C-14 chronology of late- and post-glacial marine deposits in north Jutland, *Danmarks Geologiske Undersøgelse, Årbog* 1973, pp. 93–105, 1974.
- Kuhry, P.: Palsa and peat plateau development in the Hudson Bay Lowlands, Canada: timing, pathways and causes, *Boreas*, 37, 316–327, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2007.00022.x>, 2008.
- Königsson, L.-K., Saarse, L., and Veski, S.: Holocene history of vegetation and landscape on the Kõpu Peninsula, Hiiumaa Island, Estonia, *Proceedings of the Estonian Academy of Sciences. Geology*, 47, 3–19, <https://doi.org/10.3176/GEOL.1998.1.01>, Language: English with Estonian and Russian abstracts, 1998.
- Körber-Grohne, U.: Geobotanical investigations on the Feddersen Wierde, vol. 1 of *Feddersen Wierde*, Steiner, Wiesbaden, Language: German, Title (in original language): Geobotanische Untersuchungen auf der Feddersen Wierde, 1967.
- Lajeunesse, P. and Allard, M.: Late Quaternary Deglaciation, Glaciomarine Sedimentation and Glacioisostatic Recovery in the Rivière Nastapoka Area, Eastern Hudson Bay, Northern Québec, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 57, 65–83, <https://doi.org/10.7202/010331ar>, Language: English with French and Spanish abstracts, 2003.

- Lamarre, A., Garneau, M., and Asnong, H.: Holocene paleohydrological reconstruction and carbon accumulation of a permafrost peatland using testate amoeba and macrofossil analyses, *Kuujjuarapik, subarctic Québec, Canada, Review of Palaeobotany and Palynology*, 186, 131–141, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.revpalbo.2012.04.009>, 2012.
- Lampe, R. and Janke, W.: The Holocene sea level rise in the Southern Baltic as reflected in coastal peat sequences, *Polish geological institute Special papers*, 11, 19–29, URL <https://yadda.icm.edu.pl/yadda/element/bwmeta1.element.baztech-article-BUS6-0022-0003>, 2004.
- Lampe, R., Endtmann, E., Janke, W., and Meyer, H.: Relative sea-level development and isostasy along the NE German Baltic Sea coast during the past 9 ka, *E&G Quaternary Science Journal*, 59, 3–20, <https://doi.org/10.3285/eg.59.1-2.01>, Language: English with German abstract, 2010.
- Landvik, J. Y.: The last glaciation of Germania Land and adjacent areas, northeast Greenland, *Journal of Quaternary Science*, 9, 81–92, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.3390090108>, 1994.
- Landvik, J. Y., Weidick, A., and Hansen, A.: The glacial history of the Hans Tausen Iskappe and the last glaciation of Peary Land, North Greenland, *Meddelelser om Grønland, Geoscience*, 39, 27–44, 2001.
- Larcombe, P. and Carter, R. M.: Sequence architecture during the Holocene transgression: an example from the Great Barrier Reef shelf, Australia, *Sedimentary Geology*, 117, 97–121, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0037-0738\(97\)00119-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0037-0738(97)00119-X), 1998.
- Larcombe, P., Carter, R., Dye, J., Gagan, M., and Johnson, D.: New evidence for episodic post-glacial sea-level rise, central Great Barrier Reef, Australia, *Marine Geology*, 127, 1–44, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(95\)00059-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(95)00059-8), 1995.
- Larsen, E., Kjær, K. H., Demidov, I. N., Funder, S., Grøsfjeld, K., Houmark-Nielsen, M., Jensen, M., Linge, H., and Lysa, A.: Late Pleistocene glacial and lake history of northwestern Russia, *Boreas*, 35, 394–424, <https://doi.org/10.1080/03009480600781958>, 2006.
- Larsen, N. K., Funder, S., Kjær, K. H., Kjeldsen, K. K., Knudsen, M. F., and Linge, H.: Rapid early Holocene ice retreat in West Greenland, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 92, 310–323, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2013.05.027>, aPEX II: Arctic Palaeoclimate and its Extremes, 2014.
- Larsen, N. K., Strunk, A., Levy, L. B., Olsen, J., Bjørk, A., Lauridsen, T. L., Jeppesen, E., and Davidson, T. A.: Strong altitudinal control on the response of local glaciers to Holocene climate change in southwest Greenland, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 168, 69–78, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2017.05.008>, 2017.
- Lasca, N. P.: Postglacial delevelling in Skeldal, Northeast Greenland, *Arctic*, 19, 285–364, <https://doi.org/10.14430/arctic3441>, Language: English with French and Russian abstracts, 1966.
- Lasher, G. E., Axford, Y., Masterson, A. L., Berman, K., and Larocca, L. J.: Holocene temperature and landscape history of southwest Greenland inferred from isotope and geochemical lake sediment proxies, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 239, 106–135, <https://doi.org/j.quascirev.2020.106358>, 2020.
- Lauriol, B. and Gray, J.: Oxygen Isotope Composition of Marine Shells and Relationship to Deglaciation of the Coastal Margins of the Ungava Peninsula, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 51, 185–199, <https://doi.org/10.7202/033117ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): La composition isotopique des mollusques marins et sa relation à la déglaciation de la péninsule d' Ungava, 1997.

- Lauriol, B. and Gray, J. T.: The decay and disappearance of the late Wisconsin ice sheet in the Ungava Peninsula, northern Québec, Canada, *Arctic and Alpine Research*, 19, 109–126, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00040851.1987.12002586>, 1987.
- Lauriol, B., Gray, J., Héту, B., and Cyr, A.: Chronology and paleogeography of the sea since deglaciation in the Aupaluk area, Nouveau-Québec, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 33, 189–203, <https://doi.org/10.7202/1000068ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): Le cadre chronologique et paléogéographique de l' évolution marine depuis la déglaciation dans la région d' Aupaluk Nouveau-Québec, 1979.
- Lavoie, C., Allard, M., and Duhamel, D.: Deglaciation landforms and C-14 chronology of the Lac Guillaume-Delisle area, eastern Hudson Bay: a report on field evidence, *Geomorphology*, 159, 142–155, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2012.03.015>, 2012.
- Lavoie, M. and Filion, L.: Holocene vegetation dynamics of Anticosti Island, Québec, and consequences of remoteness on ecological succession, *Quaternary Research*, 56, 112–127, <https://doi.org/10.1006/qres.2001.2239>, 2001.
- Lecavalier, B. S., Milne, G. A., Simpson, M. J., Wake, L., Huybrechts, P., Tarasov, L., Kjeldsen, K. K., Funder, S., Long, A. J., Woodroffe, S., Dyke, A. S., and Larsen, N. K.: A model of Greenland ice sheet deglaciation constrained by observations of relative sea level and ice extent, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 102, 54–84, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2014.07.018>, 2014.
- Leino, J.: Peatland conditions in some overgrown peatlands around Salon, Master's thesis, University of Turku, title translated with DeepL, Language: Finnish, Title (in original language): Eräiden umpeenkasvusoiden turvesuhteista Salon ympäristössä, 1973.
- Lemieux, A.-M., Bhiry, N., and Desrosiers, P. M.: The geoarchaeology and traditional knowledge of winter sod houses in eastern Hudson Bay, Canadian Low Arctic, *Geoarchaeology*, 26, 479–500, <https://doi.org/10.1002/gea.20365>, 2011.
- Leorri, E., Martin, R., and McLaughlin, P.: Holocene environmental and parasequence development of the St. Jones Estuary, Delaware (USA): Foraminiferal proxies of natural climatic and anthropogenic change, *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 241, 590–607, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2006.04.011>, 2006.
- Lepland, A., Hang, T., Kihno, K., Sakson, M., and Sandgren, P.: Holocene sea-level changes and environmental history in the Narva area, north-eastern Estonia, in: PACT, vol. 51, pp. 205–216, Conseil de l'Europe, Rixensart, 1996.
- Lessa, G. and Masselink, G.: Evidence of a Mid-Holocene Sea Level Highstand from the Sedimentary Record of a Macrotidal Barrier and Paleoenvironmental System in Northwestern Australia, *Journal of Coastal Research*, 22, 100–112, <https://doi.org/10.2112/05A-0009.1>, 2006.
- Levitan, M. A., Lavrushin, Y. A., and Stein, R.: Outlines of sedimentation history of the Arctic Ocean and Subarctic Seas for the last 130 ka., GEOS, Moscow, Russia, (In Russian), Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Левитан, М. А., Лаврушин, Ю. А., and П., Штайн, Title (in original language): Очерки истории седиментации в Северном Ледовитом океане и морях Субарктики в течение последних 130 тыс. лет., 2007.
- Lewis, S. E., Wüst, R. A. J., Webster, J. M., and Shields, G. A.: Mid-late Holocene sea-level variability in eastern Australia, *Terra Nova*, 20, 74–81, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3121.2007.00789.x>, 2008.

- Lewis, S. E., Sloss, C. R., Murray-Wallace, C. V., Woodroffe, C. D., and Smithers, S. G.: Post-glacial sea-level changes around the Australian margin: a review, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 74, 115–138, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2012.09.006>, linking Southern Hemisphere records and past circulation patterns: the AUS-INTIMATE project, 2013.
- Lewis, S. E., Wüst, R. A., Webster, J. M., Collins, J., Wright, S. A., and Jacobsen, G.: Rapid relative sea-level fall along north-eastern Australia between 1200 and 800cal.yrBP: An appraisal of the oyster evidence, *Marine Geology*, 370, 20–30, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2015.09.014>, 2015.
- Liiva, A., Ilves, E., and Punning, J.: List of radiocarbon dates from the Institute of Zoology and Botany of the Academy of Sciences of the Estonian SSR, *Eesti NSV Teaduste Akadeemia Toimetised, Bioloogiline seeria*, 15, 112–122, URL <https://kirjandus.geoloogia.info/reference/30212>, title translated by DeepL, Language: Russian, with abstracts in Estonian and German, Title (in original language): Список радиоуглеродных датировок Института зоологии и ботаники АН ЭССР, Journal/book (in original language): Известия Академии наук Эстонской ССР, 1966.
- Liljegren, R.: Littoral sediments in the area between Ronneby and Karlshamn, translated with DeepL, Language: Swedish, Title (in original language): Litorinasediment i området mellan Ronneby och Karlshamn, 1970.
- Lindow, J., Castex, M., Wittmann, H., Johnson, J. S., Lisker, F., Gohl, K., and Spiegel, C.: Glacial retreat in the Amundsen Sea sector, West Antarctica – first cosmogenic evidence from central Pine Island Bay and the Kohler Range, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 98, 166–173, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2014.05.010>, 2014.
- Lindén, M., Möller, P., Björck, S., and Sandgren, P.: Holocene shore displacement and deglaciation chronology in Norrbotten, Sweden, *Boreas*, 35, 1–22, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2006.tb01109.x>, 2006.
- Linke, G.: The course of Holocene transgression of the North Sea based on results from the Neuwerk/Scharhörn area, *Probleme der Küstenforschung im Südlichen Nordseegebiet*, 14, 123–157, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Der Ablauf der holozanen Transgression der Nordsee aufgrund von Ergebnissen aus dem Gebiet Neuwerk/Scharhörn, 1982.
- Liu, J., Saito, Y., Wang, H., Zhou, L., and Yang, Z.: Stratigraphic development during the Late Pleistocene and Holocene offshore of the Yellow River Delta, Bohai Sea, *Journal of Asian Earth Sciences*, 36, 318–331, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jseaes.2009.06.007>, 2009.
- Liu, J., Saito, Y., Kong, X., Wang, H., Wen, C., Yang, Z., and Nakashima, R.: Delta development and channel incision during Marine Isotope Stages 3 and 2 in the western South Yellow Sea, *Marine Geology*, 278, 54–76, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2010.09.003>, 2010.
- Liverman, D. G. E.: Quaternary geology of the Goose Bay area, Current Research Report 97-1, Newfoundland Department of Mines and Energy, Geological Survey, URL <https://www.gov.nl.ca/iet/mines/geoscience/reports-maps/currentresearch/current-research-1997/>, 1997.
- Locat, J.: Land emergence in the Baie-des-Sables/Trois-Pistoles area, Québec, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 31, 297–306, <https://doi.org/10.7202/1000279ar>, Language: French with abstracts in English and Russian, Title (in original language): L'émersion des terres dans la région de Baie-des-Sables/Trois-Pistoles, Québec, 1977.

- Logan, B. W., Read, J. F., and Davies, G. R.: History of Carbonate Sedimentation, Quaternary Epoch, Shark Bay, Western Australia, in: Carbonate Sedimentation and Environments, Shark Bay, Western Australia, American Association of Petroleum Geologists, <https://doi.org/10.1306/M13369C2>, 1970.
- Løken, O. H.: Postglacial tilting of Akpatok Island, Northwest Territories, Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences, 15, 1547–1553, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e78-160>, Language: English with French abstract, 1978.
- Long, A., Roberts, D., and Dawson, S.: Early Holocene history of the west Greenland Ice Sheet and the GH-8.2 event, Quaternary Science Reviews, 25, 904–922, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2005.07.002>, 2006.
- Long, A. J. and Roberts, D. H.: A revised chronology for the ‘Fjord Stade’ moraine in Disko Bugt, west Greenland, Journal of Quaternary Science, 17, 561–579, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.705>, 2002.
- Long, A. J. and Roberts, D. H.: Late Weichselian deglacial history of Disko Bugt, West Greenland, and the dynamics of the Jakobshavns Isbrae ice stream, Boreas, 32, 208–226, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2003.tb01438.x>, 2003.
- Long, A. J., Roberts, D. H., and Wright, M. R.: Isolation basin stratigraphy and Holocene relative sea-level change on Arveprinsen Ejland, Disko Bugt, West Greenland, Journal of Quaternary Science, 14, 323–345, [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1417\(199907\)14:4<323::AID-JQS442>3.0.CO;2-0](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1417(199907)14:4<323::AID-JQS442>3.0.CO;2-0), 1999.
- Long, A. J., Roberts, D. H., and Rasch, M.: New observations on the relative sea level and deglacial history of Greenland from Innaarsuit, Disko Bugt, Quaternary Research, 60, 162–171, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0033-5894\(03\)00085-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0033-5894(03)00085-1), 2003.
- Long, A. J., Roberts, D. H., Simpson, M. J., Dawson, S., Milne, G. A., and Huybrechts, P.: Late Weichselian relative sea-level changes and ice sheet history in southeast Greenland, Earth and Planetary Science Letters, 272, 8–18, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsl.2008.03.042>, 2008.
- Long, A. J., Woodroffe, S. A., Dawson, S., Roberts, D. H., and Bryant, C. L.: Late Holocene relative sea level rise and the Neoglacial history of the Greenland ice sheet, Journal of Quaternary Science, 24, 345–359, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.1235>, 2009.
- Long, A. J., Woodroffe, S. A., Roberts, D. H., and Dawson, S.: Isolation basins, sea-level changes and the Holocene history of the Greenland Ice Sheet, Quaternary Science Reviews, 30, 3748–3768, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2011.10.013>, 2011.
- Louwe Kooijmans, L.: Prehistoric settlement in the Rhine-Meuse Delta area and the determination of former water heights, in: Probleme der Küstenforschung im südlichen Nordseegebiet, vol. 11, pp. 119–144, Niedersächsisches Institut für historische Küstenforschung, URL <https://hdl.handle.net/1887/2791>, Language: German, Title (in original language): Prähistorische Besiedlung im Rhein-Maas-Deltagebiet und die Bestimmung ehemaliger Wasserhöhen, 1976.
- Louwe Kooijmans, L. and van de Velde, P.: The excavation Hekelingen III, Spijkenisse municipality, spring and summer 1980, interim-rapport over de verkenningen en opgravingen van de steentijdnederzettingen in de deelplannen akkers-13 en -14 en vriesland-1 en -2., Leiden University, URL <https://hdl.handle.net/1887/2794>, title translated with DeepL, Language: Dutch, Title (in original language): De opgraving Hekelingen III, gemeente Spijkenisse, voorjaar en zomer 1980, 1980.
- Lowdon, J. A. and Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates VII, Radiocarbon, 10, 207–245, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200010894>, 1968.

- Lowdon, J. A. and Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates IX, *Radiocarbon*, 12, 46–86, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200036213>, 1970.
- Lowdon, J. A. and Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XIII, Paper 73-7, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/103332>, Language: English with French abstract, 1973.
- Lowdon, J. A. and Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XV, Paper 75-7, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/102887>, 1975.
- Lowdon, J. A. and Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XIX, Paper 79-7, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/102159>, Language: English with French abstract, 1979.
- Lowdon, J. A. and Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XX, Paper 80-7, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/119073>, 1980.
- Lowdon, J. A., Fyles, J. G., and Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates VI, *Radiocarbon*, 9, 156–197, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200000503>, 1967.
- Lowdon, J. A., Robertson, I. M., and Blake, W.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XI, *Radiocarbon*, 13, 255–324, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200008456>, 1971.
- Lubinski, D. J.: Latest Pleistocene and Holocene paleoenvironments of the Franz Josef Land Region, Northern Barents Sea, Arctic Russia, Ph.D. thesis, Department of Geological Sciences, University of Colorado-Boulder, Boulder, USA, 1998.
- Ludwig, G., Müller, H., and Streif, H.: Recent data on Holocene sea level rise in the German Bight area, *Geologisches Jahrbuch D*, 33, 3–22, title translated by DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Neuere Daten zum holozänen Meeresspiegelanstieg im Bereich der Deutschen Bucht, 1979.
- Ludwig, G., Müller, H., and Streif, H.: New Dates on Holocene Sea-Level Changes in the German Bight, in: *Holocene Marine Sedimentation in the North Sea Basin*, edited by Nio, S.-D., Shüttenhelm, R. T. E., and Van Weering, T. C. E., chap. 15, pp. 211–219, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444303759.ch15>, 1981.
- Lunkka, J.-P., Putkinen, N., and Miettinen, A.: Shoreline displacement in the Belomorsk area, NW Russia during the Younger Dryas Stadial, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 37, 26–37, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2012.01.023>, 2012.
- Lõugas, L. and Tomek, T.: Marginal effect at the coastal area of Tallinn Bay: The marine, terrestrial and avian fauna as a source of subsistence during the Late Neolithic, *Muinasaja teadus*, 19, 463–485, Language: English with Estonian summary, 2013.
- MacPherson, J. B.: Delayed deglaciation by downwasting of the northeast Avalon Peninsula, Newfoundland: an application of the early postglacial pollen record, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 50, 201–220, <https://doi.org/10.7202/033089ar>, Language: English with French and German abstracts, 1996.
- Maemoku, H., Miura, H., Saigusa, S., and Moriwaki, K.: Stratigraphy of the late Quaternary raised beach deposits in the northern part of Langhovde, Lützow-Holm Bay, East Antarctica, *Proceedings of the NIPR Symposium on Antarctic Geoscience*, 10, 178–186, <https://doi.org/10.15094/00002853>, 1997.

- Makarov, A. S.: Laptev Sea level fluctuations as a factor of the Lena River Delta formation in Holocene, Ph.D. thesis, Saint-Petersburg State University, Faculty of Geography, St. Petersburg, Russia, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Макаров, Александр Сергеевич, Title (in original language): Колебания уровня моря Лаптевых как фактор формирования дельты р. Лена в голоцене, 2009.
- Makaske, B., Van Smeerdijk, D., Peeters, H., Mulder, J., and Spek, T.: Relative water-level rise in the Flevo lagoon (The Netherlands), 5300-2000 cal. yr BC: an evaluation of new and existing basal peat time-depth data, in: *De Holocene laagveenontwikkeling in de randzone van de Nederlandse kustvlakte (Noordoostpolder)*, vol. 82, pp. 115–131, Cambridge University Press, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0016774600020680>, 2003.
- Makeev, V. M.: Fluctuations of the Gulf of Ob Level in the Holocene, in: *Geographical and Glaciological Investigations in Polar Regions*, pp. 137–146, Gidrometeoizdat, Leningrad, Soviet Union, (In Russian), Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Makeev, V. M., Title (in original language): Колебания уровня Обской губы в голоцене, *Journal/book (in original language): Географические и гляциологические исследования в полярных странах*, 1988.
- Makeev, V. M., Bolshiyarov, D. Y., and N., M. O.: Morphology of the estuarine part of the Ob River valley and the history of the modern delta formation, in: *Geographical and Glaciological Investigations in Polar Regions*, pp. 125–137, Gidrometeoizdat, Leningrad, Soviet Union, title translated by DeepL, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Makeev, V. M., Большиаров, Д.Ю., Медкова, О. Н., Савин, В. Б., and Федоров, Б. Г., Title (in original language): Особенности морфологии долины устьевого участка р. Оби и история формирования современной дельты, *Journal/book (in original language): Географические и гляциологические исследования в полярных странах*, 1988.
- Mallinson, D., Riggs, S., Thielier, E. R., Culver, S., Farrell, K., Foster, D. S., Corbett, D. R., Horton, B., and Wehmiller, J. F.: Late Neogene and Quaternary evolution of the northern Albemarle Embayment (mid-Atlantic continental margin, USA), *Marine Geology*, 217, 97–117, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2005.02.030>, 2005.
- Mallinson, D., Burdette, K., Mahan, S., and Brook, G.: Optically stimulated luminescence age controls on late Pleistocene and Holocene coastal lithosomes, North Carolina, USA, *Quaternary Research*, 69, 97–109, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yqres.2007.10.002>, 2008.
- Mangerud, J., Kaufman, D., Hansen, J., and Inge Svendsen, J.: Ice-free conditions in Novaya Zemlya 35 000-30 000 cal years BP, as indicated by radiocarbon ages and amino acid racemization evidence from marine molluscs, *Polar Research*, 27, 187–208, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-8369.2008.00064.x>, 2008.
- Mann, T., Rovere, A., Schöne, T., Klicpera, A., Stocchi, P., Lukman, M., and Westphal, H.: The magnitude of a mid-Holocene sea-level highstand in the Strait of Makassar, *Geomorphology*, 257, 155–163, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2015.12.023>, 2016.
- Mann, T., Bender, M., Lorscheid, T., Stocchi, P., Vacchi, M., Switzer, A. D., and Rovere, A.: Holocene sea levels in Southeast Asia, Maldives, India and Sri Lanka: The SEAMIS database, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 219, 112–125, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2019.07.007>, 2019.
- Martindale, A., Morlan, R., Betts, M., Blake, M., Gajewski, K., Chaput, M., Mason, A., and Vermeersch, P.: Canadian archaeological radiocarbon database (CARD 2.1), URL <https://www.canadianarchaeology.ca/>, accessed June 10, 2020, 2020.

- Martinez-Macchiavello, J. C., Tatur, A., Servant-Vildary, S., and Del Valle, R.: Holocene environmental change in a marine-estuarine-lacustrine sediment sequence, King George Island, South Shetland Islands, *Antarctic Science*, 8, 313–322, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S095410209600048X>, 1996.
- Marx, P. R.: A dynamic model for an estuarine transgression based on facies variants in the nearshore of western Delaware Bay, Master's thesis, University of Delaware, Newark, Delaware, United States, 1981.
- Matthews, B.: Radiocarbon dated postglacial land uplift in Northern Ungava, Canada, *Nature*, 211, 1164–1166, <https://doi.org/10.1038/2111164b0>, 1966.
- Matthews, B.: Late Quaternary Land Emergence in Northern Ungava, Quebec, *Arctic*, 20, 176–202, <https://doi.org/10.14430/arctic3293>, Language: English with abstracts in French and Russian, 1967.
- McAndrews, J. H., Riley, J. L., and Davis, A. M.: Vegetation history of the Hudson Bay Lowland: a postglacial pollen diagram from the Sutton Ridge, *Le Naturaliste Canadien*, 109, 597–608, URL <https://www.provancher.org/le-naturaliste-canadien/#1475521633474-8127baf5-e84a>, Language: English with French abstract, 1982.
- McCallum, K. J. and Wittenberg, J.: University of Saskatchewan radiocarbon dates IV, *Radiocarbon*, 7, 229–235, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200037231>, 1965.
- McGovern, T. H., Amorosi, T., Perdikaris, S., and Woollett, J.: Vertebrate Zooarchaeology of Sandnes V51: Economic Change at a Chieftain's Farm in West Greenland, *Arctic Anthropology*, 33, 94–121, URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40316414>, 1996.
- McNeely, R.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XXXIII, Current Research 2001, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/213319>, Language: English with French abstract, 2002.
- McNeely, R.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XXXIV, Current Research 2005, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/221464>, Language: English with French abstract, 2005.
- McNeely, R.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XXXV, Current Research 2006-G, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/223025>, 2006.
- McNeely, R. and Atkinson, D. E.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XXXII, Current Research 1995-G, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/207598>, 1995.
- McNeely, R. and Brennan, J.: Geological Survey of Canada Revised Shell Dates, Open File 5019, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/221215>, Language: English with French abstract, 2005.
- McNeely, R. and Jorgensen, P. K.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XXX, Paper 90-7, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/183915>, Language: English with French abstract, 1992.
- McNeely, R. and Jorgensen, P. K.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XXXI, Paper 91-7, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/193326>, Language: English with French abstract, 1993.
- McNeely, R. and McCuaig, S.: Geological Survey of Canada radiocarbon dates XXIX, Paper 89-7, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/132453>, Language: English with French abstract, 1991.

- Meier, D.: Landscape development and settlement history of the Eiderstedt and Dithmarsch coastal areas as sub-regions of the North Sea coastal region, *Universitätsforschungen zur prähistorischen Archäologie* 79, Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Landschaftsentwicklung und Siedlungsgeschichte des Eiderstedter und Dithmarscher Küstengebietes als Teilregionen des Nordseeküstenraumes, 2001a.
- Meier, D.: Süderbusenwurth – a dwelling place of the Roman imperial period, *Die Heimat*, 108, 38–46, URL https://pdf.sub.uni-hamburg.de/kitodo/PPN846060221_0108, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Süderbusenwurth – eine Wurt der römischen Kaiserzeit, 2001b.
- Meltzner, A. J., Switzer, A. D., Horton, B. P., Ashe, E., Qiu, Q., Hill, D. F., Bradley, S. L., Kopp, R. E., Hill, E. M., Majewski, J. M., Natawidjaja, D. H., and Suwargadi, B. W.: Half-metre sea-level fluctuations on centennial timescales from mid-Holocene corals of Southeast Asia, *Nature Communications*, 8, 1–16, <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms14387>, 2017.
- Menke, B.: Upper Pleistocene Stratigraphy and Environment (Western Schleswig-Holstein, Germany), *E&G Quaternary Science Journal*, 27, 53–68, <https://doi.org/10.3285/eg.27.1.05>, Language: German with English abstract, Title (in original language): Neue Ergebnisse zur Stratigraphie und Landschaftsentwicklung im Jungpleistozän Westholsteins, 1976.
- Menke, B.: The Holocene North Sea transgression in the coastal area of the southeastern German Bight, *Offa - Bücher Neue Folge*, 66, 117–137, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Die holozäne Nordseetransgression im Küstenbereich der südöstlichen deutschen Bucht, 1988.
- Menke, B.: Palynological investigation of the vibrocore Gauss 1987/5 from the southern North Sea, in: *Deutsche Beiträge zur Quartärforschung in der südlichen Nordsee*, edited by Streif, H., vol. 146 of *Geologisches Jahrbuch Reihe A*, pp. 177–182, BGR, title translated by DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Palynologische Untersuchung des Vibrokerns Gauss 1987/5 aus der südlichen Nordsee, 1996.
- Meyer, D. A.: Pre-Dorset settlements at the Seahorse Gully site, Master's thesis, University of Manitoba, URL <http://hdl.handle.net/1993/8669>, 1970.
- Miettinen, A., Eronen, M., and Hyvärinen, H.: Land uplift and relative sea-level changes in the Loviisa area, southeastern Finland, during the last 8000 years, *Posiva Report 99–28*, Department of Geology, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland, URL <https://researchportal.helsinki.fi/en/publications/land-uplift-and-relative-sea-level-changes-in-the-loviisa-area-so>, 1999.
- Miettinen, A., Savelieva, L., Subetto, D. A., Dzhinoridze, R., Arslanov, K., and Hyvärinen, H.: Palaeoenvironment of the Karelian Isthmus, the easternmost part of the Gulf of Finland, during the Litorina Sea stage of the Baltic Sea history, *Boreas*, 36, 441–458, <https://doi.org/10.1080/03009480701259284>, 2007.
- Miettinen, A. I.: Relative sea level changes in the eastern part of the Gulf of Finland during the last 8000 years, *Annales academiae scientiarum fennicae, geologica-geographica*, University of Helsinki, Finland, volume 162, Language: English, 2002.
- Miller, A. A. L., Mudie, P. J., and Scott, D. B.: Holocene history of Bedford Basin, Nova Scotia: foraminifera, dinoflagellate, and pollen records, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 19, 2342–2367, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e82-205>, Language: English with French abstract, 1982.

- Miller, K. G., Sugarman, P. J., Browning, J. V., Horton, B. P., Stanley, A., Kahn, A., Uptegrove, J., and Aucott, M.: Sea-level rise in New Jersey over the past 5000 years: Implications to anthropogenic changes, *Global and Planetary Change*, 66, 10–18, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2008.03.008>, quaternary sea-level changes : Records and Processes, 2009.
- Miller, K. R. and Livingstone, D. A.: Late-Holocene changes in sea level and environment on eastern Cape Breton Island, Nova Scotia, Canada, *The Holocene*, 3, 211–219, <https://doi.org/10.1177/095968369300300303>, 1993.
- Miller, R. F.: New records of postglacial walrus and a review of Quaternary marine mammals in New Brunswick, *Atlantic Geology*, 26, 97–107, <https://doi.org/10.4138/1695>, Language: English with French abstract, 1990.
- Miotk-Szpiganowicz, G.: Stop 4 - Coast of the Vistula Lagoon (Przebrno). Peatbogs and fossil soils of the Vistula Spit, in: *The 13th Colloquium on Baltic Sea Marine Geology–Abstract Volume & Field Trip Guidebook.*, pp. 125–129, Polish Geological Institute–National Research Institute, Warsaw, URL <https://konferencje.pgi.gov.pl/en/baltic-home/>, 2016.
- Miotk-Szpiganowicz, G. and Uścinowicz, S.: Stand 4. Development of coastal peatlands of the Vistula Lagoon, in: *VI Polska Konferencja Paleobotaniki Czwartorzędu “Osady morskie. lagunowe i torfowisk nadbrzeżnych jako źródło informacji o paleośrodowiskach i klimacie”*, pp. 106–121, PIG-PIB, Warszawa, title translated by DeepL, Language: Polish, Title (in original language): Stanowisko 4. Rozwój torfowisk nadbrzeżnych Zalewu Wiślanego, 2013.
- Miotk-Szpiganowicz, G., Sz, U., Przedziecki, P., and Jegliński, W.: Reconstruction of the paleo-land scapes of the southern Baltic, in: *MACHU (Managing Cultural Heritage Underwater)*, edited by Manders, M. and Oosting, R., 3, pp. 80–84, Educom Publisher BV, Rotterdam, URL <https://www.cultureelerfgoed.nl/publicaties/publicaties/2010/01/01/machu-reports-2007-2008-2009>, 2009.
- Mityaev M. V., Korsun S. A., S. P. P. M. G. G.: Ancient coastlines of East Kildin, (*Doklady of the Russian Academy of Sciences*), 423, 546–550, <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1028334X08090298>, Language: Russian, with English translation, Authors (in original language): МИТЯЕВ, М. В., КОПСУН, С. А., СТРЕЛКОВ, П. П., and МАТИШОВ, Г. Г., Title (in original language): Древние береговые линии Восточного Кильдина, *Journal/book* (in original language): Доклады Академии наук, 2008.
- Miura, H., Maemoku, H., Igarashi, A., and Moriwaki, K.: Late Quaternary Raised Beach Deposits and Radiocarbon Dates of Marine Fossils Around Lützow-Holm Bay, *Special map series of National Institute of Polar Research 6*, National Institute of Polar Research, Tokyo, Japan, report, 46 p., 1 map, 1998.
- Mixon, R. B., Szabo, B. J., and Owens, J. P.: Uranium-series dating of mollusks and corals, and age of Pleistocene deposits, Chesapeake Bay area, Virginia and Maryland, *Professional Paper 1067- E*, United States Geological Survey, <https://doi.org/10.3133/pp1067E>, 1982.
- Moore, C.: Geoarchaeological investigations of stratified Holocene aeolian deposits along the Tar River in North Carolina, Ph.D. thesis, Coastal Resources Management, East Carolina University, Greenville, NC, United States, 2009.
- Morlan, R., McNeely, R., and Nielsen, E.: Manitoba radiocarbon dates, *Open File Report OF2000-1*, Manitoba Industry, Trade and Mines, Geological Survey, 2000.

- Morozov, D.: Paleogeocological reconstructions of lake systems in the southern Fennoscandia, Ph.D. thesis, St. Petersburg, URL https://irbis.gnpbu.ru/Aref_2014/Morozov_D_A_2014.pdf, title translated with DeepL, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Морозов, Дмитрий Александрович, Title (in original language): Палеогеоэкологические реконструкции озерных систем южного обрамления Фенноскандии, 2014.
- Morrison, B. V. R.: Mid to late Holocene sea level history and coastal evolution in Tasmania, Ph.D. thesis, University of Tasmania, Tasmania, Australia, <https://doi.org/10.25959/100.00031715>, 2019.
- Morrison, D.: Radiocarbon dating Thule culture, *Arctic Anthropology*, 26, 48–77, URL <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40316184>, 1989.
- Mortlock, R. A., Fairbanks, R. G., Chiu, T., and Rubenstone, J.: $^{230}\text{Th}/^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}$ and $^{231}\text{Pa}/^{235}\text{U}$ ages from a single fossil coral fragment by multi-collector magnetic-sector inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry, *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta*, 69, 649–657, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gca.2004.06.033>, 2005.
- Mortlock, R. A., Abdul, N. A., Wright, J. D., and Fairbanks, R. G.: Reply to comment by E. Bard et al. on “Younger Dryas sea level and meltwater pulse 1B recorded in Barbados reef crest coral *Acropora palmata*” by N. A. Abdul et al., *Paleoceanography*, 31, 1609–1616, <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016PA003047>, 2016.
- Murniece, S., Kalnina, L., Berzin, V., and Grasis, N.: Environmental change and prehistoric human activity in Western Kurzeme, Latvia, in: Environmental and cultural history of the eastern Baltic region, edited by Miller, U., Hackens, T., Lang, V., Raukas, A., and Hicks, S., vol. 57 of *Journal of the European network of scientific and technical cooperation for cultural heritage*, pp. 35–69, PACT, 1999.
- Murray-Wallace, C., Belperio, A., Gostin, V., and Cann, J.: Amino acid racemization and radiocarbon dating of interstadial marine strata (oxygen isotope stage 3), Gulf St. Vincent, South Australia, *Marine Geology*, 110, 83–92, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(93\)90107-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(93)90107-7), 1993.
- Murray-Wallace, C., Beu, A. G., Kendrick, G. W., Brown, L. J., Belperio, A. P., and Sherwood, J. E.: Palaeoclimatic implications of the occurrence of the arcoid bivalve *Anadara trapezia* (Deshayes) in the Quaternary of Australasia, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 19, 559–590, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(99\)00015-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(99)00015-3), 2000.
- Murray-Wallace, C. V. and Goede, A.: Aminostratigraphy and electron spin resonance dating of Quaternary coastal neotectonism in Tasmania and the Bass Strait islands, *Australian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 42, 51–67, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08120099508728178>, 1995.
- Muru, M., Rosentau, A., Kriiska, A., Lõugas, L., Kadakas, U., Vassiljev, J., Saarse, L., Aunap, R., Küttim, L., Puusepp, L., and Kihno, K.: Sea level changes and Neolithic hunter-fisher-gatherers in the centre of Tallinn, southern coast of the Gulf of Finland, Baltic Sea, *The Holocene*, 27, 917–928, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683616678462>, 2017.
- Möller, P., Larsen, N. K., Kjær, K. H., Funder, S., Schomacker, A., Linge, H., and Fabel, D.: Early to middle Holocene valley glaciations on northernmost Greenland, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 29, 3379–3398, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2010.06.044>, aPEX: Arctic Palaeoclimate and its Extremes, 2010.
- Mörner, N.-A.: The Late Quaternary history of the Kattegatt Sea and the Swedish West Coast: deglaciation, shorelevel displacement, chronology, isostasy and eustasy, Serie C 640, Sveriges geologiska undersökning, Stockholm, Sweden, URL <https://apps.sgu.se/geolagret/>

- GetMetaDataById?id=md-bdbeb412-cfe7-4f6b-8649-4420b4c3602a, Language: English with Russian summary, 1969.
- Nash, R. J.: Dorset culture in northeastern Manitoba, Canada, *Arctic Anthropology*, 9, 10–16, URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40315769>, 1972.
- Naumann, M. and Lampe, R.: The evolution of a southern Baltic coastal barrier system, deduced from geostatistical based volume calculations and relative sea level rise (Darss-Zingst-Hiddensee area/NE Germany), *Bericht der Römisch-Germanischen Kommission*, 92, 297–324, 2011.
- Newman, W. S. and Rusnak, G. A.: Holocene Submergence of the Eastern Shore of Virginia, *Science*, 148, 1464–1466, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.148.3676.1464>, 1965.
- Newman, W. S., Cinquemani, L. J., Pardi, R., and Marcus, L. F.: Holocene delevelling of the United States' East Coast, in: *Earth Rheology, Isostasy and Eustasy*, edited by Morner, N., pp. 449–463, Wiley, New York, United States, 1980.
- Nicholas, W. A., Nichol, S. L., Howard, F. J. F., Picard, K., Dulfer, H., Radke, L. C., Carroll, A. G., Tran, M., and Siwabessy, P. J. W.: Pockmark development in the Petrel Sub-basin, Timor Sea, Northern Australia: Seabed habitat mapping in support of CO2 storage assessments, *Continental Shelf Research*, 34, 129–142, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csr.2014.02.016>, *geoscience and Habitat Mapping for Marine Renewable Energy*, 2014.
- Nicks, L. P.: The study of the glacial stratigraphy and sedimentation of the Sheldon Point moraine, Saint John, New Brunswick, Open File Report 91-12, New Brunswick Department of Natural Resources and Energy, Mineral Resources, 1991.
- Nielsen, B. H.: Hedegårdkalotten. Det sidste vidne til livet før syndfloden, in: *Vesthimmerlands Museums Årbog 2010*, pp. 19–26, Vesthimmerlands Museum, 2010.
- Nielsen, P. E., Jensen, J. B., Binderup, M., Lomholt, S., and Kuijpers, A.: Marine aggregates in the Danish sector of the Baltic Sea: Geological setting, exploitation potential and environmental assessment, in: *Mineral Resources of the Baltic Sea*, edited by Harff, J., Emelyanov, E. M., Schmidt-Thomé, M., and Spiridonov, M., *Zeitschrift für angewandte Geologie*, pp. 87–109, Schweizerbart, Stuttgart, Germany, URL http://www.schweizerbart.de/publications/detail/isbn/9783510959280/Zeitschrift_f_Angew_Geologie_Sonderheft, 2004.
- Nielsen, S. K.: The studies at Aggersborg, in: *Kongens Borge: Rapport over Undersøgelserne 2007–2010*, edited by Dobat, A., Aarhus Universitetsforlag, Aarhus, title translated with DeepL, Language: Danish, Title (in original language): *Undersøgelserne ved Aggersborg*, 2013.
- Nikitina, D. L., Pizzuto, J. E., Schwimmer, R. A., and Ramsey, K. W.: An updated Holocene sea-level curve for the Delaware coast, *Marine Geology*, 171, 7–20, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227\(00\)00104-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227(00)00104-3), 2000.
- Nirgi, T., Rosentau, A., Habicht, H.-L., Hang, T., Jonuks, T., Jõelett, A., Kihno, K., Kriiska, A., Mustasaar, M., Risberg, J., Suuroja, S., Talviste, P., and Tõnisson, H.: Holocene relative shore-level changes and Stone Age palaeogeography of the Pärnu Bay area, eastern Baltic Sea, *The Holocene*, 30, 37–52, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683619865603>, 2020.
- Noakes, J. E. and Brandau, B. L.: University of Georgia Radiocarbon Dates I, *Radiocarbon*, 13, 468–474, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200008572>, 1971.
- Noakes, J. E., Kim, S. M., and Akers, L. K.: Oak Ridge Institute of Nuclear Studies Radiocarbon Dates I, *Radiocarbon*, 9, 309–315, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S003382220000059X>, 1967.

- Noakes, J. E., Kim, S. M., and Fischer, F.: Oak Ridge Associated Universities Radiocarbon Dates II, *Radiocarbon*, 10, 346–349, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200010948>, 1968.
- Nott, J.: Late Pleistocene and Holocene Sea-Level Highstands in Northern Australia, *Journal of Coastal Research*, 12, 907–910, URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4298541>, 1996.
- Nydal, R.: A critical review of radiocarbon dating of a Norse settlement at L'Anse Aux Meadows, Newfoundland Canada, *Radiocarbon*, 31, 976–985, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200012613>, 1989.
- Nydick, K. R., Bidwell, A. B., Thomas, E., and Varekamp, J. C.: A sea-level rise curve from Guilford, Connecticut, USA, *Marine Geology*, 124, 137–159, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(95\)00037-Y](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(95)00037-Y), coastal Evolution in the Quarternary: IGCP Project 274, 1995.
- Nylander, C.-E.: Vegetation history and vegetation in southern Bräkne-Hoby parish, *Meddelanden från avdelningen för ekologisk botanik, Lunds Universitet*, title translated by DeepL, Language: Swedish, Title (in original language): Vegetationshistoria och vegetation i södra Bräkne-Hoby socken, 1969.
- Occhietti, S., Chartier, H., Hillaire-Marcel, C., Cournoyer, M., Cumbaa, S., and Harington, R.: Champlain Sea Paleoenvironments in the Québec City area, 11 300-9750 BP: the Saint-Nicolas site (Québec), *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 55, 23–46, <https://doi.org/10.7202/005660ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): Paléoenvironnements de la mer de Champlain dans la région de Québec, entre 11 300 et 9750 BP: le site de Saint-Nicolas, 2001.
- Ogden, J. G. and Hart, W. C.: Dalhousie University natural radiocarbon measurements I, *Radiocarbon*, 18, 43–49, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200002356>, 1976.
- Ohlenbusch, R.: Post-glacial sequence stratigraphy and sedimentary development of the continental shelf off Townsville, central Great Barrier Reef province, Unpublished Honours Thesis, James Cook University, Townsville, Queensland, Australia, 1991.
- Oldale, R. N. and O'Hara, C. J.: New radiocarbon dates from the inner Continental Shelf off south-eastern Massachusetts and a local sea-level-rise curve for the past 12,000 yr, *Geology*, 8, 102–106, [https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613\(1980\)8<102:NRDFTI>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613(1980)8<102:NRDFTI>2.0.CO;2), 1980.
- Oldale, R. N., Colman, S. M., and Jones, G. A.: Radiocarbon ages from two submerged strandline features in the western Gulf of Maine and a sea-level curve for the northeastern Massachusetts coastal region, *Quaternary Research*, 40, 38–45, <https://doi.org/10.1006/qres.1993.1054>, 1993.
- Olson, E. A. and Broecker, W. S.: Lamont natural radiocarbon measurements VII, *Radiocarbon*, 3, 141–175, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200020919>, 1961.
- Omura, A.: Geologic history of the Kikai Island, Central Ryukyus, Japan : Summary of uranium-series dating of fossil corals from the Riukiu Limestone, *The Memoirs of the Geological Society of Japan*, 29, 253–268, URL <http://ci.nii.ac.jp/naid/110003025267>, Language: Japanese with English abstract, Authors (in original language): 大村, 明雄, Title (in original language): 中部琉球喜界島の地史: 琉球石灰岩産サンゴ化石のウラン系列年代測定のまとめとして, Journal/book (in original language): 地質学論集, 1988.
- Omura, A. and Konishi, K.: Evaluation of apparent ionium ages of some hermatypic corals, *The Journal of the Geological Society of Japan*, 76, 389–397, <https://doi.org/10.5575/geosoc.76.389>, english Title:, Language: Japanese with English abstract, Authors (in original language): 大村, 明雄 and 小西, 健二, Title (in original language): 化石サンゴの示す見掛けのイオニウム年令の評価, Journal/book (in original language): 地質学雑誌, 1970.

- Omura, A., Tsuji, Y., Ohmura, K., and Sakuramoto, Y.: New data on uranium-series ages of hermatypic corals from the Pleistocene limestone on Kikai, Ryukyu Islands, Transactions and proceedings of the Paleontological Society of Japan. New series, 1985, 196–205, https://doi.org/10.14825/prpsj1951.1985.139_196, 1985.
- Omura, A., Sasaki, K., Terao, D., and Murakami, K.: A chronological and sedimentary study on the Pleistocene Series in Kikai Island, Central Ryukyus, Southwestern Japan, The Quaternary Research, 39, 55–68, <https://doi.org/10.4116/jaqua.39.55>, english Title: A Chronological and Sedimentary Study on the Pleistocene Series in Kikai Island, Central Ryukyus, Southwestern Japan, Language: Japanese with English abstract, Authors (in original language): 大村, 明雄 and 佐々木, 圭一 and 寺尾大介 and 村上 和男, Title (in original language): 喜界島の更新世堆積物とそのウラン系列年代について, Journal/book (in original language): 第四紀研究, 2000.
- Orru, M., Širokova, M., and Veldre, M.: Estonian peat resources, Tech. rep., Eesti Geoloogiakeskus, Tallinn, Language: Estonian, Title (in original language): Eesti turbavarud, 1992.
- Painchaud, A., Dubois, J., and Gwyn, Q.: Deglaciation and Emergence of the Western Part of Anticosti Island, Gulf of St. Lawrence, Québec, Géographie physique et Quaternaire, 38, 93–111, <https://doi.org/10.7202/032545ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): Déglaciation et émergence des terres de l'ouest de l'île d'Anticosti, golfe du Saint-Laurent, Québec, 1984.
- Panayotou, K.: Geomorphology of the Minnamurra River estuary, southeastern Australia: evolution and management of a barrier estuary, Ph.D. thesis, University of Wollongong, Wollongong, Australia, URL <http://ro.uow.edu.au/theses/394>, 2004.
- Pardi, R. and Newman, E. R.: Queens College radiocarbon measurements III, Radiocarbon, 22, 1073–1083, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200011577>, 1980.
- Pardi, R. R., Tomecek, L., and Newman, W. S.: Queens College radiocarbon measurements IV, Radiocarbon, 26, 412–430, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200006779>, 1984.
- Parent, M. and Occhietti, S.: Late Wisconsinan Deglaciation and Champlain Sea Invasion in the St. Lawrence Valley, Québec, Géographie physique et Quaternaire, 42, 215–246, <https://doi.org/10.7202/032734ar>, 1988.
- Parham, P. R., Riggs, S. R., Culver, S. J., Mallinson, D. J., Rink, W. J., and Burdette, K.: Quaternary coastal lithofacies, sequence development and stratigraphy in a passive margin setting, North Carolina and Virginia, USA, Sedimentology, 60, 503–547, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3091.2012.01349.x>, 2013.
- Parham, P. R., Saito, Y., Sapon, N., Suriadi, R., and Mohtar, N. A.: Evidence for ca. 7-ka maximum Holocene transgression on the Peninsular Malaysia east coast, Journal of Quaternary Science, 29, 414–422, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.2714>, 2014.
- Park, S.-C., Yoo, D.-G., Lee, C.-W., and Lee, E.-I.: Last glacial sea-level changes and paleogeography of the Korea (Tsushima) Strait, Geo-Marine Letters, 20, 64–71, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s003670000039>, 2000.
- Partain, B. R. and Hopley, D.: Morphology and development of the Cape Tribulation fringing reefs, Great Barrier Reef, Australia, Technical memorandum GBRMPA-TM-21, Great Barrier Reef Marine Park Authority, URL <http://hdl.handle.net/11017/210>, 1989.

- Pedersen, J. B. T., Kroon, A., and Jakobsen, B. H.: Holocene sea-level reconstruction in the Young Sound region, Northeast Greenland, *Journal of Quaternary Science*, 26, 219–226, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.1449>, 2011.
- Peltier, W. and Fairbanks, R. G.: Global glacial ice volume and Last Glacial Maximum duration from an extended Barbados sea level record, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 25, 3322–3337, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2006.04.010>, 2006.
- Pendea, I. F., Costopoulos, A., Nielsen, C., and Chmura, G. L.: A new shoreline displacement model for the last 7 ka from eastern James Bay, Canada, *Quaternary Research*, 73, 474–484, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yqres.2010.02.001>, 2010.
- Persson, C.: Shore displacement during Ancylus time in the Rejmyra area south central Sweden, C 755, Sveriges geologiska undersökning, URL <https://apps.sgu.se/geolagret/GetMetaDataById?id=md-68a824c2-3624-47b7-bc2b-4903a4e63918>, 1979.
- Persson, G.: Postglacial transgressions in Bohuslän, Southwestern Sweden, C 684, Sveriges geologiska undersökning, URL <https://apps.sgu.se/geolagret/GetMetaDataById?id=md-4f7fb93d-71d1-49d9-a92c-2ad62235e2f2>, 1973.
- Petersen, K. S.: On the postglacial marine evolution and level conditions of the Limfjord, illuminated by mollusc fauna and C-14 dating, in: *Danmarks Geologiske Undersøgelse, Årbog 1975*, pp. 75–103, Geological Survey of Denmark, Language: Danish, Title (in original language): Om Limfjordens postglaciale marine udvikling og niveauforhold, belyst ved molluskfaunen og C-14 dateringer, 1975.
- Petersen, K. S.: The postglacial transgression and mollusc fauna in the Tude Å area, Great Belt, Denmark, in: *Danmarks Geologiske Undersøgelse, Årbog for 1977*, pp. 39–52, Geological Survey of Denmark, title translated with DeepL, Language: Danish, Title (in original language): Den postglaciale transgression og molluskfaunaen i Tude Å-området, Store Bælt, Danmark, 1978.
- Petersen, K. S.: The Holocene Marine Transgression and its molluscan fauna in the Skagerrak–Limfjord Region, Denmark, in: *Holocene Marine Sedimentation in the North Sea Basin*, edited by Nio, S.-D., Shüttenhelm, R. T. E., and Van Weering, T., vol. 5 of *Special Publications International Association of Sedimentologists*, pp. 497–503, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444303759.ch34>, 1981.
- Petersen, K. S.: Late Weichselian and Holocene Marine Transgressions in Northern Jutland, Denmark, *E&G Quaternary Science Journal*, 35, 71–78, <https://doi.org/10.3285/eg.35.1.11>, Language: English with German abstract, 1985.
- Petersen, K. S.: Holocene coastal and faunal development of the Skagen odde, Northern Jutland, Denmark, *Quaternary International*, 9, 53–60, [https://doi.org/10.1016/1040-6182\(91\)90063-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/1040-6182(91)90063-T), 1991.
- Petersen, K. S.: Environmental changes recorded in the Holocene molluscan faunas from Djursland, Denmark, in: *Proceedings of the symposium ‘Molluscan Palaeontology’: 11th International Malacological Congress, Siena (Italy) 30th August - 5th September 1992*, edited by Janssen, A. W. and Janssen, R., no. 2 in *Scripta Geologica Special Issue*, pp. 359–369, URL <https://repository.naturalis.nl/pub/317346>, 1993.
- Petersen, K. S.: (The Holocene marine environmental evolution of the Limfjord bars and adjacent parts of the North Sea - Jydske Reef, illuminated by the mollusc fauna, in: *Limfjordsprojektet*, vol. 8, pp. 303–323, Sekretariatet for Limfjordsprojektet, title translated using DeepL, Language: Danish, Title (in original language): Den Holocene marine miljøudvikling ved Limfjordstangerne og tilgrænsende dele af Nordsøen - Jydske Rev, belyst ved molluskfaunaen, 1998.

- Petersen, K. S. and Rasmussen, K. L.: The impact of radiocarbon datings on natural historical sciences in Denmark: especially paleozoological and shore-line datings, PACT, pp. 117–130, 1995.
- Petersen, K. S. and von Platen-Hallermund, F. I.: Topography: The origin of the landscape in Thy and Vester Hanherred, processes and sediments, in: Bronze Age Settlement and Land-Use in Thy, Northwest Denmark, edited by Bech, J.-H., Eriksen, B. V., and Kristiansen, K., vol. 102 of *Jysk Arkæologisk Selskabs Skrifter*, chap. 7, pp. 185–192, Aarhus University Press, 2018.
- Pico, T., Mitrovica, J., Ferrier, K., and Braun, J.: Global ice volume during MIS 3 inferred from a sea-level analysis of sedimentary core records in the Yellow River Delta, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 152, 72–79, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2016.09.012>, 2016.
- Pico, T., Creveling, J. R., and Mitrovica, J. X.: Sea-level records from the US mid-Atlantic constrain Laurentide Ice Sheet extent during Marine Isotope Stage 3, *Nature Communications*, 8, 1–6, <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms15612>, 2017.
- Pienitz, R., Lortie, G., and Allard, M.: Isolation of lacustrine basins and marine regression in the Kuu-jjuaq area, northern Québec, as inferred from diatom analysis, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 45, 155–174, <https://doi.org/10.7202/032858ar>, Language: English with French and German abstracts, 1991.
- Playford, P. E.: Guidebook to the geology of Rottneest Island, Geological Society of Australia, W A Division and the Geological Survey of Western Australia, Perth, Australia, URL <https://www.dmp.wa.gov.au/Geological-Survey/Geology-of-Rottneest-Island-16421.aspx>, 1988.
- Plumet, P.: Archaeology and glacio-isostatic rebound in the Poste-de-la-Baleine area, New Quebec, *La Revue de Géographie de Montréal*, 28, 443–447, title translated by DeepL, Language: French, Title (in original language): L'archéologie et le relèvement glacio-isostatique de la région de Poste-de-la-Baleine, Nouveau-Québec, 1974.
- Polyak, L., Gataullin, V., Okuneva, O., and Stelle, V.: New constraints on the limits of the Barents-Kara ice sheet during the Last Glacial Maximum based on borehole stratigraphy from the Pechora Sea, *Geology*, 28, 611–614, [https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613\(2000\)28<611:NCOTLO>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613(2000)28<611:NCOTLO>2.0.CO;2), 2000.
- Polyakova, Y. I. and Stein, R.: Holocene paleoenvironmental implications of diatom and organic carbon records from the southeastern Kara Sea (Siberian Margin), *Quaternary Research*, 62, 256–266, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yqres.2004.08.002>, 2004.
- Polyakova, Y. I., Bauch, H. A., and Klyuvitkina, T. S.: Early to middle Holocene changes in Laptev Sea water masses deduced from diatom and aquatic palynomorph assemblages, *Global and Planetary Change*, 48, 208–222, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2004.12.014>, 2005.
- Poska, A. and Veski, S.: Man and environment at 9500 BP. A palynological study of an Early-Mesolithic settlement site in south-west Estonia, in: *Acta Paleobotanica. Supplement 2. Proceedings of the fifth European palaeobotanical and palynological conference*, pp. 603–607, Polish Academy of Sciences, URL <http://bomax.botany.pl/pubs/#article-2103>, 1999.
- Preuss, H.: Holocene development of the North Sea coast in the area of the Eastern Weser marshes, *Geologische Jahrbuch A*, 53, 3–85, Language: German, Title (in original language): Die holozäne Entwicklung der Nordseeküste im Gebiet der östlichen Wesermarsch, 1979.
- Psuty, N. P.: Holocene sea level in New Jersey, *Physical Geography*, 7, 156–167, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02723646.1986.10642288>, 1986.

- Pujāte, A.: Traces of Environmental Change and Human Impact in the Sediments of Lakes Along the Coast of the Gulf of Riga, Ph.D. thesis, Latvijas Universitāte, Riga, Latvia, URL <https://dspace.lu.lv/dspace/handle/7/28353>, Language: Latvian, Title (in original language): Vides apstākļu izmaiņu un cilvēka darbības pēdas Rīgas līča piekrastes ezeru nogulumos, 2015.
- Punning, J. M., Ilves, E., Liiva, A., and Rinne, T.: Tartu Radiocarbon dates V, *Radiocarbon*, 13, 78–83, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200000874>, 1971.
- Punning, J. M., Kakum, T., and Rajamäe, R.: Tallinn Radiocarbon Dates I, *Radiocarbon*, 15, 586–591, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200009036>, 1973.
- Punning, J. M., Rajamäe, R., Ehrenpreis, M., and Sarv, L.: Tallinn radiocarbon dates IV, *Radiocarbon*, 19, 111–117, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200003386>, 1977.
- Pye, K. and Rhodes, E. G.: Holocene development of an episodic transgressive dune barrier, Ramsay Bay, North Queensland, Australia, *Marine Geology*, 64, 189–202, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(85\)90104-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(85)90104-5), 1985.
- Raab, A., Melles, M., Berger, G. W., Hagedorn, B., and Hubberten, H.-W.: Non-glacial paleoenvironments and the extent of Weichselian ice sheets on Severnaya Zemlya, Russian High Arctic, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 22, 2267–2283, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(03\)00139-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(03)00139-2), 2003.
- Rahbek, U. and Rasmussen, K. L.: Danish "archaeological" 14C dating, Copenhagen 1993, *Arkæologiske udgravninger i Danmark*, pp. 276–288, Language: Danish, Title (in original language): Danske arkæologiske 14C-dateringer, København 1993, 1994.
- Rampton, V. N., Gauthier, R. C., Thibault, J., and Seaman, A. A.: Quaternary geology of New Brunswick, Memoir 416, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/119730>, Language: English with French abstract, 1984.
- Ramsey, K. W. and Baxter, S. J.: Radiocarbon dates from Delaware: a compilation, Report of Investigations 54, Delaware Geological Survey, University of Delaware, Newark, Delaware, United States, URL <http://udspace.udel.edu/handle/19716/3170>, 1996.
- Randsalu, L.: Holocene relative sea-level changes in the Tasiusaq area, southern Greenland, with focus on the Ta1 and Ta3 basins, Master's thesis, Lund University, URL <http://lup.lub.lu.se/student-papers/record/1320376>, dissertations in Geology at Lund University, Language: English with Swedish abstract, 2008.
- Rasch, M.: A Compilation of Radiocarbon Dates from Disko Bugt, Central West Greenland, *Geografisk Tidsskrift - Danish Journal of Geography*, 97, 143–159, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00167223.1997.10649400>, 1997.
- Rasmussen, K. L.: Danish archaeological 14C-dates, Copenhagen 1991, *Arkæologiske udgravninger i Danmark*, pp. 233–251, title translated with DeepL, Language: Danish, Title (in original language): Danske arkæologiske 14C-dateringer, København 1991, 1992.
- Rasmussen, P.: Stavns fjords alder (Age of Stavns fjord), in: Stavns Fjord Et natur- og kulturhistorisk forskningsområde på Samsø, edited by Hansen, H. H. and Aaby, B., pp. 23–33, Carlsbergfondet og Nationalmuseet, København, Language: Danish, 1995.
- Raukas, A., Kimmel, K., and Rajamäe, R.: A new site of buried peat at Lõpe, SW Estonia, *Proceedings of the Estonian Academy of Sciences: Geology*, 44, 133–137, <https://doi.org/10.3176/geol.1995.2.06>, Language: English with abstracts in Estonian and Russian, 1995.

- Raukas, A., Moora, T., and Karukäpp, R.: The Development of the Baltic Sea and Stone Age Settlement in the Pärnu Area of Southwestern Estonia, in: Environmental and Cultural History of the Eastern Baltic Region, edited by Miller, U. and Hackens jt, T., vol. 57 of *PACT*, pp. 15–34, PACT, 1999.
- Read, J. F.: Carbonate Bank and Wave-Built Platform Sedimentation, Edel Province, Shark Bay, Western Australia 1, in: Evolution and Diagenesis of Quaternary Carbonate Sequences, Shark Bay, Western Australia, AAPG Special Volumes, American Association of Petroleum Geologists, <https://doi.org/10.1306/M22379C1>, 1974.
- Redfield, A. C.: Postglacial change in sea level in the western North Atlantic Ocean, *Science*, 157, 687–692, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.157.3789.687>, 1967.
- Redfield, A. C. and Rubin, M.: The age of salt marsh peat and its relation to recent changes in sea level at Barnstable, Massachusetts, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 48, 1728, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.48.10.1728>, 1962.
- Reimer, P. J., Austin, W. E. N., Bard, E., Bayliss, A., Blackwell, P. G., Bronk Ramsey, C., Butzin, M., Cheng, H., Edwards, R. L., Friedrich, M., Grootes, P. M., Guilderson, T. P., Hajdas, I., Heaton, T. J., Hogg, A. G., Hughen, K. A., Kromer, B., Manning, S. W., Muscheler, R., Palmer, J. G., Pearson, C., van der Plicht, J., Reimer, R. W., Richards, D. A., Scott, E. M., Southon, J. R., Turney, C. S. M., Wacker, L., Adolphi, F., Büntgen, U., Capano, M., Fahrni, S. M., Fogtmann-Schulz, A., Friedrich, R., Köhler, P., Kudsk, S., Miyake, F., Olsen, J., Reinig, F., Sakamoto, M., Sookdeo, A., and Talamo, S.: The IntCal20 Northern Hemisphere Radiocarbon Age Calibration Curve (0–55 cal kBP), *Radiocarbon*, 62, 725–757, <https://doi.org/10.1017/RDC.2020.41>, 2020.
- Reinhardt, W.: Studies on the development of rural settlement patterns in the marshes of the East Frisian west coast, *Probleme der Küstenforschung im südlichen Nordseegebiet*, 8, 73–148, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Studien zur Entwicklung des ländlichen Siedlungsbildes in den Seemarschen der ostfriesischen Westküste, 1965.
- Reintam, L., Moora, T., and Raukas, A.: Gleysols on sandy deposits of the Litorina Sea underlain by Histosol formations of Ancylus Lake age in western Estonia, *Estonian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 57, <https://doi.org/10.3176/earth.2008.4.03>, Language: English with Estonian abstract, 2008.
- Repkina, T., Romanenko, F., Baranskaya, A., and Samsonova, S. Y.: (Dynamics of the eastern coast of Unskaya Bay, White Sea, in the Holocene), *Вестник МГУ. Сер. географическая* (Bulletin of Moscow State University. Ser. geographic), -, -, in review.
- Repkina, T. Y. and Romanenko, F. A.: Coastal relief of the Babye More and the Velikiy Island: history of development and modern changes, *Proceedings of the White Sea Biological Station of Moscow State University* 19, White Sea Biological Station of Moscow State University, URL http://wsbs-msu.ru/res/DictionaryAttachment/1022/DOC_FILENAME/BBS%20Proceed%20Vol%2012%20total%201.pdf#page=178, Language: Russian with English abstract, Authors (in original language): Ю., Репкина Т. and А., Романенко Ф., Title (in original language): Рельеф побережий Бабьего моря и о. Великого: история развития и современные изменения, *Journal/book* (in original language): Труды Беломорской биостанции МГУ, 2016.
- Ricard, J.: Paleogeographic reconstruction in the Deception River region, Ungava Peninsula, Quebec, Master's thesis, Université de Montréal, Montréal, Canada, title translated by DeepL, Language: French, Title (in original language): Reconstitution paléogéographique dans la région de la rivière Déception, péninsule d'Ungava, Québec, 1989.

- Richardt, N.: Sedimentological examination of the Late Weichselian sea-level history following deglaciation of northern Denmark, in: Late Quaternary Palaeoceanography of the North Atlantic Margins, edited by Andrews, J. T., Austin, W. E. N., Bergsten, H., and Jennings, A. E., vol. 111 of *Geological Society, London, Special Publications*, pp. 261–273, Geological Society of London, <https://doi.org/10.1144/GSL.SP.1996.111.01.17>, 1996.
- Ridler, R H; Shilts, W. W.: Exploration for Archean polymetallic sulphide deposits in permafrost terrains: an integrated geological/geochemical technique, Kaminak Lake area, District of Keewatin, Paper 73-34, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/103314>, 1974.
- Ristaniemi, O.: The highest shore and Ancyclus limit of the Baltic Sea and the Ancient Lake Päijänne in Central Finland, Series c, 59, University of Turku, Turku, Finland, Language: Finnish, Title (in original language): Itämeren korkein ranta ja Ancyclusraja sekä Muinai-Päijänne Keski-Suomessa, 1987.
- Ristaniemi, O. and Glückert, G.: Ancyclus and Litorina transgressions in south-west Finland, in: Tutkimuksia geologian alalta, vol. 67 of *Annales Universitatis Turkuensis C*, pp. 129–145, University of Turku, Language: Finnish, Title (in original language): Ancyclus- ja Litorinatransgressiot Lounais-Suomessa, 1988.
- Robertsson, A.-M.: Shoreline shift in the Eskilstuna area about 9000 to 4000 years ago, Rapporter och meddelanden 67, Sveriges geologiska undersökning, Uppsala, Sweden, URL <https://resource.sgu.se/dokument/publikation/rm/rm67rapport/rm67-rapport.pdf>, title translated with DeepL, Language: Swedish with English abstract, Title (in original language): Strandförskjutningen i Eskilstunatrakten för ca 9000 till 4000 år sedan, 1991.
- Roeleveld, W. and Gotjé, W.: Holocene water level development in the Northeast Polder in relation to sea level movement and coastal development, in: De Holocene laagveenontwikkeling in de randzone van de Nederlandse kustvlakte (Noordoostpolder), chap. 4, pp. 76–90, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, URL <https://research.vu.nl/en/publications/de-holocene-laagveenontwikkeling-in-de-randzone-van-de-nederlands>, w. Gotjé, PHD Thesis, title translated with DeepL, Language: Dutch, Title (in original language): Holocene waterspiegelontwikkeling in de Noordoostpolder in relatie tot zeespiegelbeweging en kustontwikkeling, 1993.
- Rogers, E. E. and Pizzuto, J. E.: The Holocene stratigraphy of three freshwater to brackish wetlands, Kent County, Delaware, in: Paleoenvironmental studies of the State Route 1 corridor: contexts for prehistoric settlement, New Castle and Kent counties, Delaware, edited by Kellogg, D. C. and Custer, J. F., vol. 114 of *Archaeology Series*, pp. 48–81, Delaware Department of Transportation, URL <https://deldot.gov/environmental/archaeology/paleoenvironmental/index.shtml>, 1994.
- Rohde, H.: Water level observations in the area of the German North Sea coast before the middle of the 19th century, *Die Küste*, 28, 1–96, URL <https://izw.baw.de/publikationen/die-kueste/0/k028102.pdf>, Language: German with English abstract, Title (in original language): Wasserstandsbeobachtungen im Bereich der deutschen Nordseeküste vor der Mitte des 19. Jahrhunderts, 1975.
- Romanenko, F. A. and Shilova, O. S.: The postglacial uplift of the Karelian Coast of the White Sea according to radiocarbon and diatom analyses of lacustrine-boggy deposits of Kindo Peninsula, *Doklady Earth Sciences*, 442, 544–548, <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1028334X12020079>, 2012.

- Romanenko, F. A., Belova, N. G., Nikolaev, V. I., and Olyunina, O. S.: Structural Features of Loose Deposits of the Yugorskiy Coast of Baydaratskaya Bay, Kara Sea, in: Proceedings of the V All-Russian. Quaternary meeting, pp. 348–351, GEOS, Moscow, Russia, URL <http://www.geogr.msu.ru/structure/labs/geos/personal/belova/Romanenko%20et%20al%202007.pdf>, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Романенко, Ф. А., Белова, Н. Г., Николаев, В. И., and Олюнина, О. С., Title (in original language): Особенности строения рыхлых отложений Югорского побережья Байдарацкой губы Карского моря, Journal/book (in original language): Матер. V Всеросс. совещания по изучению четвертичного периода, 2007.
- Rosentau, A., Veski, S., Kriiska, A., Aunap, R., Vassiljev, J., Saarse, L., Hang, T., Heinsalu, A., and Oja, T.: Palaeogeographic Model for the SW Estonian Coastal Zone of the Baltic Sea, chap. 8, pp. 165–188, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-17220-5_8, 2011.
- Rosentau, A., Muru, M., Kriiska, A., Subetto, D. A., Vassiljev, J., Hang, T., Gerasimov, D., Nordqvist, K., Ludikova, A., Lõugas, L., Raig, H., Kihno, K., Aunap, R., and Letyka, N.: Stone Age settlement and Holocene shore displacement in the Narva-Luga Klint Bay area, eastern Gulf of Finland, *Boreas*, 42, 912–931, <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12004>, 2013.
- Rosentau, A., Nirgi, T., Muru, M., Bjursäter, S., Hang, T., Preusser, F., Risberg, J., Sohar, K., Tönisson, H., and Kriiska, A.: Holocene relative shore level changes and Stone Age hunter-gatherers in Hiiumaa Island, eastern Baltic Sea, *Boreas*, 49, 783–798, <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12452>, 2020.
- Rosentau, A., Klemann, V., Bennike, O., Steffen, H., Wehr, J., Latinović, M., Bagge, M., Ojala, A., Berglund, M., Becher, G. P., Schoning, K., Hansson, A., Nielsen, L., Clemmensen, L. B., Hede, M. U., Kroon, A., Pejrup, M., Sander, L., Statterger, K., Schwarzer, K., Lampe, R., Lampe, M., Uścinowicz, S., Bitinas, A., Grudzinska, I., Vassiljev, J., Nirgi, T., Kublitskiy, Y., and Subetto, D.: A Holocene relative sea-level database for the Baltic Sea, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 266, 107 071, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2021.107071>, 2021.
- Rovere, A., Ryan, D. D., Vacchi, M., Dutton, A., Simms, A. R., and Murray-Wallace, C. V.: The World Atlas of Last Interglacial Shorelines (version 1.0), *Earth System Science Data*, 15, 1–23, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-15-1-2023>, 2023.
- Roy, P. S. and Crawford, E. A.: Holocene geological evolution of the southern Botany Bay-Kurnell region, central New South Wales coast, *Records of the Geological Survey of New South Wales* 20, Part 2, New South Wales Geological Survey, URL <https://search.geoscience.nsw.gov.au/report/R00047897>, 1981.
- Rubin, M. and Alexander, C.: U. S. Geological Survey Radiocarbon Dates V, *Radiocarbon*, 2, 129–185, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1061592X00020652>, 1960.
- Rutherford, A. A., Wittenberg, J., and McCallum, K. J.: University of Saskatchewan radiocarbon dates VI, *Radiocarbon*, 15, 193–211, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200058707>, 1973.
- Rutherford, A. A., Wittenberg, J., and Wilmeth, R.: University of Saskatchewan radiocarbon dates VIII, *Radiocarbon*, 21, 48–94, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200004215>, 1979.
- Rémillard, A. M., St-Onge, G., Bernatchez, P., Héту, B., Buylaert, J.-P., Murray, A. S., and Vigneault, B.: Chronology and stratigraphy of the Magdalen Islands archipelago from the last glaciation to the early Holocene: new insights into the glacial and sea-level history of eastern Canada, *Boreas*, 45, 604–628, <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12179>, 2016.

- Rémillard, A. M., St-Onge, G., Bernatchez, P., Héту, B., Buylaert, J.-P., Murray, A. S., and Lajeunesse, P.: Relative sea-level changes and glacio-isostatic adjustment on the Magdalen Islands archipelago (Atlantic Canada) from MIS 5 to the late Holocene, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 171, 216–233, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2017.07.015>, 2017.
- Saarnisto, M.: Holocene emergence history and stratigraphy in the area north of the Gulf of Bothnia, *Annales Academiae Scientiarum Fennicae. Series A. III. Geologica - Geographica*, 130, 7–42, 1981.
- Saarse, L., Vassiljev, J., and Miidel, A.: Simulation of the Baltic Sea shorelines in Estonia and neighbouring areas, *Journal of Coastal Research*, pp. 261–268, URL <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4299167>, 2003.
- Saarse, L., Vassiljev, J., Miidel, A., and Niinemets, E.: Holocene buried organic sediments in Estonia, *Proceedings of the Estonian Academy of Sciences, Geology*, 55, 296–320, <https://doi.org/10.3176/geol.2006.4.03>, Language: English with Estonian abstract, 2006.
- Saarse, L., Heinsalu, A., and Veski, S.: Litorina Sea sediments of ancient Vääna Lagoon, northwestern Estonia, *Estonian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 58, 85–93, <https://doi.org/10.3176/earth.2009.1.08>, 2009.
- Saint-Laurent, D. and Filion, L.: Paleocological Interpretation of the Sand Dunes at the Tree Line, North-East Sector of Hudson Bay, Québec, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 46, 209–220, <https://doi.org/10.7202/032905ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): *Interprétation paléoécologique des dunes à la limite des arbres, secteur nord-est de la mer d' Hudson, Québec*, 1992.
- Salama, M. S.: Late Quaternary sedimentary characteristics, processes and evolution of the Princess Charlotte Bay area: a Great Barrier Reef province, Ph.D. thesis, The University of Queensland, Brisbane, Queensland, Australia, <https://doi.org/10.14264/775f317>, 1991.
- Salomaa, R.: Post-glacial shoreline displacement in the Lauhanvuori area, western Finland, in: *Studies on the Baltic shorelines and sediments indicating relative sea-level changes. Proceedings of the symposium of INQUA subcommission on shorelines of northwestern Europe, Lammi 13th September 1981*, vol. 134 of *Annales Academiae scientiarum Fennicae. Series A. III. Geologica - Geographica*, pp. 81–97, Suomalainen tiedeakatemia, Helsinki, 1982.
- Samson, C., Barrette, L., LaSalle, P., and Fortier, J.: Quebec radiocarbon measurements I, *Radiocarbon*, 19, 96–100, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200003362>, 1977.
- Sander, L., Fruergaard, M., Koch, J., Johannessen, P. N., and Pejrup, M.: Sedimentary indications and absolute chronology of Holocene relative sea-level changes retrieved from coastal lagoon deposits on Samsø, Denmark, *Boreas*, 44, 706–720, <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12124>, 2015.
- Sandgren, P., Subetto, D. A., Berglund, B. E., Davydova, N. N., and Savelieva, L. A.: Mid-Holocene Littorina Sea transgressions based on stratigraphic studies in coastal lakes of NW Russia, *GFF*, 126, 363–380, <https://doi.org/10.1080/11035890401264363>, 2004.
- Sarv, A.: Geochronological subdivision of Holocene bog-lacustrine deposits in the region of Kõivasoo swamp (Hiiumaa island, Estonia), *Proceedings of the Academy of Sciences of the Estonian SSR. Geology*, 30, 173–178, <https://doi.org/10.3176/geol.1981.4.06>, Language: Russian with Estonian and English abstracts, Title (in original language): *СТРАТИГРАФИЯ И ГЕОХРОНОЛОГИЯ ОЗЕРНЫХ И БОЛОТНЫХ ОТЛОЖЕНИЙ БОЛОТА КЫЙВАСОО (о. ХИЙУМАА, ЭСТОНСКАЯ ССР)*, 1981.

- Sas, Z. A.: Holocene sedimentation, Blackwood River Estuary, Western Australia, Environmental Study of the Blackwood River Estuary: Technical Report 2, Department of Conservation and the Environment, Perth, Australia, 1974.
- Sasaki, K., Omura, A., Murakami, K., Sagawa, N., and Nakamori, T.: Interstadial coral reef terraces and relative sea-level changes during marine oxygen isotope stages 3-4, Kikai Island, central Ryukyus, Japan, *Quaternary International*, 120, 51–64, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2004.01.006>, coastal Environmental Change during Sea-Level Highstands, IGCP 437 Symposium, Barbados, 2004.
- Sasaki, K., Omura, A., Miwa, T., Tsuji, Y., Matsuda, H., Nakamori, T., Iryu, Y., Yamada, T., Sato, Y., and Nakagawa, H.: $^{230}\text{Th}/^{234}\text{U}$ and ^{14}C dating of a lowstand coral reef beneath the insular shelf off Irabu Island, Ryukyus, southwestern Japan, *Island Arc*, 15, 455–467, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1440-1738.2006.00541.x>, 2006.
- Saulnier-Talbot, É. and Pienitz, R.: Postglacial isolation of a coastal basin near Kuujjuaraapik-Whapmagoostui, Hudsonie: A diatom biostratigraphical investigation, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 55, 63–74, <https://doi.org/10.7202/005662ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): Isolation au postglaciaire d'un bassin côtier près de Kuujjuaraapik-Whapmagoostui, en Hudsonie (Québec) : une analyse biostratigraphique diatomifère, 2001.
- Savoie, L. and Gangloff, P.: Pollen analysis of a palsa at the archaeological site of Killiniq, N.W.T., *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 34, 301–320, <https://doi.org/10.7202/1000414ar>, Language: French with English and German abstracts, Title (in original language): Analyse pollinique d' une palse au site archéologique de Vieux-Port-Burwell (Killiniq), Territoires du Nord-Ouest, 1980.
- Scheder, J., Frenzel, P., Bungenstock, F., Engel, M., Brüeckner, H., and Pint, A.: Vertical and lateral distribution of Foraminifera and Ostracoda in the East Frisian Wadden Sea—developing a transfer function for relative sea-level change, *Geologica Belgica*, 22, 99–110, <https://doi.org/10.20341/gb.2019.007>, 2019.
- Scheder, J., Bungenstock, F., Haynert, K., Pint, A., Schlütz, F., Frenzel, P., Wehrmann, A., Brückner, H., and Engel, M.: Insights into Holocene relative sea-level changes in the southern North Sea using an improved microfauna-based transfer function, *Journal of Quaternary Science*, 37, 71–85, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.3380>, 2022.
- Scheffers, A., Brill, D., Kelletat, D., Brückner, H., Scheffers, S., and Fox, K.: Holocene sea levels along the Andaman Sea coast of Thailand, *The Holocene*, 22, 1169–1180, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683612441803>, 2012.
- Schimanski, A. and Stattegger, K.: Deglacial and Holocene evolution of the Vietnam shelf: stratigraphy, sediments and sea-level change, *Marine Geology*, 214, 365–387, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2004.11.001>, 2005.
- Schmid, P.: Oldorf – an early medieval Frisian dwelling settlement, *Germania*, 72, 231–267, <https://doi.org/10.11588/ger.1994.65612>, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Oldorf - eine frühmittelalterliche friesische Wurtsiedlung, 1994.
- Schmidt, R., Mäusbacher, R., and Müller, J.: Holocene diatom flora and stratigraphy from sediment cores of two Antarctic lakes (King George Island), *Journal of Paleolimnology*, 3, 55–74, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00209300>, 1990.

- Schütte, H.: Sinking Land on the North Sea? On the Coastal History of Northwest Germany, *Schriften des Deutschen Naturkundevereins Neue Folge*, 9, 144, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Sinkendes Land an der Nordsee? Zur Küstengeschichte Nordwestdeutschlands, 1939.
- Scoffin, T. P. and Le Tissier, M. D. A.: Late Holocene sea level and reef-flat progradation, Phuket, South Thailand, *Coral Reefs*, 17, 273–276, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s003380050128>, 1998.
- Scott, D. B. and Greenberg, D. A.: Relative sea-level rise and tidal development in the Fundy tidal system, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 20, 1554–1564, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e83-145>, Language: English with French abstract, 1983.
- Scott, D. B. and Medioli, F. S.: Micropaleontological documentation for early Holocene fall of relative sea level on the Atlantic coast of Nova Scotia, *Geology*, 10, 278–281, [https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613\(1982\)10<278:MDFEHF>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613(1982)10<278:MDFEHF>2.0.CO;2), 1982.
- Scott, D. B., Williamson, M. A., and Duffett, T. E.: Marsh foraminifera of Prince Edward Island: their recent distribution and application for former sea level studies, *Maritime Sediments and Atlantic Geology*, 17, 98–129, <https://doi.org/10.4138/1380>, Language: English with French abstract, 1981.
- Scott, D. B., Medioli, F. S., and Duffett, T. E.: Holocene rise of relative sea level at Sable Island, Nova Scotia, Canada, *Geology*, 12, 173–176, [https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613\(1984\)12<173:HRORSL>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613(1984)12<173:HRORSL>2.0.CO;2), 1984.
- Scott, D. B., Boyd, R., and Medioli, F. S.: Relative sea-level changes In Atlantic Canada: observed level and sedimentological changes vs. theoretical models, in: *Sea-level fluctuation and coastal evolution*, SEPM Society for Sedimentary Geology, <https://doi.org/10.2110/pec.87.41.0087>, 1987.
- Scott, D. B., Boyd, R., Douma, M., Medioli, F. S., Yuill, S., Leavitt, E., and Lewis, C. F. M.: Holocene relative sea-level changes and Quaternary glacial events on a continental shelf edge: Sable Island Bank, in: *Late Quaternary sea-level correlation and applications*, pp. 105–119, Springer, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-009-0873-4_6, 1989.
- Scott, D. B., Brown, K., Collins, E. S., and Medioli, F. S.: A new sea-level curve from Nova Scotia: evidence for a rapid acceleration of sea-level rise in the late mid-Holocene, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 32, 2071–2080, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e95-160>, Language: English with French abstract, 1995.
- Scott, S., Catto, N., and Liverman, D.: Quaternary marine deposits of the Springdale-Hall' s Bay area, Newfoundland, *Atlantic Geology*, 27, 181–191, <https://doi.org/10.4138/1733>, Language: English with French abstract, 1991.
- Scott, T. W.: Correlating late Pleistocene deposits on the coastal plain of Virginia with the glacial-eustatic sea-level curve, Master's thesis, Old Dominion University, Norfolk, VA, United States, 2006.
- Seaman, A. A.: Late Pleistocene history of New Brunswick, Canada, in: *Quaternary Glaciations—Extent and Chronology - Part II: North America*, edited by Ehlers, J., Gibbard, P. L., and Hughes, P. D., *Developments in Quaternary Science*, pp. 151–167, Elsevier, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1571-0866\(04\)80195-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1571-0866(04)80195-7), 2004.
- Searle, D. J. and Logan, B. W.: A report on sedimentation in Geographe Bay, Report to the public works department of western australia, *Sedimentology and Marine Geology Group*, University of Western Australia, Perth, Australia, 1978.

- Searle, D. J. and Woods, P. J.: Detailed documentation of a Holocene sea-level record in the perth region, southern Western Australia, *Quaternary Research*, 26, 299–308, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894\(86\)90091-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894(86)90091-8), 1986.
- Searle, D. J., Semeniuk, V., and Woods, P. J.: Geomorphology, stratigraphy and Holocene history of the Rockingham-Becher Plain, Southwestern Australia, *Journal of the Royal Society of Western Australia*, 70, 89–109, URL <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/part/238330>, 1988.
- Sears, P. C.: Evolution of Platt Shoals, northern North Carolina shelf, Master's thesis, Old Dominion University, Norfolk, VA, United States, 1973.
- Semeniuk, V.: The age structure of a Holocene barrier dune system and its implication for sealevel history reconstructions in southwestern Australia, *Marine Geology*, 67, 197–212, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(85\)90092-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(85)90092-1), 1985.
- Semeniuk, V.: An early Holocene record of rising sea level along a bathymetrically complex coast in southwestern Australia, *Marine Geology*, 131, 177–193, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(96\)00007-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(96)00007-2), 1996.
- Seppä, H., Tikkanen, M., and Shemeikka, P.: Late-Holocene shore displacement of the Finnish south coast: diatom, litho- and chemostratigraphic evidence from three isolation basins, *Boreas*, 29, 219–231, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2000.tb00980.x>, 2000.
- Sergeev, A., Sivkov, V., Zhamoida, V., Ryabchuk, D., Bitinas, A., and Mažeika, J.: Holocene organic-rich sediments within the Curonian Spit coast, the south-eastern Baltic Sea, *Baltica*, 28, 41–50, <https://doi.org/10.5200/baltica.2015.28.05>, 2015.
- Shaw, J. and Edwardson, K. A.: Surficial sediments and post-glacial relative sea-level history, Hamilton Sound, Newfoundland, *Atlantic Geology*, 30, 97–112, <https://doi.org/10.4138/2123>, Language: English with French abstract, 1994.
- Shaw, J. and Forbes, D. L.: Coastal barrier and beach-ridge sedimentation in Newfoundland, in: *Proceedings, Canadian Coastal Conference*, pp. 437–454, Natural Resources Council Canada Ottawa, URL https://www.researchgate.net/publication/291167843_Coastal_barrier_and_beach-ridge_sedimentation_in_Newfoundland, Language: English with French abstract, 1987.
- Shaw, J. and Forbes, D. L.: The postglacial relative sea-level lowstand in Newfoundland, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 32, 1308–1330, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e95-107>, Language: English with French abstract, 1995.
- Shaw, J. and Potter, D. P.: Surficial geology, coastal waters, Island of Newfoundland, Newfoundland and Labrador, *Bulletin 605*, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/10.4095/293728>, 2015.
- Shaw, J., Taylor, R., and Forbes, D.: Impact of the Holocene transgression on the Atlantic coastline of Nova Scotia, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 47, 221–238, <https://doi.org/10.7202/032950ar>, Language: English with French abstract, 1993.
- Shaw, J., Fader, G. B., and Taylor, R. B.: Submerged early Holocene coastal and terrestrial landforms on the inner shelves of Atlantic Canada, *Quaternary International*, 206, 24–34, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2008.07.017>, 2009.

- Shaw, J., Amos, C. L., Greenberg, D. A., O' Reilly, C. T., Parrott, D. R., and Patton, E.: Catastrophic tidal expansion in the Bay of Fundy, Canada, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 47, 1079–1091, <https://doi.org/10.1139/E10-046>, 2010.
- Short, A., Fotheringham, D., and Buckley, R.: Coastal morphodynamics and Holocene evolution of the Eyre Peninsula coast, Coastal Studies Unit Technical Report 86/2, University of Sydney, 1986.
- Simon, K. M., James, T. S., Forbes, D. L., Telka, A. M., Dyke, A. S., and Henton, J. A.: A relative sea-level history for Arviat, Nunavut, and implications for Laurentide Ice Sheet thickness west of Hudson Bay, *Quaternary research*, 82, 185–197, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yqres.2014.04.002>, 2014.
- Simon, K. M., James, T. S., Henton, J. A., and Dyke, A. S.: A glacial isostatic adjustment model for the central and northern Laurentide Ice Sheet based on relative sea level and GPS measurements, *Geophysical Journal International*, 205, 1618–1636, <https://doi.org/10.1093/gji/ggw103>, 2016.
- Sindowski, K.-H.: Geological Map of Lower Saxony 1:25000, Sheet 2213 Wangerooge, Blatt 2213, Hannover Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Bodenforschung, Hannover, Germany, title translated by DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Geologische Karte von Niedersachsen 1:25000, Blatt 2213 Wangerooge, 1969.
- Sinsakul, S.: Evidence of Quaternary sea level changes in the coastal areas of Thailand: a review, *Journal of Southeast Asian Earth Sciences*, 7, 23–37, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0743-9547\(92\)90012-Z](https://doi.org/10.1016/0743-9547(92)90012-Z), global Environmental Change the Role of the Geoscientist Past, Present and Future Sea-level changes, 1992.
- Skaarup, J. and Grøn, O.: Geology and topography, in: Møllegabet ii, a submerged Mesolithic settlement in southern Denmark, edited by Skaarup, J. and Grøn, O., vol. 1328, pp. 4–20, British Archaeological Reports Limited, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.30861/9781841716732>, 2004.
- Slagle, A. L., Ryan, W. B. F., Carbotte, S. M., Bell, R., Nitsche, F. O., and Kenna, T.: Late-stage estuary infilling controlled by limited accommodation space in the Hudson River, *Marine Geology*, 232, 181–202, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2006.07.009>, 2006.
- Sloss, C., Murray-Wallace, C., Jones, B., and Wallin, T.: Aspartic acid racemisation dating of mid-Holocene to recent estuarine sedimentation in New South Wales, Australia: a pilot study, *Marine Geology*, 212, 45–59, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2004.07.009>, 2004.
- Sloss, C. R.: Holocene sea-level change and the aminostratigraphy of wave-dominated barrier estuaries on the southeast coast of Australia, Ph.D. thesis, University of Wollongong, Wollongong, Australia, URL <http://ro.uow.edu.au/theses/447>, 2005.
- Sloss, C. R., Murray-Wallace, C. V., and Jones, B. G.: Aminostratigraphy of Two Holocene Wave-Dominated Barrier Estuaries in Southeastern Australia, *Journal of Coastal Research*, 22, 113–136, <https://doi.org/10.2112/05A-0010.1>, 2006.
- Sloss, C. R., Murray-Wallace, C. V., and Jones, B. G.: Holocene sea-level change on the southeast coast of Australia: a review, *The Holocene*, 17, 999–1014, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683607082415>, 2007.
- Sloss, C. R., Jones, B. G., Murray-Wallace, C. V., and Bouvet, M.: The geomorphological evolution of a saline coastal lagoon on the southeast coast of Australia: Swan Lake, New South Wales, *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 224, 301–313, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2019.05.009>, 2019.

- Slupik, A. A., Wesselingh, F. P., Mayhew, D. F., Janse, A. C., Dieleman, F. E., Van Strydonck, M., Kiden, P., Burger, A. W., and Reumer, J. W. F.: The role of a proto-Schelde River in the genesis of the southwestern Netherlands, inferred from the Quaternary successions and fossils in Moriaanshoofd Borehole (Zeeland, the Netherlands), *Netherlands Journal of Geosciences*, 92, 69–86, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0016774600000299>, 2013.
- Snyder, J. A., Forman, S. L., Mode, W. N., and Tarasov, G. A.: Postglacial relative sea-level history: sediment and diatom records of emerged coastal lakes, north-central Kola Peninsula, Russia, *Boreas*, 26, 329–346, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1997.tb00859.x>, 1997.
- Somboon, J. R. P.: Paleontological study of the recent marine sediments in the lower central plain, Thailand, *Journal of Southeast Asian Earth Sciences*, 2, 201–210, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0743-9547\(88\)90031-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0743-9547(88)90031-1), 1988.
- Somboon, J. R. P. and Thiramongkol, N.: Holocene highstand shoreline of the Chao Phraya delta, Thailand, *Journal of Southeast Asian Earth Sciences*, 7, 53–60, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0743-9547\(92\)90014-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0743-9547(92)90014-3), global Environmental Change the Role of the Geoscientist Past, Present and Future Sea-level changes, 1992.
- Souza, P. E., Sohbaty, R., Murray, A. S., Clemmensen, L. B., Kroon, A., and Nielsen, L.: Optical dating of cobble surfaces determines the chronology of Holocene beach ridges in Greenland, *Boreas*, 50, 606–618, <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12507>, 2021.
- Sparrenbom, C. J., Bennike, O., Björck, S., and Lambeck, K.: Holocene relative sea-level changes in the Qaqortoq area, southern Greenland, *Boreas*, 35, 171–187, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2006.tb01148.x>, 2006a.
- Sparrenbom, C. J., Bennike, O., Björck, S., and Lambeck, K.: Relative sea-level changes since 15 000 cal. yr BP in the Nanortalik area, southern Greenland, *Journal of Quaternary Science*, 21, 29–48, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jqs.940>, 2006b.
- Spaur, C. C. and Snyder, S. W.: Coastal wetlands evolution at the leading edge of the marine transgression: Jarrett Bay, North Carolina, *Journal of the Elisha Mitchell Scientific Society*, 115, 20–46, URL <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24335554>, 1999.
- Spenceley, A. P.: The geomorphological and zonal development of mangrove swamps in the Townsville area, North Queensland, Ph.D. thesis, James Cook University of North Queensland, Townsville, Queensland, Australia, 1980.
- Stanton, C. L. T.: Holocene inner continental shelf stratigraphy, micropaleontology and paleoenvironmental change off the Outer Banks, North Carolina, Master's thesis, East Carolina University, Greenville, North Carolina. United States, 2008.
- Stattegger, K., Tjallingii, R., Saito, Y., Michelli, M., Trung Thanh, N., and Wetzel, A.: Mid to late Holocene sea-level reconstruction of Southeast Vietnam using beachrock and beach-ridge deposits, *Global and Planetary Change*, 110, 214–222, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2013.08.014>, land-Ocean-Atmosphere interaction in the coastal zone of South Vietnam, 2013.
- Stea, R. and Mott, R.: Deglaciation of Nova Scotia: stratigraphy and chronology of lake sediment cores and buried organic sections, *Géographie physique et Quaternaire*, 52, 3–21, <https://doi.org/10.7202/004871ar>, Language: English with French and German abstracts, 1998.
- Stea, R. R. and Mott, R. J.: Deglaciation environments and evidence for glaciers of Younger Dryas age in Nova Scotia, Canada, *Boreas*, 18, 169–187, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.1989.tb00388.x>, 1989.

- Stea, R. R. and Wightman, D. M.: Age of the Five Islands Formation, Nova Scotia, and the deglaciation of the Bay of Fundy, *Quaternary Research*, 27, 211–219, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894\(87\)90078-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894(87)90078-0), 1987.
- Steinke, S., Kienast, M., and Hanebuth, T.: On the significance of sea-level variations and shelf paleomorphology in governing sedimentation in the southern South China Sea during the last deglaciation, *Marine Geology*, 201, 179–206, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227\(03\)00216-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227(03)00216-0), Asian Monsoons and Global Linkages on Milankovitch and Sub-Milankovitch Time Scales, 2003.
- Storms, J. E. A., de Winter, I. L., Overeem, I., Drijkoningen, G. G., and Lykke-Andersen, H.: The Holocene sedimentary history of the Kangerlussuaq Fjord-valley fill, West Greenland, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 35, 29–50, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2011.12.014>, 2012.
- Strahl, E.: First farmers in the German Marsh—The Late Bronze Age settlement of Rodenkirchen-Hahnenknooper Mühle, *Ldkr. Wesermarsch, Berichte zur Denkmalpflege in Niedersachsen*, 22, 79–82, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Erste Bauern in der deutschen Marsch—Die jungbronzezeitliche Siedlung Rodenkirchen-Hahnenknooper Mühle, *Ldkr. Wesermarsch*, 2002a.
- Strahl, E.: The Late Bronze Age settlement of Rodenkirchen-Hahnenknooper Mühle, *Ldkr. Wesermarsch – First farmers in the German Marsch*, *Schriftenreihe des Landesmuseums für Natur und Mensch Oldenburg*, 33, 52–59, Language: German, Title (in original language): Die jungbronzezeitliche Siedlung Rodenkirchen-Hahnenknooper Mühle, *Ldkr. Wesermarsch – Erste Bauern in der deutschen Marsch*, 2002b.
- Street, F. A.: Deglaciation and Marine Paleoclimates, Schuchert Dal, Scoresby Sund, East Greenland, *Arctic and Alpine Research*, 9, 421–426, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00040851.1977.12003935>, 1977.
- Streif, H.: Explanatory notes on sheet no. 2414 Wilhelmshaven, *Geologische Karte von Niedersachsen 1:25 000*, Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Bodenforschung, Hannover, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Erläuterungen zu Blatt Nr. 2414 Wilhelmshaven, 1981.
- Streif, H.: The coastal Holocene on the eastern side of Jade Bay, in: *INQUA-Excursion Guide, Sub-commission on Shorelines of NW Europe, Field Conference 1984*, pp. 13–18, 1984.
- Streif, H.: Explanatory notes on sheet no. 2314 Hooksiel, *Geologische Karte von Niedersachsen 1:25 000*, Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Bodenforschung, Hannover, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Erläuterungen zu Blatt Nr. 2314 Hooksiel, 1985.
- Streif, H.: On the ageing and development of the East Frisian Islands, *Offa*, 43, 29–44, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Zur Altersstellung und Entwicklung der Ostfriesischen Inseln, 1986.
- Streif, H., Uffenorde, H., and Vinken, R.: Investigations on the Pleistocene and Holocene transgression events in the southern North Sea region, Report, Niedersächsisches Landesamt für Bodenforschung, title translated with DeepL, Language: German, Title (in original language): Untersuchungen zum pleistozänen und holozänen Transgressionsgeschehen im Bereich der südlichen Nordsee, 1983.
- Strunk, A., Larsen, N. K., Nilsson, A., Seidenkrantz, M.-S., Levy, L. B., Olsen, J., and Lauridsen, T. L.: Relative Sea-Level Changes and Ice Sheet History in FINDERUP Land, North Greenland, *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 6, <https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2018.00129>, 2018.
- Stuckenrath, R., Coe, W. R., and Ralph, E. K.: University of Pennsylvania radiocarbon dates IX, *Radiocarbon*, 8, 348–385, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200000217>, 1966.

- Stuiver, M. and Daddario, J. J.: Submergence of the New Jersey coast, *Science*, 142, 951–951, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.142.3594.951>, 1963.
- Stuiver, M., Deevey, E. S., and Rouse, I.: Yale Natural Radiocarbon Measurements VIII, *Radiocarbon*, 5, 312–341, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200036936>, 1963.
- Ta, T. K. O., Nguyen, V. L., Tateishi, M., Kobayashi, I., Tanabe, S., and Saito, Y.: Holocene delta evolution and sediment discharge of the Mekong River, southern Vietnam, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 21, 1807–1819, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(02\)00007-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(02)00007-0), 2002.
- Tamers, M. A., Pearson, F. J., and Davis, E. M.: University of Texas Radiocarbon Dates II, *Radiocarbon*, 6, 138–159, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200010614>, 1964.
- Tamura, T., Saito, Y., Sieng, S., Ben, B., Kong, M., Choup, S., and Tsukawaki, S.: Depositional facies and radiocarbon ages of a drill core from the Mekong River lowland near Phnom Penh, Cambodia: Evidence for tidal sedimentation at the time of Holocene maximum flooding, *Journal of Asian Earth Sciences*, 29, 585–592, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jseaes.2006.03.009>, 2007.
- Tamura, T., Saito, Y., Sieng, S., Ben, B., Kong, M., Sim, I., Choup, S., and Akiba, F.: Initiation of the Mekong River delta at 8 ka: evidence from the sedimentary succession in the Cambodian lowland, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 28, 327–344, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2008.10.010>, special Theme: Modern Analogues in Quaternary Palaeoglaciological Reconstruction, 2009.
- Tanabe, S., Saito, Y., Sato, Y., Suzuki, Y., Sinsakul, S., Tiyaipairach, S., and Chaimanee, N.: Stratigraphy and Holocene evolution of the mud-dominated Chao Phraya delta, Thailand, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 22, 789–807, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791\(02\)00242-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-3791(02)00242-1), 2003.
- Tanner, V.: Studies on the Quaternary system in the northern parts of Fennoscandia. II . New contributions to the question of glaciation and level changes in Finland, *Bulletin de la Commission géologique de Finlande* 21, Geologian tutkimuskeskus, Helsingfors, Finland, URL https://gtk.verkkokirjasto.fi/en/web/arena/results?p_p_id=crDetailWicket_WAR_arenaportlet&p_p_lifecycle=1&p_p_state=normal&p_r_p_arena_urn%3Aarena_search_item_id=37620&p_r_p_arena_urn%3Aarena_agency_name=AFI000021&_crDetailWicket_WAR_arenaportlet_back_url=https%3A%2F%2Fgtk.verkkokirjasto.fi%2Fen%2Fweb%2Farena%2Fsearch%3Fp_p_id%3DsearchResult_WAR_arenaportlet%26p_p_lifecycle%3D1%26p_p_state%3Dnormal%26p_r_p_arena_urn%253Aarena_facet_queries%3D%26_searchResult_WAR_arenaportlet_agency_name%3DAFI000021%26p_r_p_arena_urn%253Aarena_search_item_no%3D0%26p_r_p_arena_urn%253Aarena_search_query%3DStudier%2B%25C3%25B6fver%2Bkvart%25C3%25A4rsystemet%2Bi%2BFennoskandias%2Bnordliga%2Bdelar%26p_r_p_arena_urn%253Aarena_search_type%3Dsolr%26p_r_p_arena_urn%253Aarena_sort_advice%3Dfield%253DRelevance%2526direction%253DDescending%26_searchResult_WAR_arenaportlet_arena_member_id%3D28678239%26backLinkUsed%3Dtrue&p_r_p_arena_urn%3Aarena_arena_member_id=28678239, title translated using DeepL, Language: Swedish with French summary, Title (in original language): Studier öfver kvartärsystemet i Fennoskandias nordliga delar. II . Nya bidrag till frågan om Finmarkens glaciation och nivåförändringar, 1907.
- Tauber, H.: Copenhagen Radiocarbon Dates IV, *Radiocarbon*, 2, 12–25, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1061592X00020561>, 1960.

- Tauber, H.: Danish carbon-14 dating results I, *Bulletin of the Geological Society of Denmark*, 14, 386–405, URL <https://2dggf.dk/xpdf/bull-1961-14-4-386-405.pdf>, title translated with DeepL, Language: Danish with English abstract, Title (in original language): Danske kulstof-14 dateringsresultater I, Journal/book (in original language): Meddelelser fra Dansk Geologisk Forening, 1961.
- Tauber, H.: Copenhagen Radiocarbon Dates VI, *Radiocarbon*, 6, 215–225, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200010699>, 1964.
- Tauber, H.: Copenhagen Radiocarbon Dates VII, *Radiocarbon*, 8, 213–234, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200000126>, 1966.
- Ten Brink, N. W.: Holocene history of the Greenland ice sheet based on radiocarbon-dated moraines in West Greenland, *Bulletin Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 113, 1–44, <https://doi.org/10.34194/bullggu.v113.6654>, 1975.
- Ten Brink, N. W. and Weidick, A.: Greenland ice sheet history since the last glaciation, *Quaternary Research*, 4, 429–440, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894\(74\)90038-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894(74)90038-6), 1974.
- Thom, B. G. and Chappell, J.: Holocene sea levels relative to Australia, *Search*, 6, 90–93, 1975.
- Thom, B. G. and Roy, P. S.: Sea-level change in New South Wales over the past 15,000 years., in: *Australian sea levels in the last 15,000 years: a review*, edited by Hopley, D., vol. 3 of *Monograph Series*, pp. 64–84, Department of Geography, James Cook University of North Queensland, 1983.
- Thom, B. G., Hails, J. R., and Martin, A. R. H.: Radiocarbon evidence against higher Postglacial sea levels in eastern Australia, *Marine Geology*, 7, 161–168, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(69\)90038-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(69)90038-3), 1969.
- Thom, B. G., Wright, L. D., and Coleman, J. M.: Mangrove Ecology and Deltaic-Estuarine Geomorphology: Cambridge Gulf-Ord River, Western Australia, *Journal of Ecology*, 63, 203–232, <https://doi.org/10.2307/2258851>, 1975.
- Thomas, A. L., Henderson, G. M., Deschamps, P., Yokoyama, Y., Mason, A. J., Bard, E., Hamelin, B., Durand, N., and Camoin, G.: Penultimate Deglacial sea-level timing from Uranium/Thorium dating of Tahitian corals, *Science*, 324, 1186–1189, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1168754>, 2009.
- Tjia, H. D. and Fujii, S.: Late Quaternary shorelines in peninsular Malaysia, in: *The Coastal Zone of Peninsular Malaysia*, edited by Tjia, H. D. and Sharifah, M., 274, IGCP, Ipoh, Malaysia, 1992.
- Tjia, H. D., Fujii, S., Kigoshi, K., Sugimura, A., and Zakaria, T.: Radiocarbon dates of elevated shorelines, Indonesia and Malaysia. Part 1, *Quaternary Research*, 2, 487–495, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894\(72\)90087-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894(72)90087-7), 1972.
- Tjia, H. D., Fujii, S., and Kigoshi, K.: Holocene shorelines of Tioman island in the South China Sea, in: *Developments in physical geography - a tribute to J. I. S. Zonneveld*, edited by Terwindt, J. H. J. and Van Steijn, H., vol. 62 of *Geologie en Mijnbouw*, pp. 599–604, Netherlands Koninklijk Nederlands Geologisch, URL <https://www.kngmg.nl/geologie-en-mijnbouw-portal-1961-2004/>, 1983.
- Tolonen, K. and Tolonen, M.: Synchronous pollen changes and traditional land use in south Finland, studied from three adjacent sites : A lake, a bog and a forest soil, in: *Lake, mire and river environments during the last 15,000 years : proceedings of the INQUA/IGCP 158 meeting on the Palaeohydrological changes during the last 15,000 years*, Bern, June 1985, edited by Balkema, A. A., pp. 83–97, Rotterdam, 1988.

- Trautman, M. A.: Isotopes, Inc. Radiocarbon Measurements III, *Radiocarbon*, 5, 62–79, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200036791>, 1963.
- Trimonis, E., Gulbinskas, S., Blažauskas, N., Kuzavinis, M., and Visakavičius, E.: Composition and formation of sand massifs in the Curonian–Sambian submarine plateau (Baltic Sea), *Geologija (Lietuvos mokslų akademija)*, 60, 39–50, URL <https://mokslozurnalai.lmaleidykla.lt/geologija/2007/4/4284>, Language: English with Lithuanian and Russian abstracts, 2007.
- Tuck, J. A.: An archaic cemetery at Port au Choix, Newfoundland, *American Antiquity*, 36, 343–358, <https://doi.org/10.2307/277719>, 1971.
- Twiggs, E. J. and Collins, L. B.: Development and demise of a fringing coral reef during Holocene environmental change, eastern Ningaloo Reef, Western Australia, *Marine Geology*, 275, 20–36, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2010.04.004>, 2010.
- Tye, S.: A stratigraphic and geochemical study of the Holocene evolution of southern Halifax Bay, North Queensland, Honours Thesis, James Cook University, 1992.
- Umitsu, M., Buman, M., Kawase, K., and Woodroffe, C. D.: Holocene palaeoecology and formation of the Shoalhaven River deltaic-estuarine plains, southeast Australia, *The Holocene*, 11, 407–418, <https://doi.org/10.1191/095968301678302841>, 2001.
- Uścinowicz, S., Miotk-Szpiganowicz, G., Krąpiec, M., Witak, M., Harff, J., Lübke, H., and Tauber, F.: Drowned Forests in the Gulf of Gdańsk (Southern Baltic) as an Indicator of the Holocene Shoreline Changes, in: *The Baltic Sea Basin*, edited by Harff, J., Björck, S., and Hoth, P., pp. 219–231, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-17220-5_11, 2011.
- Uścinowicz, S., Miotk-Szpiganowicza, G., Gałka, M., Pawlyta, J., Piotrowska, N., Pomian, I., and Witak, M.: The rise, development and destruction of the medieval port of Puck in the light of research into palaeoclimate and sea level change, *Archaeologia Polona*, 49, 87–104, URL <https://rcin.org.pl/dlibra/publication/77027/edition/61749>, 2013.
- Vacchi, M., Engelhart, S. E., Nikitina, D., Ashe, E. L., Peltier, W. R., Roy, K., Kopp, R. E., and Horton, B. P.: Postglacial relative sea-level histories along the eastern Canadian coastline, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 201, 124–146, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2018.09.043>, 2018.
- van Andel, T. H., Heath, G. R., Moore, T. C., and McGeary, D. F. R.: Late Quaternary history, climate, and oceanography of the Timor sea, northwestern Australia, *American Journal of Science*, 265, 737–758, <https://doi.org/10.2475/ajs.265.9.737>, 1967.
- van de Plassche, O.: Sea-level change and water-level movements in the Netherlands during the Holocene, Ph.D. thesis, Vrije Universiteit, Amsterdam, Netherlands, URL https://puc.overheid.nl/rijkswaterstaat/doc/PUC_147237_31/, 1982.
- van de Plassche, O.: Mid-Holocene sea-level change on the Eastern Shore of Virginia, *Marine Geology*, 91, 149–154, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(90\)90138-A](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(90)90138-A), 1990.
- van de Plassche, O.: Late Holocene sea-level fluctuations on the shore of Connecticut inferred from transgressive and regressive overlap boundaries in salt-marsh deposits, *Journal of Coastal Research Special Issue*, 11, 159–179, URL <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25735578>, *quaternary Geology of Long Island Sound and Adjacent Coastal Areas: Walter S. Newman Memorial Volume*, 1991.

- van de Plassche, O.: Evolution of the intra-coastal tidal range in the Rhine-Meuse delta and Flevo Lagoon, 5700-3000 yrs cal BC, *Marine Geology*, 124, 113–128, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(95\)00035-W](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(95)00035-W), 1995.
- van de Plassche, O., Mook, W. G., and Bloom, A. L.: Submergence of coastal Connecticut 6000–3000 (14C) years B.P., *Marine Geology*, 86, 349–354, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(89\)90093-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(89)90093-5), 1989.
- van de Plassche, O., van der Borg, K., and de Jong, A. F. M.: Sea level–climate correlation during the past 1400 yr, *Geology*, 26, 319–322, [https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613\(1998\)026<0319:SLCCDT>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1130/0091-7613(1998)026<0319:SLCCDT>2.3.CO;2), 1998.
- van de Plassche, O., van der Borg, K., and de Jong, A. F. M.: Relative sea-level rise across the Eastern Border fault (Branford, Connecticut): evidence against seismotectonic movements, *Marine Geology*, 184, 61–68, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227\(01\)00277-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227(01)00277-8), 2002.
- van de Plassche, O., Bohncke, S., Makaske, B., and van der Plicht, J.: Water-level changes in the Flevo area, central Netherlands (5300–1500 BC): implications for relative mean sea-level rise in the Western Netherlands, *Quaternary International*, 133-134, 77–93, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2004.10.009>, 2005.
- van de Plassche, O., Makaske, B., Hoek, W. Z., Konert, M., and van der Plicht, J.: Mid-Holocene water-level changes in the lower Rhine-Meuse delta (western Netherlands): implications for the reconstruction of relative mean sea-level rise, palaeoriver-gradients and coastal evolution, *Netherlands Journal of Geosciences - Geologie en Mijnbouw*, 89, 3–20, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0016774600000780>, 2010.
- van Heteren, S., Van der Spek, A. J. F., and De Groot, T.: Architecture of a preserved Holocene tidal complex offshore the Rhine-Meuse mouth, the Netherlands, Tech. Rep. NITG 01-27-A, Netherlands Institute of Applied Geoscience TNO-National Geological Survey, 2002.
- van Tatenhove, F. G. M., van der Meer, J. J. M., and Koster, E. A.: Implications for Deglaciation Chronology from New AMS Age Determinations in Central West Greenland, *Quaternary Research*, 45, 245–253, <https://doi.org/10.1006/qres.1996.0025>, 1996.
- Vassiljev, J., Saarse, L., Grudzinska, I., and Heinsalu, A.: Relative sea level changes and development of the Hiiumaa Island during the Holocene, *Geological Quarterly*, 59, 517–530, <https://doi.org/10.7306/gq.1227>, 2015.
- Veeh, H. H. and France, R. E.: Uranium-series ages of corals and coexisting phosphate deposits on Pelsaert Reef Complex, Houtman-Abrolhos Islands, Western Australia, *Quaternary Research*, 30, 204–209, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894\(88\)90024-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0033-5894(88)90024-5), 1988.
- Veinbergs, I.: The history of development of the Baltic Basin in the final stage of the glacial and the post-glacial, Based on material from research at the Latvian coast and adjacent seabed, university of Latvia, Institute of Geology, 1996.
- Verleyen, E., Hodgson, D. A., Milne, G. A., Sabbe, K., and Vyverman, W.: Relative sea-level history from the Lambert Glacier region, East Antarctica, and its relation to deglaciation and Holocene glacier readvance, *Quaternary Research*, 63, 45–52, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.yqres.2004.09.005>, 2005.
- Verleyen, E., Tavernier, I., Hodgson, D. A., Whitehouse, P. L., Kudoh, S., Imura, S., Heirman, K., Bentley, M. J., Roberts, S. J., De Batist, M., Sabbe, K., and Vyverman, W.: Ice sheet retreat and glacio-isostatic adjustment in Lützow-Holm Bay, East Antarctica, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 169, 85–98, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2017.06.003>, 2017.

- Veski, S.: Vegetation history, human impact and palaeogeography of West Estonia: Pollen analytical studies of lake and bog sediments, Ph.D. thesis, Uppsala University, Uppsala, 1998.
- Veski, S., Heinsalu, A., Klassen, V., Kriiska, A., Lõugas, L., Poska, A., and Saluäär, U.: Early Holocene coastal settlements and palaeoenvironment on the shore of the Baltic Sea at Pärnu, southwestern Estonia, *Quaternary International*, 130, 75–85, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2004.04.033>, baltic Sea Science Congress 2001, 2005.
- Vink, A., Steffen, H., Reinhardt, L., and Kaufmann, G.: Holocene relative sea-level change, isostatic subsidence and the radial viscosity structure of the mantle of northwest Europe (Belgium, the Netherlands, Germany, southern North Sea), *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 26, 3249–3275, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2007.07.014>, 2007.
- Vogel, J. C. and Waterbolk, H. T.: Groningen radiocarbon dates X, *Radiocarbon*, 14, 6–110, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033822200001016>, 1972.
- Vos, P. C.: Explanatory notes map sheet 43/49 West and 49 East-Concept note 43/49 West: Holocene section, Tech. rep., Rijks Geologische Dienst, Distrikt Noord, title translated with DeepL, Language: Dutch, Title (in original language): Toelichting kaartblad 43/49 West en 49 Oost: concept toelichting 43/49 West, holocene deel, 1992.
- Vos, P. C.: Geologisch en paleolandschappelijk onderzoek Yangtzehaven (Maasvlakte, Rotterdam), Tech. Rep. Rapport 1206788-000-BGS-0001, Deltares, Utrecht, Netherlands, 2013.
- Vos, P. C. and Cohen, K. M.: Landscape genesis and palaeogeography, in: Interdisciplinary archaeological research programme Maasvlakte 2, Rotterdam, edited by Moree, J. M. and Sier, M. M., vol. 566 of *BOORrapporten*, chap. 3, pp. 63–146, Bureau Oudheidkundig Onderzoek Rotterdam, Rotterdam, Netherlands, URL <https://dspace.library.uu.nl/handle/1874/309133>, 2014.
- Vos, P. C., Bunnik, F. P. M., Cremer, H., and Hennekman, F. M.: Palaeolandscape survey Papegaaienberg and Kop van Beer, Tech. Rep. Rapport 1201910-000-BGS-000187, Deltares, Utrecht, Netherlands, title translated with DeepL, Language: Dutch, Title (in original language): Paleolandschappelijk onderzoek Papegaaienberg en Kop van Beer, 2010.
- Vos, P. C., Bazelmans, J., Weerts, H. J. T., and van der Meulen, M. J.: Atlas Van Nederland in het Holoceen, Prometheus, Amsterdam, Netherlands, 2011.
- Vos, P. C., Bunnik, F. P. M., Cohen, K. M., and Cremer, H.: A staged geogenetic approach to underwater archaeological prospection in the Port of Rotterdam (Yangtzehaven, Maasvlakte, The Netherlands): A geological and palaeoenvironmental case study for local mapping of Mesolithic lowland landscapes, *Quaternary International*, 367, 4–31, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2014.11.056>, 2015.
- Wagner, F. J. E.: Additional radiocarbon dates, Tyrrell Sea area, *Atlantic Geoscience*, 3, 100–104, <https://doi.org/10.4138/1550>, 1967.
- Walbran, P. D.: Post-glacial and contemporary sedimentation on John Brewer Reef with an assessment of long-term crown-of-thorns starfish outbreaks in the central Great Barrier Reef, Honours Thesis, James Cook University of North Queensland, 1991.
- Walcott, R. I. and Craig, B. G.: Uplift Studies, southeastern Hudson Bay, in: Report of activities part A, April to October 1974, vol. 75-1A of *Paper*, pp. 455–456, Geological Survey of Canada, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.4095/104621>, 1975.

- Wallin, J. E.: The development of permanent agriculture in the lower valley of the Ångermanälven during the Iron Age and the Middle Ages, *Acta Antiqua Ostrobothniensia*, 3, 127–154, title translated with DeepL, Language: Swedish, Title (in original language): Den fasta jordbruksnäringens utveckling i Ångermanälvens nedre dalgång under järnåldern och medeltiden, 1994.
- Walton, A., Trautman, M. A., and Friend, J. P.: Isotopes, Inc. radiocarbon measurements I, *Radiocarbon*, 3, 47–59, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S003382220002083X>, 1961.
- Wang, Y., Li, G., Zhang, W., and Dong, P.: Sedimentary environment and formation mechanism of the mud deposit in the central South Yellow Sea during the past 40 kyr, *Marine Geology*, 347, 123–135, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.margeo.2013.11.008>, 2014.
- Wasell, A. and Håkansson, H.: Diatom stratigraphy in a lake on Horseshoe Island, Antarctica: a marine-brackish-fresh water transition with comments on the systematics and ecology of the most common diatoms, *Diatom Research*, 7, 157–194, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0269249X.1992.9705205>, 1992.
- Washburn, A. L. and Stuiver, M.: Radiocarbon-dated postglacial delevelling in Northeast Greenland and its implications, *Arctic*, 15, 66–73, <https://doi.org/10.14430/arctic3558>, 1962.
- Way, A.: Post-glacial stratigraphy of Upstart Bay off the Burdekin River, north Queensland, Master's thesis, James Cook University, Townsville, Townsville, Queensland, Australia, 1987.
- Webber, P. J., Richardson, J. W., and Andrews, J. T.: Post-glacial uplift and substrate age at Cape Henrietta Maria, southeastern Hudson Bay, Canada, *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 7, 317–325, <https://doi.org/10.1139/e70-029>, 1970.
- Weidick, A.: Observations on some Holocene glacier fluctuations in West Greenland, *Bulletin Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 73, 1–202, <https://doi.org/10.34194/bullggu.v73.6611>, 1968.
- Weidick, A.: Holocene shore-lines and glacial stages in Greenland – an attempt at correlation, *Rapport Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 41, 1–39, URL <https://geusjournals.org/index.php/rapggu/issue/view/1005>, 1972a.
- Weidick, A.: C14 dating of Survey material performed in 1971, *Rapport Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 45, 58–67, <https://doi.org/10.34194/rapggu.v45.7303>, 1972b.
- Weidick, A.: C14 dating of Survey material performed in 1972, *Rapport Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 55, 66–75, <https://doi.org/10.34194/rapggu.v55.7356>, 1973.
- Weidick, A.: C14 dating of Survey material performed in 1973, *Rapport Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 66, 42–45, <https://doi.org/10.34194/rapggu.v66.7402>, 1974.
- Weidick, A.: C14 dating of Survey material performed in 1974, *Rapport Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 75, 19–20, <https://doi.org/10.34194/rapggu.v75.7436>, 1975.
- Weidick, A.: C14 dating of Survey material carried out in 1975, *Rapport Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 80, 136–144, <https://doi.org/10.34194/rapggu.v80.7507>, 1976.
- Weidick, A.: C14 dating of Survey material carried out in 1976, *Rapport Grønlands Geologiske Undersøgelse*, 85, 127–129, <https://doi.org/10.34194/rapggu.v85.7545>, 1977.
- Weidick, A., Bennike, O., Citterio, M., and Nørgaard-Pedersen, N.: Neoglacial and historical glacier changes around Kangarsuneq fjord in southern West Greenland, *GEUS Bulletin*, 27, 1–68, <https://doi.org/10.34194/geusb.v27.4694>, 2012.

- Weihe, R.: Late Quaternary glacial geology and relative sea level history of Franz Josef Land, Russia, Master's thesis, Department of Geological Sciences, The Ohio State University, Ohio, USA, 1996.
- Weiss, T. L., Linsley, B. K., Gordon, A. L., Rosenthal, Y., and Dannenmann-Di Palma, S.: Constraints on Marine Isotope Stage 3 and 5 Sea Level from the Flooding History of the Karimata Strait in Indonesia, *Paleoceanography and Paleoclimatology*, p. e2021PA004361, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021PA004361>, e2021PA004361 2021PA004361, 2022.
- Wiedicke, M., Kudrass, H.-R., and Hübscher, C.: Oolitic beach barriers of the last Glacial sea-level lowstand at the outer Bengal shelf, *Marine Geology*, 157, 7–18, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227\(98\)00162-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-3227(98)00162-5), 1999.
- Winn, K., Averdieck, F.-R., Erlenkeuser, H., and Werner, F.: Holocene sea level rise in the western Baltic and the question of isostatic subsidence, *Meyniana*, 38, 61–80, URL <http://oceanrep.geomar.de/id/eprint/29994>, Language: English with German abstract, 1986.
- Winterfeld, M., Schirrmeister, L., Grigoriev, M. N., Kunitsky, V. V., Andreev, A., Murray, A., and Overduin, P. P.: Coastal permafrost landscape development since the Late Pleistocene in the western Laptev Sea, Siberia, *Boreas*, 40, 697–713, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2011.00203.x>, 2011.
- Wood, P. A.: A possible Holocene shoreline at Maroochydore, Queensland, *Queensland Government Mining Journal*, 73, 331, URL <https://geoscience.data.qld.gov.au/data/report/cr048731>, 1972.
- Woodroffe, C., Chappell, J. M. A., Thom, B. G., and Wallensky, E.: Geomorphological dynamics and evolution of the South Alligator tidal river and plains, Northern Territory, vol. 3 of *Mangrove Monograph*, Australian National University North Australia Research Unit, URL <http://hdl.handle.net/1885/8957>, 1986.
- Woodroffe, C. D., Thom, B. G., and Chappell, J.: Development of widespread mangrove swamps in mid-Holocene times in northern Australia, *Nature*, 317, 711–713, <https://doi.org/10.1038/317711a0>, 1985.
- Woodroffe, C. D., Thom, B., Chappell, J., Wallensky, E., and Grindrod, J.: Relative sea level in the South Alligator River region, north Australia, during the Holocene, *Search*, 18, 198–200, 1987.
- Woodroffe, C. D., Brooke, B. P., Linklater, M., Kennedy, D. M., Jones, B. G., Buchanan, C., Mleczko, R., Hua, Q., and Zhao, J.-x.: Response of coral reefs to climate change: Expansion and demise of the southernmost Pacific coral reef, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 37, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010GL044067>, 2010.
- Woodroffe, S. A.: Testing models of mid to late Holocene sea-level change, North Queensland, Australia, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 28, 2474–2488, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2009.05.004>, 2009.
- Woodroffe, S. A., Long, A. J., Lecavalier, B. S., Milne, G. A., and Bryant, C. L.: Using relative sea-level data to constrain the deglacial and Holocene history of southern Greenland, *Quaternary Science Reviews*, 92, 345–356, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2013.09.008>, aPEX II: Arctic Palaeoclimate and its Extremes, 2014.
- Wyrwoll, K. H.: Late Quaternary events in Western Australia, *Search*, 8, 32–34, 1977.
- Yokoyama, Y., Lambeck, K., De Deckker, P., Johnston, P., and Fifield, L. K.: Timing of the Last Glacial Maximum from observed sea-level minima, *Nature*, 406, 713–716, <https://doi.org/10.1038/35021035>, 2000.

- Yokoyama, Y., Esat, T. M., and Lambeck, K.: Coupled climate and sea-level changes deduced from Huon Peninsula coral terraces of the last ice age, *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 193, 579–587, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0012-821X\(01\)00515-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0012-821X(01)00515-5), 2001.
- Yokoyama, Y., Purcell, A., Marshall, J. F., and Lambeck, K.: Sea-level during the early deglaciation period in the Great Barrier Reef, Australia, *Global and Planetary Change*, 53, 147–153, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2006.01.014>, late Quaternary paleoceanography of the northwestern Pacific: Results from IMAGES program, 2006.
- Yokoyama, Y., Esat, T. M., Thompson, W. G., Thomas, A. L., Webster, J. M., Miyairi, Y., Sawada, C., Aze, T., Matsuzaki, H., Okuno, J., Fallon, S., Braga, J.-C., Humblet, M., Iryu, Y., Potts, D. C., Fujita, K., Suzuki, A., and Kan, H.: Rapid glaciation and a two-step sea level plunge into the Last Glacial Maximum, *Nature*, 559, 603, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-018-0335-4>, 2018.
- Young, R. W., Bryant, E. A., Price, D. M., Wirth, L. M., and Pease, M.: Theoretical constraints and chronological evidence of Holocene coastal development in central and southern New South Wales, Australia, *Geomorphology*, 7, 317–329, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-555X\(93\)90061-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0169-555X(93)90061-6), 1993.
- Yu, K.-F. and Zhao, J.-X.: U-series dates of Great Barrier Reef corals suggest at least +0.7 m sea level ~7000 years ago, *The Holocene*, 20, 161–168, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0959683609350387>, 2010.
- Yu, S.-Y., Andrén, E., Barnekow, L., Berglund, B. E., and Sandgren, P.: Holocene palaeoecology and shoreline displacement on the Biskopsmåla Peninsula, southeastern Sweden, *Boreas*, 32, 578–589, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3885.2003.tb01237.x>, 2003.
- Yu, S.-Y., Berglund, B. E., Sandgren, P., and Fritz, S. C.: Holocene palaeoecology along the Blekinge coast, SE Sweden, and implications for climate and sea-level changes, *The Holocene*, 15, 278–292, <https://doi.org/10.1191/0959683605hl792rp>, 2005.
- Yu, S.-Y., Berglund, B. E., Sandgren, P., and Lambeck, K.: Evidence for a rapid sea-level rise 7600 yr ago, *Geology*, 35, 891–894, <https://doi.org/10.1130/G23859A.1>, 2007.
- Yu, X., Duan, B., Zhao, J., Gu, D., Feng, A., Liu, Y., and Li, T.: Deep Submerged Speleothems in the Sansha Yongle Blue Hole (South China Sea) as Constraints for Low Sea-levels during the Last Glacial Maximum, *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 9, 2582, 2022.
- Zaretskaya, N., Shevchenko, N., Simakova, A., and Sulerzhitsky, L.: The North Dvina river delta development over the Holocene: geochronology and palaeoenvironment, *Geochronometria*, 38, 116–127, <https://doi.org/10.2478/s13386-011-0012-y>, 2011.
- Zaretskaya, N. E., Shevchenko, N. V., and Khaitov, V. M.: Results of comprehensive studies of Holocene mollusk findings in the area of the White Sea Biological Station of Moscow State University, in: *Proceedings of the Scientific conference dedicated to the 75th anniversary of the White Sea Biological Station named after N.A. Pertsov*. M., pp. 96–100, Moscow State University Publishing House, title translated with DeepL, Language: Russian, Authors (in original language): Зарецкая, Н. Е., Шевченко, Н. В., and Хайтов, В. М., Title (in original language): Результаты комплексных исследований местонахождений голоценовых моллюсков в районе Беломорской Биологической Станции МГУ, Journal/book (in original language): Материалы научной конференции «Морская биология, геология, океанология междисциплинарные исследования на морских стационарах», посвященной 75-летию Беломорской биологической станции им Н.А.Перцова, 2013.
- Zeeberg, J., Lubinski, D. J., and Forman, S. L.: Holocene relative sea-level history of Novaya Zemlya, Russia, and implications for Late Weichselian ice-sheet loading, *Quaternary Research*, 56, 218–230, <https://doi.org/10.1006/qres.2001.2256>, 2001.

- Zhang, Q. and Peterson, J. A.: A geomorphology and late Quaternary geology of the Vestfold Hills, Antarctica, Anare Reports 133, Antarctic Division, Department of Science and Technology, Australian National Antarctic Research Expeditions, Canberra, Australia, URL <https://trove.nla.gov.au/work/18831650>, 1984.
- Zhuravlev, V., Korago, E., Kostin, D., and Zuykova, O.: State geologic map of the Russian Federation, Explanatory report, VSEGEI (All-Russian Geologic Institute Named after A.P. Karpinskiy. Cartographic Fabric of VSEGEI, Saint-Petersburg, Russia, scale 1:1000000 (Third Generation). Series Barents-North Kara. List R-39, 40 - Kolguev Island - Karskie Vorota Strait, Language: Russian, Title (in original language): Государственная геологическая карта России, 2013.
- Zwartz, D., Bird, M., Stone, J., and Lambeck, K.: Holocene sea-level change and ice-sheet history in the Vestfold Hills, East Antarctica, *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, 155, 131–145, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0012-821X\(97\)00204-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0012-821X(97)00204-5), 1998.
- Zwartz, D. P.: The recent history of the Antarctic ice sheet: constraints from sea-level change, Ph.D. thesis, Australian National University, Canberra, Australia, <https://doi.org/10.25911/5d74e47990bf7>, 1995.
- Žulkus, V. and Girininkas, A.: The coast of the Baltic Sea 10,000 years ago, Klaipėda, Klaipėdos universiteto leidykla, title translated with DeepL, Language: Lithuanian, Title (in original language): Baltijos jūros krantai prieš 10 000 metų, 2012.